

SUPERSHINE

D4.5 SUPERSHINE training toolkit

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- * PU = Public
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 RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
 CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Executive Summary

This deliverable explains how the SUPERSHINE capacity-building toolkit was designed and developed. The toolkit was created to support the sharing of knowledge from the SUPERSHINE project. It brings together contributions from SUPERSHINE experts in four main areas: technical, financial, social, and environmental.

The work was carried out in close collaboration with the expertise partners, the SUPERSHINE lighthouse cities, and municipal experts. ICONS coordinate the final format of the toolkit resources, while WP2 (EEIP) is responsible for uploading and hosting the materials on the SUPERSHINE portal.

To create the toolkit, several surveys in different formats were carried out at the beginning of the process. These surveys helped us check if the proposed topics were useful, if the consortium had enough expertise to cover them, and if any additional topics should be included.

A simple and structured methodology was used to collect, organise, and share project knowledge in line with the DoA. The methodology focuses on identifying the needs of the lighthouse cities, mapping the expertise of the consortium, selecting the most relevant topics, and confirming that the consortium can provide this knowledge. It includes four steps:

- **Knowledge collection:** combining partner expertise with district needs.
- **Topic selection:** using an expertise map and a knowledge matrix.
- **Format definition:** turning the selected content into clear and standardized factsheets under the four project domains.
- **Dissemination:** through follow-up meetings, in-person exchanges, and an online workshop to present the main results.

To support communication and dissemination, an online workshop will be organised. In this session, experts will present the key topics, explain their importance, and show how they can be used in practice.

All resources will be available on the SUPERSHINE portal as part of the project toolkit. This will include the factsheet PDFs, the workshop video, and interactive games designed to help users learn and build their skills.

1. Introduction

This document outlines the core capacity-building activities developed within the SUPERSHINE project. These activities have been carried out in collaboration with the technical partners, the SUPERSHINE lighthouse cities, and municipal experts. The final format of the capacity-building resources is coordinated by ICONS, in collaboration with WP2 (EEIP), which is responsible for uploading the materials to the SUPERSHINE portal.

The toolkit resources will be hosted on a dedicated board within the SUPERSHINE portal, where all materials forming part of the SUPERSHINE capacity-building programme will be made available

1.1. Deliverable's objective

According to the SUPERSHINE Description of Action (DoA), the objective of Task T4.3, “Capacity building on the lighthouse districts”, is to develop a toolkit defined as a set of technical, social, financial, and environmental resources that will support the dissemination of the knowledge generated throughout the SUPERSHINE project. The main purpose of the toolkit is to identify horizontal skill needs and outline the actions required within the project.

All knowledge is identified through the actions and work carried out across the different SUPERSHINE district demonstrators.

- **Italian lighthouse district (Trieste; First photo):** The Italian district includes the retrofitting of eight buildings to provide new social housing for vulnerable families, managed by ATER. The intervention aims to improve energy performance and living conditions.
- **Danish lighthouse district (Herning; Second photo):** The Danish district includes four large housing blocks from the 1950s–1960s. All retrofitting actions were defined together with residents and include facade insulation and an upgraded heating system.
- **Latvian lighthouse district (Riga; Third photo):** The Latvian district is mainly composed of older buildings and shows high energy consumption linked to district heating. Large-scale renovation has not yet started; however, the municipality plans a gradual neighbourhood upgrade in collaboration with an active local community.

Figure 1: Location of the SUPERSHINE lighthouse districts

1.2. Timeline of toolkit task

Before starting the development of the Toolkit activities, a shared timeline was prepared among the SUPERSHINE partners involved in this task. The timeline aims to compile all the work to be carried out from April to December.

Each activity included in the timeline graphic is represented using a different colour and grouped according to the objectives of each task or action. In this timeline, the work is structured into three main components.

- The first component, referred to as “**Task Work**” and shown in red, covers the task-related activities described in the DoA. This group includes information and actions related to activities such as gathering all SUPERSHINE knowledge and organising workshop activities.
- The second component, called “**Portal**”, includes all actions related to the implementation of the toolkit on the SUPERSHINE portal. This work is mainly carried out by EEIP with support from ICONS, which designs and develops the factsheet template.
- Finally, a separate section is dedicated to the work associated with the delivery format of this deliverable, D4.5 SUPERSHINE Training Toolkit, and is labelled as “**D4.5**”.

The milestones are placed at the top of the corresponding months, creating a clear visual marker as the work progresses and is completed. To indicate the progress of each activity, a symbol; either a stack or an hourglass, is used to visually represent the level of completion.

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Figure 2: First part of the timeline showing the work progress of the Toolkit: SUPERSHINE Capacity Building Activity

Figure 3: Second part of the timeline showing the work progress of the Toolkit: SUPERSHINE Capacity Building Activity

2. Methodology

In order to ensure that the knowledge produced within the SUPERSHINE liveable life project is captured and used effectively, a specific methodology was developed in line with the objectives defined in the Description of Action (DoA) for this task. To ensure this alignment, the task description in the DoA was analysed in detail, and a structured methodology was established accordingly.

DoA TASK GOALS	CARTIF METHODOLOGY
<p>1. Develop Capacity-Building Activities: <i>Strengthen skills and competencies across all levels in the lighthouse districts, from residents to organizations, for a sustainable impact.</i></p>	<p>-Identify the needs of the lighthouse cities. -Map the technical expertise of consortium members. -Define the key topics to be covered in this task. -Evaluate the consortium's capacity for knowledge dissemination.</p>
<p>2. Organize diffusion activities (Task 1.4): <i>Conduct dissemination activities focusing on organisational development, human resources, and resident engagement.</i></p>	<p>-LEARNING WAY: Define the methods for sharing knowledge</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Experience Exchange (EE) ▪ Thematic Expert (TE) ▪ Lessons Learned (LL) <p>-LEARNING FORMAT: Define how the methods of each Learning way will be documented</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Webinar/Workshop ▪ Factsheet ▪ Report
<p>3. Create the SUPERSHINE Training Toolkit: <i>Develop a toolkit with all capacity-building materials, accessible through the SUPERSHINE portal.</i></p>	<p>-Standardize formats for reporting this knowledge. -Develop Portal-Ready Formats -Develop the toolkit on the Supershine portal (WP2).</p>

Figure 4: Visual summary of the methodology development, based on an analysis of the DoA objectives and the definition and implementation of the CARTIF methodology

This methodology focuses on identifying the needs of the lighthouse cities, mapping the technical expertise of consortium members, and defining the key capacity-building topics to be addressed. It also assesses the consortium's capacity for knowledge dissemination.

Based on this analysis, different learning approaches were defined, including Experience Exchange, Thematic Experts, and Lessons Learned. These learning approaches are documented through different formats, such as webinars and workshops, factsheets, and reports.

Finally, the methodology supports the development of the SUPERSHINE training toolkit by standardising reporting formats, preparing portal-ready resources, and ensuring that all capacity-building materials are accessible through the SUPERSHINE portal.

- **FIRST STEP: Knowledge** > Key knowledge within the consortium is identified and collected, together with the specific needs of the different SUPERSHINE districts.
- **SECOND STEP: Topics** > The most relevant topics for dissemination are selected. In this step, the partners' technical expertise is mapped, and the interests and needs of the districts are considered. A knowledge matrix is created to identify project expertise profiles and the knowledge needs across the project.
- **THIRD STEP: Format** > The selected content is developed and organised into simple, standardised capacity-building materials and mainly technical factsheets. A common structure is applied, and all materials are categorised under the four technical topics of the project: social, financial, environmental, and technical. This ensures that the materials are consistent, easy to compare, and ready for practical use.
- **FINALLY, FOURTH STEP: Dissemination** > The knowledge produced is disseminated through different activities.
 - Regular follow-up meetings, aligned with the project's monthly meetings, are used to review updates from the different tasks and work packages. Partners' capacities and contributions are also discussed.
 - In-person project meetings held since the start of this task are also used to run capacity-building activities and support knowledge exchange.
 - As the final event of this sub-task, an online workshop will be organised, where the main results will be presented and disseminated.

Figure 5: Capacity building process: Methodology Overview

3.STEP 1 & 2: Knowledge & Topics

This section provides information on the process followed to map the technical expertise of the consortium partner's project and to analyse the consortium's capacity for knowledge dissemination. Jointly with the previous information described in the previous sentences, the identification of the lighthouse cities 'knowledge needs is also included in this section as well.

~OBJECTIVES ADDRESSED THROUGH THE METODOLOGY~

- Identify the needs of the lighthouse cities.
- Map the technical expertise of consortium members.
- Define the key topics to be covered in this task.
- Evaluate the consortium's capacity for knowledge dissemination.
- Defining format of the work:
 - LEARNING WAY: Define the methods for sharing knowledge*
 - LEARNING FORMAT: Define how the methods of each Learning way*
- Standardize formats for reporting this knowledge.
- Develop Portal-Ready Formats develop the toolkit on the Supershine portal (WP2)

3.1.Knowledge Pyramid

SUPERSHINE starts by defining a knowledge pyramid to address the project's knowledge gaps and identify the key technical concepts that require further development. The first draft of this knowledge structure builds on experience from previous European projects (such as NetZeroCities (NZC), mySMARTLife, and Making City, among others) and on the expertise provided by the SUPERSHINE consortium. This expertise is organised across four main dimensions: technical, economic, social, and environmental.

The knowledge pyramid is structured into four main groups that reflect the project's core technical profiles: Energy Efficient Buildings, Low Carbon Districts, Sustainable Lifestyles, and Social Acceptance and Governance. These groups are further broken down into 11 sub-topics and more than 35 thematic areas, creating a clear mapping between consortium expertise and the knowledge needs identified across the SUPERSHINE districts.

Figure 6: CARTIF Knowledge pyramid

This structure helps to define and prioritise the specific knowledge that each methodology needs to enhance. This structure also helps to define and prioritise the specific knowledge that the methodology needs to enhance, guiding the identification of key contents to be addressed within each thematic area. The draft structure is then reviewed with the lighthouse districts and the relevant partners to confirm priorities and ensure that the selected topics respond to practical needs.

Based on this validated mapping, the project defines the most suitable learning routes (e.g., Experience Exchange, Thematic Experts, and Lessons Learned) and translates the selected content into standardised outputs, mainly technical factsheets and portal-ready resources.

Once these thematic areas and their interconnections are established, a core methodology is developed to ensure the comprehensive consolidation of knowledge across all areas.

Figure 7: Organisational structure of thematic knowledge in SUPERSHINE

3.2. Partners' role

The consortium partners' roles change significantly from one European project to another. Companies usually develop and enhance their knowledge, and in each project they may take on different roles to manage specific tasks. For this reason, the capacity-building methodology includes a review of each partner's technical profile.

The technical profile of the different partners involved in the SUPERSHINE project was identified using two methods:

- A table was shared within the project so that each partner involved in the task could rate the relevance of several predefined topics and indicate their level of expertise in each one.

			CONSORTIUM MEMBERS																	
			CARTIF		CIV		APRE		UYV		DMR		ATER		FB		CRCE		EGC	
			Importance	Expertise	Importance	Expertise	Importance	Expertise	Importance	Expertise	Importance	Expertise	Importance	Expertise	Importance	Expertise	Importance	Expertise	Importance	Expertise
ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS	Energy efficiency and used of resources	Insulation																		
		Change windows and doors																		
		Control system																		
	Integration of Renewables	High-Efficiency																		
		Solar Panels (PV-Thermal)																		
		Wind Energy (Floor-Wall)																		
Architectural aspect	Other Renewables (Geothermal - Biomass)																			
	Envelope Enhancement																			
	Light																			
LOW CARBON DISTRICTS	Decarbonisation	Control system																		
		Architectural Design																		
		Urban Districts																		
	Implemented pedestrian and bicycle way	Decarbonisation of heating																		
		Decarbonisation of transport																		
		Carbon Capture in industry																		
District Heating	Reduction of GHG emissions																			
	Workshop																			
	Brussels																			
SUSTAINABLE LIFESTYLES	Green Areas	Change station																		
		Energy Generation																		
		Distribution Networks																		
	Energy behaviours	Heat Exchange																		
		Co-generation																		
		Air Quality																		
SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE AND	Life-cycle Thinking and circularity	Urban Green Areas System																		
		Urban Water System																		
		Ecosystem Services																		
	Affordability	Urban Ecosystem																		
		Lighting control (Natural/Artificial)																		
		Regular maintenance of Energy																		
Economic Models	Educate in energy saving practices																			
	Light-Cycle Analysis																			
	Resource Management																			

Figure 8: Capture of Expertise Table

			CARTIF		
			Importance	Expertise	Importance
ENERGY EFFICIENT	Energy efficiency and used of resources	Insulation			
		Change windows and doors			
		Control system			
	Integration of Renewables	High-Efficiency			
		Solar Panels (PV-Thermal)			
		Wind Energy (Floor-Wall)			
		Other Renewables (Geothermal -			

Figure 9: Expertise table - Importance of each topic

			CARTIF		
			Importance	Expertise	Importance
ENERGY EFFICIENT	Energy efficiency and used of resources	Insulation			
		Change windows and doors			
		Control system			
		High-Efficiency			
		Solar Panels (PV-Thermal)			

Figure 10: Expertise table - Partner Expertise Levels

- The second method was implemented during one of the in-person meetings, where CARTIF conducted a workshop to collect data and verify the information included in the table explained before. This workshop is described in the following sections 4.2 IN-PERSON workshop: Copenhagen workshop this deliverable, under the name Copenhagen Workshop.

4.Step 2: Check topics and knowledge format

This section mainly describes the objectives and results obtained during the Copenhagen workshop. The event was used as an opportunity to review and confirm the role of each partner in the SUPERSHINE consortium, and to check which topics can be covered by the partners and which ones are seen as the most relevant to disseminate.

At the same time, the best formats for sharing this knowledge were discussed and agreed, and some initial ideas on the graphic design of the main resources were also explored.

~OBJECTIVES ADDRESSED THROUGH THE METODOLOGY~

- Identify the needs of the lighthouse cities.
- Map the technical expertise of consortium members
- Define the key topics to be covered in this task
- Evaluate the consortium's capacity for knowledge dissemination
- Defining format of the work:
 - LEARNING WAY: Define the methods for sharing knowledge
 - LEARNING FORMAT: Define how the methods of each Learning way
- Standardize formats for reporting this knowledge.
- Develop Portal-Ready Formats Develop the toolkit on the Supershine portal (WP2)

4.1.Web-based Excel file

The first method is a web-based Excel file where SUPERSHINE partners can provide input on the importance of each topic and indicate their level of expertise. These topics correspond to the initial structure of the technical knowledge pyramid.

Subsection 3.2. Partners' role provides a detailed explanation of this approach to organising information and checking each partner's profile.

4.2.IN-PERSON workshop: Copenhagen workshop

The second method is an **IN-PERSON workshop** held during one of the consortium meetings in Copenhagen. This physical session allowed participants to exchange ideas, discuss technical content, and share knowledge directly with each other.

Figure 11: SUPERSHINE consortium in-person meeting at the Copenhagen conference

The platform used to develop this workshop was Miro, an online collaborative tool that allows multiple users to work together in real time. It offers a wide range of visual boards, templates, and design frameworks that help organise information, share ideas, and support knowledge-building. The platform is especially useful for workshops and co-creation sessions, as it enables interactive participation, structured discussions, and the collective development of content in a clear and visual way.

The workshop was developed on the Miro platform and structured into five separate boards, each with a specific purpose. First, one board was used to confirm the role of each consortium partner within the SUPERSHINE project. Second, another board was used to review the relevance of the proposed list of topics and to give partners the option to suggest additional topics that they considered important. Third, a dedicated board showed each partner's level of expertise in relation to the proposed topics. Fourth, another board explored which formats the consortium prefers to use to disseminate knowledge and support learning through the capacity-building activities. Finally, one board was used to review the graphic design options for each potential format.

- **BOARD 1:** Partners 'role
- **BOARD 2:** Relevance of each topic
- **BOARD 3:** Partner expertise
- **BOARD 4:** Knowledge format
- **BOARD 5:** Knowledge design

At the end of the workshop, we created an additional board to evaluate the workshop's overall impact. This evaluation was carried out at the end of the session. It is not a main part of the capacity-building framework and did not provide key results for the analysis. However,

the results should be included in an annex to show the group work and to support the continuous capacity-building process.

Figure 12: Miro board with all the information about the Copenhagen workshop

4.3.Consolidated Results of the Thematic Workshop

After the workshop, we reviewed all the input collected, including what was discussed, voted on, and shared, as well as the comments raised during the workshop and the general consortium meeting. Based on this information, the answers were grouped into knowledge blocks to make the methodology easier to apply.

4.4.SUPERSHINE technical knowledge and expertise

From the topics identified, each partner indicated the areas in which they had expertise. Based on this information, we created a 'second and final knowledge pyramid of the consortium. This helped us to see which topics are well covered and where we might need help or work more closely with other partners.

TOPIC		PARTNERS - TECHNICAL INFORMATION																			
		CARTIF	EMA	HE	SP	EGG	APRE	IGORS	INSPE	ATHING	UeY	DEMR	GRCE	ATER	REA	KM	TENDER	ZF	FB		
ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS	Energy efficiency Interventions	Envelope insulation		X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X					
		Change window and door		X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				
		Control System		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				X
		Restoration of heating system				X		X				X			X	X				X	
		Restoration of technical infrastructure						X				X			X						
		Manual controls																		X	
	Integration of Renewable	Solar Panels (PV-Thermal, others)		X	X	X		X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X
		Wind energy		X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X			
		Other Renewable (Geothermal, Biomass, ...)		X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X			
		Individual heating system based on renewables																		X	
		Energy communities		X				X	X			X			X	X		X	X		
		Share of self-consumption																		X	
	Architectural Aspects	Envelope Enhancement (glass and other materials, etc.)		X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X			X
		NBS		X	X	X		X		X	X	X		X	X	X	X				
		Architectural Durian (New Building)		X	X	X	X	X		X	X		X	X		X	X	X			
		Urban Durian		X	X	X	X	X		X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X			
		Overseer conservation approach			X			X								X					
		Technical conservation														X					
Fire risk w. efficiency of the envelope																			X		
General Aspects	Decarbonisation and Efficiency Energy Use		X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X		
	Carbon capture in Industry		X	X			X		X	X	X	X	X		X			X			
	Reduction of GHG emissions		X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X			X			
	Public energy poverty				X		X				X			X	X						

Figure 13: Topic classification by interest level in the consortium

Information about the expertise available in the consortium was also included. The voted topics were matched with the areas of knowledge identified by each partner, and it was confirmed that all topics are fully covered. No gaps in expertise were found. This verification

was based on the results from the workshop and on the web-based Excel file (3.2 Partners' role).

TOPIC		PARTNERS - TECHNICAL INFORMATION																			
		CARTIF	EMA	HE	SP	EGC	APRE	ICONS	IRSMI	ATMING	UoY	DEMIR	CIRCE	ATER	REA	KM	TENDER	ZP	FB		
SUSTAINABLE LIFESTYLES	Green Area	Air Quality																			
		Urban Green Area System			X																
		Urban Water system																			
		Ecosystem Services								X											
		Urban ecosystem			X		X	X	X												
		Recycling building materials	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?
	Energy behaviour	Best practices of Energy Facilities					X		X	X											X
	Educate in energy saving practices			X		X	X	X													
SOCIAL ACCEPT	Life-cycle Thinking and circularity	Life-Cycle Analysis		X			X		X	X	X			X		X					
		Circular economy		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X		X					
		GHG accounting and reduction	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	
		Operational economic, social and environmental LCA	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	
		Air quality	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	
		Economic value from repairing, reusing and recycling of materials	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	2?	

Figure 14: Match between topics and consortium expertise

4.5. Evaluation and categorisation of Topics

Each topic was classified according to the level of interest it generated within the consortium. A scoring model was developed to assign a value to each topic, allowing them to be grouped into three levels of importance: high, medium, or low. Based on this, the topics were prioritised as follows:

- **HIGH-SCORING TOPICS:** These attracted the most interest. Technical factsheets will be developed for them, and they will also be explored further during specific workshops.
- **MEDIUM-SCORING TOPICS:** These will be addressed through technical factsheets, but no workshops will be organised for them.
- **LOW-SCORING TOPICS:** These were not considered relevant for the consortium at this stage and will not be further developed.

As the graph below shows, it is important to say that some topics have a double evaluation. This is because they were scored twice: first in a pre-evaluation, and then again during the Copenhagen workshop. For this reason, some topics have a maximum score of 4 (only one score), while others can reach a maximum of 10 (two scores added). The “High” label shows priority, not the exact number, so different scores can still be marked as “High”.

		TOPIC	
ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS	Energy efficiency Interventions	Envelope Insulation	4.00 High
		Change windows and doors	3.00 Medium
		Control system	2.00 Medium
	Integration of Renewables	Solar Panels (PV-Thermal, others)	4.00 High
		Other Renewables (Geothermal, Biomass...)	3.00 Medium
		Envelope Enhancement (glazed enclosures, shading elements, others)	4.00 High
	Architectural Aspect	Architectural Design (New Bauhaus)	2.00 Medium
		Urban Design	4.00 High
		Quarter renovation approach	4.00 High
ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS	Energy efficiency Interventions	Renovation of technical infrastructure (wiring, pipes)	3.00 Medium
		Renovation of heating system	3.00 Medium
		Cooling in residential building	1.00 Low
	Integration of Renewables	Energy communities and self-consumption	13.00 High
		Self-heating in social housing (Gas/electricity)	1.00 Low
	Architectural Aspect	Scientific renovation	1.00 Low
LOW CARBON DISTRICTS	General Aspects	Decarbonisation and Efficiency Energy Use	4.00 High
		Smart Grids	1.00 Low
	Implemented pedestrian and bicycle way	Reduction of GHG emissions	3.00 Medium
		Walkways	0.00 Low
		Bikeways	1.00 Low
	District Heating	Decarbonisation of transport	2.00 Medium
	Energy Generation	1.00 Low	
	Distribution Networks	1.00 Low	
	Energy Efficiency	0.00 Low	

Figure 15: Topic prioritisation results based on consortium interest levels

Then, after evaluating all topics using the scoring method, the following topics were selected by category. A screenshot of the summary table is attached, showing the four main categories, the corresponding topic for each one, and the full list of topics included.

		TOPIC
ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS	Energy efficiency Interventions	Envelope Insulation
	Integration of Renewables	Solar Panels (PV-Thermal, others)
		Energy communities and self-consumption
	Architectural Aspect	Envelope Enhancement (glazed enclosures, shading elements, others)
		Urban Design
Quarter renovation approach		
LOW CARBON DISTRICTS	General Aspects	Decarbonisation and Efficiency Energy Use
		Smart Grids
SUSTAINABLE LIFESTYLES	Green Areas	Recycling building materials
SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE AND GOVERNANCE	Life-cycle Thinking and circularity	GHG measuring and reduction (Scopes 1,2,3)
		Air quality
	Affordability	Grants / Funding availability

Figure 16: Topic prioritisation results based on consortium interest levels

Finally, each expert in the project was given the opportunity to refine and streamline the themes. The aim was to ensure that the technical evaluation relevant to each topic was

properly considered, to avoid duplication, and to provide the most concise and clear information for every topic. Below, the final list of topics is attached, together with the assignment of each one to the technical partners of the project.

		TOPIC	Main
ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS	1. Envelope insulation and enhancement	Change windows and doors	CARTIF
		Envelope control system (Automatic blinds and adjustable slats)	
		Glazed enclosures	
		Shading elements	
		Green façades	
	2. Integration of Renewables	Solar Panels (PV-Thermal...)	CARTIF
		Other Renewables (Geothermal, Biomass...)	
		Energy communities (a neighbourhood-level model for renewable energy sharing)	
	3. New Design Paradigm	Architectural and Urban Design (New Bauhaus)	DEMIR
NBS			
LOW CARBON DISTRICTS	4. Urban Decarbonisation	Decarbonisation and Efficient Energy Use	CIRCE
		Decarbonisation of Transport	
	5. Sustainable mobility	Walkways	CIRCE
		Bikeways	
		Micro-Mobility and new mobility infrastructure	
	6. District Heating and Cooling Networks	Energy Generation	CARTIF
		Distribution Networks	
Heat Exchange			
SUSTAINABLE LIFESTYLES	7. Urban Green Infrastructure	Urban Green Areas System (green roofs, community gardens)	DEMIR
		Urban Ecosystem (Interrelation between green areas, water bodies, biodiversity, and human activity in the urban environment)	
	8. Energy Use: Improving Behaviours	Good Use of Energy and Energy Facilities: Best Practices and Educational Activities	CIRCE
ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT	9. Life-cycle Thinking and circularity	Life-Cycle Analysis (embodied energy)	CIRCE
		Recycling and Re-Use (Users)	UoY
		Circular economy	
	10. Waste: End of life phase	Waste reduction	DEMIR
		Waste Management (Sorting, Recycling, Composting, others...)	
		Waste Recovery and Valorisation	
	11. Economic Aspects of Energy Actions	Economic Models	UoY
		Reducing Energy Poverty	
Grants and Funding Availability			
SMEs (Small and Medium-sized Enterprises)		INSME	

Figure 17: List of topics selected for the next phase of the SUPERSHINE toolkit

5.Step 3: Format and Technical factsheets

First, the topics to be developed in the project were evaluated together with each technical partner. The partners and cities in the consortium were also considered. Based on this, the most suitable format to share the project knowledge was selected.

5.1.Selection of the dissemination format

During the workshop in Copenhagen, held in person, the consortium evaluated the dissemination approach. Two boards were used. The first one (Board 4) showed a simple matrix linking different learning methods to different content formats. The second board and the final part of the workshop template were used to explore the best layout and format to present this knowledge. Both boards are described in section 4.2. (*IN-PERSON workshop: Copenhagen workshop*). In this section, the results taken from this part of the workshop are presented.

5.2.Knowledge format

To understand the format preferred by the consortium for knowledge dissemination, a matrix was used. In this matrix, each learning way was linked to a learning format. As main preferences, Experience Exchange and Thematic Experts were chosen by the partners. These were mostly linked to a webinar format and to reports. It was also agreed that these reports should include lessons learnt and experience exchange. Only after reviewing the matrix were these preferences confirmed.

Figure 18: Matrix linking “Learning Way” and “Learning Format”, used during the Copenhagen workshop to identify preferred dissemination mixes

5.3. Design learning format

Graphic evaluation was carried out by the partners, and it was found that the consortium prefers dissemination documents with strong visual content. It was agreed that text should be reduced as much as possible, keeping only what is really needed.

In addition, any element that can present information mainly through graphics was evaluated positively. Clear and concise visuals, with short and concrete messages, were seen as the best option.

5.4. Factsheet

After the format and the information to be included in the dissemination documents were evaluated and identified, it was decided that the best way to disseminate knowledge in this project is through technical factsheets. These factsheets will be uploaded to the project portal and compiled into a good practice book.

5.5. Factsheet template

The factsheet is divided into two parts: a summary version and a complete version. This supports quick sharing and more detailed technical work. In both versions, the thematic area and main topic are clearly stated, and the action is explained in technical terms, with images or diagrams to make it easier to understand.

The content is organised into clear implementation phases. In the complete version, these phases include specific tasks, indicative timings, and a simple Gantt plan. The factsheet also provides practical recommendations to adapt the action to different cities, and a simple scoring of difficulty, cost, environmental impact, and social acceptance, with further explanation in the complete version. To support replication, it also includes common risks, links with related actions, relevant policies, stakeholder roles, and external references and good practice examples.

The factsheet template shared with the project partners is attached below. It includes the template and guidance notes explaining what information should be included in each SUPERSHINE factsheet.

● **SUMMARY FACTSHEET**

Table 1: Summary factsheet part: Description

Thematic Area	MAIN TOPIC
Short technical description	
<i>A description of the technical action should be included. (2-3 paragraph)</i>	
Technical diagram	
<i>Include a diagram/photo that best summarises the information related to the main topic.</i>	

● **TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE**

Table 2: Summary factsheet part: Phases of implementation

Phases of implementation	
P1	Descriptive name: Phase nameInclude information...
P1.1	XX: Sub-Phase name
P1.2	XX: Sub-Phase name
P1.3	XX: Sub-Phase name
P2	Descriptive name: Phase nameInclude information...
P2.1	XX: Sub-Phase name
...	
Px	XX: xx
PX.x	XX: Sub-Phase name

** In this section, This section should describe the main steps to carry out the selected action. Organise the information into clear phases and sub-phases, using short and simple titles. Keep the descriptions general – Avoid technical language and specific dates.*

Make sure the steps follow a logical order (for example: assessment → planning → implementation → monitoring).

If you are working with more than one topic, you can use a different table for each topic to make everything clearer.

● **KNOWLEDGE RECOMMENDATIONS**

Table 3: Summary factsheet part: Recommendations

RECOMMENDATIONS
<i>This section provides general recommendations, identifies potential challenges, and explains how to adapt the action for successful implementation across different cities. It may also serve as a summary of the full set of recommendations.</i>

• SCORING

* This part can be evaluated using a scale, considering all the subtopics described within the main topic. In addition, specific evaluations may be provided for each subtopic, especially if they are further developed in detail.

Table 4: Summary factsheet part: Scoring

<p><i>Difficulty level</i></p>	
<p><i>Environmental impact</i></p>	

• COMPLETE FACHTSHEET

Table 5: Complete factsheet: Description

Thematic Area	MAIN TOPIC
DESCRIPTION	
Technical description	
<p><i>Describe all technical aspects and objectives of the action. Use clear, non-high-level language when possible. (Expected length 2 or 3 pages)</i></p> <p><i>Include all visual information necessary to explain the action. Include any diagrams/photos that best sum up the main topics' information</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>[...Insert photo/s here...]</i></p>	
SCORING	
Technical Scoring	
<p><i>Include information about technical difficulty of implementation. Include aspects such as technical complexity, level of expertise, integration with existing systems... The description should reflect and justify the score selected in the short factsheet version.</i></p>	
Finance Scoring	
<p><i>Include information about the estimated cost of implementation. Include aspects such as initial investment, operational and maintenance costs, and potential needs for external funding... The description should reflect and justify the score selected in the short factsheet version.</i></p>	
Environment Scoring	
<p><i>Include information about the environmental impact of the solution. Include aspects such as emissions, resource consumption, waste generation, and contribution to sustainability goals... The description should reflect and justify the score selected in the short factsheet version.</i></p>	
Social Scoring	
<p><i>Include information about social acceptance and societal integration. Include aspects such as public perception, ease of adoption, alignment with social values or regulatory norms... The description should reflect and justify the score selected in the short factsheet version.</i></p>	

CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND	
Recurrent risks	
<p><i>Frequent risks during implementation may include technical difficulties, budget limitations, resistance from end-users, or legal restrictions. These should be considered to adapt the solution realistically to its context.</i></p> <p><i>City issues like traffic, lack of green areas, or poor housing</i></p> <p><i>Environmental problems like pollution or climate risks</i></p> <p><i>Management gaps like weak planning or low citizen involvement</i></p> <p><i>Obsolete technologies with high energy consumption or that fail to meet current standards.</i></p>	

- **TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE**

Table 6: Complete factsheet: Phases of implementation

Phases of implementation	
P1	Descriptive name: Phase name Include information...
¿XX? Describe the phase and include technical information or values that allow for the installation of the main topic	
P1.1	XX: Sub-Phase name
	¿XX?
P1.2	XX: Sub-Phase name
	¿XX?
P1.3	XX: Sub-Phase name
	¿XX?
P2	Descriptive name: Phase name Include information...
¿XX? Describe the phase and include technical information or values that allow for the installation of the main topic	
P2.1	XX: Sub-Phase name
	¿XX?
...	... : ...
	...
Px	XX: xx
¿XX? Describe the phase and include technical information or values that allow for the installation of the main topic	
...	... : ...
	...

** Refer to the simplified overview of implementation steps provided in the Summary Factsheet for a quick understanding of the sub-blocks involved. In this section, each sub-block should be expanded into concrete phases with a clear title, estimated duration, and a concise description of the technical tasks. This will ensure continuity between both versions and support cities in adapting the action to their local conditions and capacities.*

If you consider that this section is not relevant to your topic, you may modify it or replace it with a more appropriate structure. Additionally, if you believe that more subtopics or more than two levels of sub-sections are needed, feel free to include them.

- **GANTT**

*GANTT: include as many Phases as indicated on the previous section and place them in time. Make the table as long as needed and use months/semesters/ years as needed

If you consider that this section is not relevant for your topic, you may modify it or replace it with a more suitable structure.

Table 7: Complete factsheet: Gantt

		M1	Mx											
P1	[...Phase name...]													
	P.1.1 [...Sub-Phase name...]													
	P.1.2 [...Sub-Phase name...]													
	P.1.3 [...Sub-Phase name...]													
	P.1.4 [...Sub-Phase name...]													
P2	[...Phase name...]													
	P.2.1 [...Sub-Phase name...]													
	P.2.2 [...Sub-Phase name...]													
	P.2.3 [...Sub-Phase name...]													
	P.2.4 [...Sub-Phase name...]													
Px	[...Phase name...]													
	P.X.x [...Sub-Phase name...]													
	P.X.x [...Sub-Phase name...]													
	P.X.x [...Sub-Phase name...]													
	P.X.x [...Sub-Phase name...]													

- **STRATEGIC**

Table 8: Complete factsheet: Recommendations

RECOMMENDATIONS			
DOs	Include information related to the base city context that allows the implementation of the main topic		DON'Ts
			Include information about disadvantages of implementing this action

- **CROSS-LINK MATRIX BETWEEN TECHNICAL ACTIONS**

* This section includes the interrelations between the main topic and other subtopics. For each related item, specify the type of relationship using the legend above the table:

- R = Related
- NR = Not significantly related
- S = Synergy (strong positive interaction)
- C = Complementary or coordination advised

Below each code, include a brief comment explaining how the two actions are functionally or technically connected.

This section should be included if this information is relevant and applicable for the topic&subtopics

Table 9: Complete factsheet: Cross link matrix

Main Topic ↓ Related →	PHASE NAME 1	Ex: GREEN FAÇADES	PHASE NAME 3	PHASE NAME 4
BIOPHILIC ARCHITECTURE	Relation type	Ex: S Synergy		
	<i>Brief comment about link synergies</i>	<i>Strong visual and ecological harmony.</i>		
PHASE NAME 2				
PHASE NAME 3				
PHASE NAME 4				

- POLICY FRAMEWORK

Table 10: Complete factsheet: Policy framework

Relevant Policies
<p><i>*If you are aware of, please include any relevant regulation applicable to this measure/solution. You don't need to explain it in depth</i></p> <p><i>The main topic can be linked to several strategic frameworks and policies at different levels.</i></p>
<p>International level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>At the international level, it may align with the European Green Deal, the 2030 Agenda and its Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the New European Bauhaus, the Paris Agreement and COP climate goals, UN-Habitat's New Urban Agenda, the Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy, the Resilient Cities Network, or the Just Transition Framework.</i>
<p>European level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>At the European sectoral level, relevant references may include the EU Urban Mobility Framework, the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, the Smart Cities Marketplace, the EU Biodiversity Strategy, the Fit for 55 Package, the EU Climate Adaptation Strategy, REPowerEU, the Renovation Wave initiative, and the Digital Europe Programme.</i>
<p>National level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>At the national or regional level, the topic may relate to National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs), Climate Adaptation Plans, Urban Agendas, Smart City strategies, Sustainable Mobility</i>

<i>Plans, Circular Economy roadmaps, national Green Deals or climate legislation, or investment frameworks such as the NextGenerationEU recovery funds.</i>
Local level
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At the local level, supporting references may include Local Climate Action Plans (SECAP or PACES), Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP), strategies for renaturalisation or green infrastructure, Smart City action plans, Local Urban Agendas (such as Agenda 21), as well as local housing, energy renovation, regeneration, digitalisation or open data strategies.

● **STAKEHOLDER ROLES AND ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK**

** This section defines the key stakeholders required for the successful implementation of the action, clarifying their responsibilities and levels of involvement. Understanding the roles of public, private, and civil society actors ensures coordinated delivery and promotes social acceptance.*

Table 11: Complete factsheet: Stakeholder roles and engagement framework

Stakeholder	Role	Type of Collaboration
STAKEHOLDER 1	Regulation, co-financing, project lead	Regulatory / Financial
STAKEHOLDER 2		
STAKEHOLDER X		
...		

● **MAIN REFERENCES**

Table 12: Complete factsheet: Good Practices

GOOD PRACTICES / SOME EXAMPLES
Project
<p><i>[...Insert information about a project that has implemented the main action. Include name, location brief description and link if available....]</i></p> <p><i>Project name: xxx</i> <i>Location: xxx</i> <i>Description: xxx</i> <i>Link: xxx</i></p>
Web-site
<p><i>[...Include a website that offers high-quality, up-to-date information on the main topic....]</i></p> <p><i>Website: xxx</i> <i>Link: xxx</i> <i>Description: xxx</i></p>
Paper
<p><i>[...Reference a scientific or technical paper that provides detailed analysis, data, or evaluation of the action. Include full citation in APA format if possible....]</i></p>

Paper title: xxx
Authors: xxx
Journal: xxx
DOI or link: xxx

*Provide examples of relevant projects, websites, or academic papers that showcase the application of this action in real contexts. Include links and short summaries.

- **KEY CONSIDERATIONS**

* If you consider that there is additional information that should be included in this factsheet, you may add it in this section

Table 13: Complete factsheet: Additional notes

Additional Notes
¿XX? ...

5.6. Factsheet dissemination

Dissemination of the factsheets is centrally coordinated by ICONS in close alignment with the overall SUPERSHINE Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy. The dissemination approach is designed to ensure wide visibility, ease of access, and effective uptake of the project’s knowledge outputs by diverse target audiences, including policy makers, public authorities, housing providers, practitioners, and other non-technical stakeholders.

Each factsheet is organised according to a modular and layered structure, designed to address the needs of different target audiences and levels of technical expertise.

The structure includes:

- **Summary of the Factsheet:** A concise and visually engaging overview presenting the key messages, main insights, and policy- or practice-relevant takeaways. This section is designed for rapid consumption by non-technical audiences and serves as the primary dissemination asset.
- **Complete Factsheet:** The full version of the factsheet, providing detailed information, technical explanations, data, and contextual analysis. This section is intended for stakeholders requiring a deeper understanding of the topic, including practitioners, experts, and technical staff.

Dissemination of the factsheets will be implemented through a combination of digital channels and project activities to maximise their reach and impact. Both the summary

version and the complete factsheet will be made available on the SUPERSHINE portal and promoted through the project's newsletters and social media channels.

The visually engaging Summary of the Factsheet will function as the main entry point for dissemination, supported by a clear Call to Action directing interested stakeholders to the complete version for further exploration.

In addition, the factsheets will be actively used and referenced within SUPERSHINE training activities, workshops, and capacity-building sessions, ensuring their integration into broader knowledge-transfer actions and supporting the effective uptake of project results beyond the project consortium.

5.7. Supershine Portal Toolkit

The training toolkit is delivered as a consolidated PDF report that summarises a set of **capacity-building** and **knowledge-transfer** activities developed during the project's lifetime. The SUPERSHINE Training Toolkit is positioned as a comprehensive **capacity-building report** that captures and structures key results and **learnings** generated across multiple workstreams, rather than being a course or a single-**purpose** document. Not only does it serve as a reference document, but it also provides a practical resource for stakeholders seeking to replicate, adapt or scale relevant practices beyond the project's duration.

The toolkit will be uploaded and made publicly available via the official project website (<https://super-i-supershine.eu/>).

Figure 19: Screen capture of the SUPERSHINE headline linked to the project social media platform

Following the **conclusion of SUPERSHINE** in March 2026, the toolkit is intended to form part of the project's business exploitation activities, supporting post-project uptake and longer-term value creation. At the time of writing, the exploitation route hasn't yet been finalised. Potential implementation approaches may include direct hosting on the project website, integration into a partner platform, or inclusion within a **portfolio of exploitable project results**; however, the final configuration will be selected based on feasibility and stakeholder needs identified at the end of the project.

Importantly, regardless of which exploitation pathway is adopted, **the consortium commits to maintaining public accessibility of the toolkit** at least until March 2029, ensuring continued access for target audiences and enabling sustained dissemination, reuse, and impact. This **approach** supports the project's long-term **capacity-building** objectives and ensures that the toolkit continues to deliver benefits beyond the formal end of SUPERSHINE.

6.STEP 4: Dissemination

An online dissemination workshop will be held on 14 January 2026, where each partner will present one selected topic. This deliverable includes the event organisation.

6.1.Promotion of the Workshop

Dissemination activities for the workshop were coordinated and implemented by ICONS. These included a targeted social media campaign on LinkedIn, featuring dedicated visual cards for each speaker and their respective sessions, as well as the distribution of a project newsletter aimed at gathering participants and promoting registration.

In line with the workshop dissemination protocol, ICONS also mobilised its internal Energy Cluster, engaged with the sister projects DRop and ProLight, and activated the relevant networks in which SUPERSHINE participates. All these stakeholders were informed about the event to maximise visibility, encourage participation, and strengthen cross-project synergies.

6.2.Workshop structure

For this activity, a workshop was designed and structured around three technical expert areas. The environmental part is covered by two project partners, each presenting a different perspective, one at municipal scale and the other at building scale.

This content is then complemented by a technical session, and it closes with a technical assessment that supports the discussion of the financial impact. The workshop follows a short, focused presentation format by each expert, and ends with an interactive game to help participants reinforce the key messages and check the knowledge gained during the session.

The event agenda is attached below to clearly present the structure of the session, the participation of the different speakers, and the topic selected by each partner in the consortium.

Table 14: Event agenda and session structure

TIME	ACTIVITY	DETAILS
13:00-13:05 5 min	Welcome	Welcome all participants and open the session
	SUPERSHINE project	Short presentation of the SUPERSHINE project
	Session information	Presentation of the session's objectives and structure

ENVIRONMENTAL PART		
13:05-13:25		
19 min	DEMIR Welcome	Speaker: Esra Özkul Demir
	Urban green infrastructure	
1 min	<i>Wrap-Up Game</i>	
TECHNICAL PART		
13:25-13:45		
19 min	CARTIF Welcome	Speakers: Ana Gómez
	Envelope insulation and enhancement	
1 min	<i>Wrap-Up Game</i>	
ENVIRONMENTAL PART		
13:45-14:05		
20 min	CIRCE Welcome	Speaker: Eva Roldán Saso
	Urban Decarbonisation	
FINANCIAL PART		
14:05-14:25		
19 min	UoY Welcome	Speakers: Paola Zerilli and Ahmed Djeddi
	Improving social housing with public-private funding to reduce energy poverty	
1 min	<i>Wrap-Up Game</i>	
Q&A		
14:25-14:30 5 min	Questions and Conclusions	

Figure 23: Event agenda and session structure

6.3. Topics formats

Based on the agenda and the four presentations, the online workshop will be organised as a series of short expert blocks delivered by partners from different consortium organisations, each focused on a specific SUPERSHINE topic.

The session will open with the partner from DEMIR in the environmental part, who will present Urban Green Infrastructure, explaining what it is, why it matters for cities, its main benefits, and the key steps from planning and design to construction and long-term maintenance. It will then continue with the partner from CARTIF in the technical part on Envelope Insulation and Enhancement, who will explain the value of improving building façades, the main retrofit solutions (such as ETICS, better windows, shading systems, green

facades, and smart technologies), expected energy savings, and the general implementation phases, risks, and recommendations.

After that, the partner from CIRCE will provide a second environmental perspective on Urban Decarbonisation, describing the city decarbonisation challenge and an integrated approach that combines energy efficiency, electrification, clean district energy, flexibility, circularity, and zero-emission mobility, together with practical phases for implementation and support for municipalities. Finally, the partner from the University of York will deliver the financial block on improving social housing through public–private funding to reduce energy poverty, presenting how PPP models such as shared-savings and guaranteed-savings contracts can finance renovation, what types of investment are involved, and how impacts on energy use and energy poverty will be assessed.

As planned in the agenda, the main blocks will be followed by short wrap-up quizzes or interactive games to reinforce key messages and check learning, and the workshop will close with a brief Q&A for questions and conclusions.

6.4. Mock session

A test version of this session was held with internal project participants only on 24 November, from 13:00 to 14:30. During this rehearsal, the meeting settings were checked, internal participation was confirmed, and the date and time of the final event were agreed and scheduled.

Figure 20: Screenshot from the mock session of the workshop

Conclusions

The SUPERSHINE capacity-building toolkit has helped the project collect and organise useful knowledge from the project experts and the lighthouse districts. Through surveys, topic selection, and the creation of clear factsheets, the project experience has been turned into simple and practical resources that can support cities and other stakeholders.

Work was done together with the expert partners, the lighthouse cities, and municipal experts. This helped make sure the toolkit answers real needs and uses the knowledge available in the consortium. The step-by-step methodology also helped to select the most relevant topics, agree on the best format, and prepare the materials in a consistent way.

The online workshop will help share the main results and show how the selected topics can be used in practice. It will also support communication and make the toolkit more visible.

All materials will be available on the SUPERSHINE portal. Users will be able to access the factsheets, the workshop video recording, and interactive learning tools. By keeping everything in one organised place, the toolkit supports long-term learning and helps cities build their capacity to use the knowledge developed in SUPERSHINE.

Annex I: Reference Capacity-Building Web services

The goal of Task T4.3 is achieved by using three platforms as references. All of them are used to share knowledge in different contexts: European cities, citizens from a specific European region (such as Catalonia), or one of the states in the American continent:

1. **NZC portal:** The NZC project created a simple and practical website where cities and project partners can share useful information and important documents. The goal is to support a group of cities that want to reach climate neutrality by 2030. Their knowledge and experience will later help other European cities work towards the same goal by 2050.

Link: [NetZeroCities](https://netzerocities.com)

Figure 27: Capture of NZC online platform

2. **Catalan Energy Institute:** The Catalan Energy Institute aims to improve energy efficiency, strengthen the use of renewable resources, and promote the transition towards a sustainable and decarbonised energy model in the region. On the organisation's website, users can find key energy concepts, information about self-consumption, energy companies, and a summary of the energy regulatory framework, among other services.

Link: [L'energia](https://lenergia.cat).

Figure 28: Capture of Catalan energy institute

- Massachusetts Clean Energy Center:** The state of Massachusetts, in collaboration with the Massachusetts Clean Energy Centre and the Massachusetts Department of Energy Resources, developed a platform where residents could access information on renewable energy resources and the impact of installing such facilities. This section also provides details on how the state of Massachusetts could reduce its GHG emissions and what actions residents can implement to help reduce them.

Link: [Solar Electricity - Massachusetts Clean Energy Center](#)

Figure 29: Capture of Massachusetts, clean energy centre

Annex II: Copenhagen Workshop results obtained

The Copenhagen workshop is structured around some dashboards, developed to collect data on specific aspects of capacity development. Each dashboard is designed to collect a particular type of data and generate results related to the main capacity development objective of the Task 4.3 toolkit.

1st MIRO BOARD: Expert Role

This board is designed to gather feedback on the role of SUPERSHINE partners. It is structured into three main groups:

Figure 21: Frist Miro Board: Expertise Role

- **Cities:** Divided into SUPERSHINE Lighthouse and Fellow districts, with each city partner represented. This group aims to identify which partners are linked to each SUPERSHINE municipality.
- **Municipality Partners:** This group follows the same structure as the Cities section but is intended to include partners who work externally with municipalities. These institutions typically provide technical expertise to municipalities and play an important role in disseminating technical knowledge within the project.
- **Technical Partners:** This section is divided into four thematic areas; financial, technical, social, and environmental. Each partner is asked to indicate their primary area(s) of expertise.

Based on the information above, the main results of the first Miro board are presented below.

Table 15: SUPERSHINE Cities' Partners

CITIES	PARTNER	
	ATER	AZIENDA TERRITORIALE PER L'EDILIZIA RESIDENZIALE DI TRIESTE
	REA	RIGA MUNICIPAL AGENCY "RIGA ENERGY AGENCY"
	SP	SPACETIME LLC
	ZV	SOCIEDAD MUNICIPAL ZARAGOZA VIVIENDA SL
	DEMIR	DE SURDURULEBILIR ENERJI VE INSAAT SANAYI TICARET LIMITED SIRKETI
	KM	KADIKOY BELEDIYESI

Table 16: SUPERSHINE Municipality' Partners

MUNICIPALITY	PARTNER	
	FB	FAELLESBO
	ATER	AZIENDA TERRITORIALE PER L'EDILIZIA RESIDENZIALE DI TRIESTE
	REA	RIGA MUNICIPAL AGENCY "RIGA ENERGY AGENCY"
	ENA	AGENCIA DE ENERGIA E AMBIENTE DA ARRABIDA
	KM	KADIKOY BELEDIYESI

Table 17: SUPERSHINE Technical' Partners

TECHNICAL PARTNERS: TECHNICAL EXPERTISE	PARTNER	
	FB	FAELLESBO
	ATER	AZIENDA TERRITORIALE PER L'EDILIZIA RESIDENZIALE DI TRIESTE
	REA	RIGA MUNICIPAL AGENCY "RIGA ENERGY AGENCY"
	ENA	AGENCIA DE ENERGIA E AMBIENTE DA ARRABIDA
	KM	KADIKOY BELEDIYESI

Table 18: SUPERSHINE Social' Partners

TECHNICAL PARTNERS: SOCIAL EXPERTISE	PARTNER	
	DEMIR	DE SURDURULEBILIR ENERJI VE INSAAT SANAYI TICARET LIMITED SIRKETI
	ICONS	FONDAZIONE ICONS
	APRE	AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA
	ZV	SOCIEDAD MUNICIPAL ZARAGOZA VIVIENDA S.L.
	CIRCE	FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGETICOS
	INSME	RETE INTERNAZIONALE PER LE PICCOLEE MEDIE IMPRESE

Table 19: SUPERSHINE Environmental' Partners

TECHNICAL PARTNERS: ENVIRONMENTAL EXPERTISE	PARTNER	
	DEMIR	DE SURDURULEBILIR ENERJI VE INSAAT SANAYI TICARET LIMITED SIRKETI
	INSME	RETE INTERNAZIONALE PER LE PICCOLEE MEDIE IMPRESE
	CIRCE	FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGETICOS

Table 20: SUPERSHINE Finance' Partners

TECHNICAL PARTNERS: FINANCE EXPERTISE	PARTNER	
	UoY	UNIVERSITY OF YORK
	TENDER	TENDERCAPITAL ALTERNATIVE FUNDS PLCS
	AYMING	AYMING ITALIA S.R.L. SOCIETABENEFIT IN FORMA ABBREVIATA AYMING ITALIA SRL SB

2nd and 3rd MIRO BOARDS: Topic relevance and expertise partners

The second board shows a simplified knowledge pyramid. It lets each partner vote for the topics they think are most relevant. There is also a space where all partners can add new topics they find important.

In Figure 12, you can see the extra topics added by the SUPERSHINE partners under the different themes. These new topics are shown with post-its in a different colour.

Figure 22: Topics relevance board

The main objective of this board is to check that the information provided by the SUPERSHINE partners in the Excel file is correct. This Excel file was shared with the consortium and is described in Section 3.1 (“Web-based Excel File”) of this deliverable. In this sense, the board works as a verification document.

The results from both boards are not included in this section, as they will be presented later in a summarised and condensed format. This is done to keep the content concise and avoid duplicating information.

Figure 23: Expertise of Partners by Knowledge Topic

4th and 5th MIRO BOARD: Choosing your knowledge format

These steps used two boards. The first one (Board 4) showed a simple matrix linking different learning ways to different content formats. SUPERSHINE partners were asked to choose the best combinations for sharing knowledge in the project. For example, they could match experience exchange, thematic expertise, or lessons learned with formats such as webinars, workshops, factsheets, or reports.

Figure 24: Learning matrix way

In the following step (Board 5) and final part of this workshop template, were used to explore the best layout and format to present this knowledge. Partners could choose between different styles for factsheets, videos or PowerPoint presentations.

Figure 25: Learning format template

Annex III: Interactive Quiz: Genially

In the Capacity building SUPERSHINE workshop, it will be added that, as an evaluation method, short quizzes and interactive games have been planned using the Genially tool. This online format will help participants understand how the evaluation will work and will support them in reinforcing and internalising the key information from each topic.

Two types of Genially activities will be created as examples. In the first one, each participant will have to choose which image correctly answers the quiz question.

Figure 26: Example of a Genially quiz where participants answer a question by selecting the correct image from three options.

A second option will be included in the form of a game called “Pixel Roll”. Only by answering the questions correctly will participants be able to move forward and complete the game.

Figure 27: Example of the Genially “Pixel Roll” game

Annex IV: Factsheets

Factsheet 1.- Technical: Envelope insulation and enhancement (CAR)

ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS	ENVELOPE INSULATION AND ENHANCEMENT
DESCRIPTION	
Technical description	
<p>The construction sector is one of the main causes of pollution in cities. It produces around 36% of all greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (United Nations Environment Programme [UNEP], 2021). A big part of this pollution comes from old buildings that waste a lot of energy. Improving these buildings is one of the best ways to lower emissions and to create more comfortable spaces for people (European Commission, 2020).</p>	
<p>The part of a building that faces the outside, called the <i>façade</i>, is very important. It protects the inside from cold, heat, rain, and noise. A good <i>façade</i> saves a lot of energy (BPIE, 2011). There are several ways to make <i>façades</i> better: changing windows and doors, adding glass enclosures, installing shading devices, growing green walls, or using smart systems like automatic blinds or special glass that changes with the sunlight (IEA, 2021).</p>	
<p>In old buildings, many problems come from heat escaping through doors, windows, and small gaps in the walls and thermal bridges. These problems cause higher energy bills and make indoor spaces less comfortable. To solve these problems, it is important to replace old windows and doors and to add insulation to the outside walls using systems like ETICS (European Commission, 2020).</p>	
Main Actions:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Change windows and doors: Many buildings, especially those built before 1980, have very old windows and doors that do not close properly. These gaps let cold air in during winter and let cool air out during summer. Replacing them with modern, efficient ones can reduce heating and cooling needs by more than 20% (BPIE, 2011). ● Apply ETICS (external insulation): Covering the exterior walls with a thick layer of insulation keeps the indoor temperature stable. It helps to avoid cold spots and moisture problems inside the building. A well-insulated <i>façade</i> can cut energy losses by up to 30% (IEA, 2021). ● Install glass enclosures and shading devices: Enclosing balconies with glass can create a "buffer zone" that helps to trap heat in winter. In summer, installing shading devices, like canopies or blinds, protects indoor spaces from overheating. These measures reduce the need for heating and air conditioning (UNEP, 2021). ● Add green <i>façades</i> and smart control systems: Growing plants on the building walls not only cools the building naturally but also improves air quality and makes the city more beautiful. Smart systems, like automatic blinds or special reactive glass, adjust the amount of light and 	

heat that enters the building without needing human action. This increases comfort and saves even more energy (European Commission, 2020).

Extra Benefits:

- People feel more comfortable inside renovated buildings.
- Energy bills are lower.
- Buildings look newer and more attractive.
- Cities become greener and healthier places to live.

Renovating façades is not only good for saving energy. It also helps to fight climate change, improves the quality of life for citizens, and creates new jobs in construction and renovation sectors. It is a smart investment for the future of cities.

ScienceDirect. (n.d.). Energy-efficient building envelope [Diagram]. ScienceDirect Topics. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/earth-and-planetary-sciences/energy-efficient-building-envelope>

SCORING

Technical Scoring

The technical complexity of envelope insulation and enhancement measures can vary, but overall they are considered medium in difficulty.

ETICS: Replacing windows and doors and installing ETICS (external thermal insulation systems) require skilled labour but use well-established technologies. Integration with existing buildings, especially older ones, can pose **moderate challenges, such as handling irregular structures, managing thermal bridges, and avoiding moisture problems during insulation installation.**

GLASS AND SHADING ELEMENTS: Glass enclosures and shading devices are relatively easy to implement, while green façades and smart systems demand higher expertise (particularly in system design and plant maintenance, or smart automation programming).

In general, the required level of expertise is accessible for trained construction professionals, but attention to detail and good project planning are critical to ensure proper integration and avoid issues like condensation or thermal discontinuities.

Thus, technical complexity is moderate to moderately high, depending on the combination of interventions. In conclusion, technical complexity ranges from moderate to high depending on building conditions and the integration of advanced systems.

Finance Scoring

The **financial cost of envelope insulation and enhancement is typically medium to high**. Initial investment costs can be significant, **especially for external insulation systems and window replacement**.

Typical ranges are:

- **Window and door replacement:** €300–€800 per window, depending on materials and performance levels.
- **External insulation (ETICS systems):** €50–€100/m².
- **Glass enclosures and shading systems:** €300–€600/m², depending on design complexity.
- **Green façades and smart control systems:** higher upfront costs, especially for intelligent adaptive systems.

Intervention	Spain	Italy	Denmark	Riga	France
Window and door replacement	300–700 / unit	350–800 / unit	400–900 / unit	300–600 / unit	350–850 / unit
External insulation (ETICS systems)	45–90 / m ²				
Shading and glass enclosure systems	280–500 / m ²				
Green façades / intelligent systems	400–800 / m ²				

Operational and maintenance costs are generally low for insulation and traditional shading devices but moderate for green façades (due to irrigation, pruning, plant replacement) and smart systems (possible need for software maintenance). There are **substantial potential savings on energy bills** (typically 20–30%) and access to subsidies or funding programmes (especially under climate and energy transition initiatives at the EU and national levels) can reduce the financial burden. Overall, **the payback period can vary from 5 to 15 years** depending on the depth of the retrofit.

Environment Scoring

Envelope insulation and enhancement measures have a highly positive environmental impact. By reducing energy consumption for heating and cooling—often the largest share of energy use in buildings—

they lead to a substantial decrease in GHG emissions. According to the IEA (2021), insulation can cut building-related CO₂ emissions by up to 30%.

Materials such as mineral wool, EPS, or natural insulators (wood fibre, cork) vary in terms of embodied carbon, but **the lifecycle environmental benefit from reduced operational energy use generally outweighs the initial impact within a few years. Some interventions, like green façades, actively improve urban microclimates, absorb pollutants, and reduce the urban heat island effect.**

Waste generation during retrofits is moderate but manageable through recycling protocols (e.g. recovery of window frames or mineral-based renderings). Water consumption is negligible except for irrigated façades, which require efficient drip systems and drought-resistant plants.

Social Scoring

Envelope retrofit actions are generally well accepted by the public, especially when they result in visible improvements (modernised façades, better comfort, lower bills). **There is a strong alignment with societal values like energy efficiency, affordability, and quality of life.** Interventions are especially **appreciated in vulnerable neighbourhoods** where poor envelope quality often correlates with energy poverty.

The ease of adoption is medium: while users don't need to interact directly with insulation or façade systems, temporary disruption during works (noise, dust, scaffolding) can affect perception. For green façades and smart systems, awareness-raising and user training help ensure lasting social integration and proper use.

Additionally, these measures support employment generation in the construction sector and **promote inclusive renovation strategies under the EU's "Leave No One Behind" principle. As such, social scoring is medium-high to high, depending on community engagement and communication during deployment.**

CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

Recurrent risks

Technical Difficulties

- **Irregular or deteriorated building stock**, especially in buildings over 50 years old, may present unpredictable challenges such as hidden moisture damage, asbestos, or structural weaknesses that complicate insulation installation.
- **Thermal bridge correction** and airtightness continuity are often overlooked or poorly executed, reducing the effectiveness of the intervention.
- In green façades or smart systems, **specialised knowledge** is needed to integrate technologies without compromising structural integrity or indoor air quality.
- Climate-related risks such as **heatwaves or increased humidity require careful selection of materials** (vapour-open vs. airtight systems) to avoid moisture-related pathologies.

Financial Constraints

- Retrofitting requires **significant upfront investment**, particularly for large-scale external insulation or intelligent envelope systems. In socially vulnerable or energy-poor areas, these costs can be a major barrier without targeted public funding or incentives.

- **Unforeseen additional costs** (e.g. scaffold modifications, repairs) often appear mid-project, straining limited budgets.

Social and Legal aspects

- **Opposition from residents or owners**, especially in multi-family buildings, can delay or block interventions due to disruption, cost-sharing issues, or aesthetic preferences.

● **TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE**

Phases of implementation	
P1	Preliminary Analysis of the envelope
<i>Technical diagnosis and custom design of envelope enhancement solutions based on building conditions and urban context</i>	
P1.1	Building envelope audit <i>Thermal assessment through visual inspection, thermography, blower door tests, and plan review. Identification of energy losses, thermal bridges, and envelope pathologies (e.g. moisture, mould).</i>
P1.2	Material and system selection <i>Selection of insulation materials, window/door types, shading systems or green façade technologies based on orientation, local climate, relative humidity, and applicable regulations (e.g. CTE DB-HE, EN 13165).</i>
P1.3	Legal and administrative compliance <i>Acquisition of building permits, municipal authorisations, subsidy applications (e.g. NextGenEU, national funds), and compliance with aesthetic or heritage requirements in protected zones.</i>
P2	Construction and Installation Phases
<i>Execution of the physical interventions on the building envelope.</i>	
P2.1	Façade preparation <i>Cleaning of surfaces, removal of obsolete elements (old coatings, gutters), structural repair, and crack sealing. Verification of surface mechanical resistance for insulation anchoring.</i>
P2.2	Insulation system installation (ETICS / ventilated façade) <i>Fixing of insulation panels (EPS, mineral wool, cork, etc.) with adhesive and mechanical anchors. Application of base coat, mesh reinforcement, and final protective finishes. Typical thickness: 6–14 cm; thermal conductivity ≤ 0.040 W/m·K.</i>
P2.3	Window and door replacement <i>Installation of high-performance units ($U_w \leq 1.3$ W/m²·K), with double or triple low-emissivity glazing and thermally broken frames. Perimeter air-tight sealing is essential.</i>
P2.4	Shading and solar control systems <i>Installation of solar control devices: fixed or mobile slats, awnings, automated shutters. In smart systems, link to light or thermal sensors for adaptive control.</i>
P2.5	Building envelope final technical audits <i>Thermal assessment through visual inspection, thermography, blower door tests, and plan review. Identification of energy losses, thermal bridges, and envelope pathologies (e.g. moisture, mould).</i>

P3	Monitoring and Maintenance
<i>Final quality check, user guidance, and maintenance planning to ensure long-term performance.</i>	
P3.1	System inspection and performance testing <i>On-site quality control: insulation thickness check, sealing continuity, airtightness test, and thermal imaging. In automated systems: sensor responsiveness and control logic testing.</i>
P3.2	User training and documentation <i>Provision of manuals and user guides (for automated shading, plant maintenance), and basic training for occupants or facility managers.</i>
P3.3	Maintenance plan setup (and further periodic revisions) <i>Establishment of routine inspection schedules (annually for windows and solar controls; every 6 months for greenery). Definition of replacement frequency for components such as seals, plants, or smart sensors.</i>

● **GANTT**

**These values and task durations represent average estimates. Timelines may be adjusted to account for differences across countries and cities.*

		M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	
P1	Preliminary analysis and planning	█											
P.1.1	Building envelope audit	█											
P.1.2	Material & system selection and works planning		█	█	█	█	█						
P.1.3	Legal and administrative compliance	█	█	█	█								
P2	Construction and Installation Phase					█	█	█	█	█			
P.2.1	Façade preparation					█	█	█					
P.2.2	Insulation system						█	█					
P.2.3	Window and door replacement							█	█				
P.2.4	Shading & solar control system					█	█		█	█			
P3	Monitoring and Maintenance								█	█	█	█	
P.3.1	System inspection								█	█	█		
P.3.2	User Training										█	█	
P.3.3	Maintenance plan setup										█	█	

● **STRATEGIC**

RECOMMENDATIONS	
DOES	<p><i>Prioritise inefficient pre-1980 buildings using thermal diagnostics (e.g. blower door tests, thermography).</i></p> <p><i>Integrate projects into climate strategies (SECAP, CCC), using data to target high-vulnerability zones.</i></p>
DON'TS	<p><i>Do not intervene in heritage buildings without adapted design.</i></p> <p><i>Avoid applying insulation without solving thermal bridges or moisture risks.</i></p> <p><i>Avoid using materials unsuited to local climate conditions</i></p>

<p><i>Design climate-adapted solutions with U-values $\leq 0.30 \text{ W/m}^2\text{-K}$ and dynamic solar control.</i></p> <p><i>Ensure social equity with passive, low-maintenance systems suited for low-income areas.</i></p> <p><i>Link funding to performance: Require $\geq 25\%$ energy savings, no condensation risk, and validated simulation tools.</i></p> <p><i>Respect heritage constraints with reversible, indoor or visually neutral interventions.</i></p> <p><i>Include maintenance obligations: Biannual checks for green/smart systems, with digital monitoring.</i></p>	<p><i>Select insulation based on thermal conductivity, vapour resistance, and weather durability.</i></p> <p><i>Do not install smart façade systems without safeguards</i> <i>Include user training, manual override, system commissioning, and maintenance protocols.</i></p> <p><i>Do not prioritise energy savings over overall performance</i> <i>Ensure the design also addresses comfort, acoustics, aesthetics, and indoor environmental quality (IEQ).</i></p>
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● **CROSS-LINK MATRIX BETWEEN TECHNICAL ACTIONS**

Main Topic ↓ Related →	Preliminary Analysis and Planning	Construction and Installation Phase	Commissioning, Monitoring and Maintenance
Preliminary Analysis and Planning		S Synergy <i>A robust planning phase, including envelope audits and material selection, ensures optimal construction performance, reduced error rates, and fewer corrections.</i>	C Complementary <i>Maintenance and monitoring strategies must be anticipated during design and specification.</i>
Construction and Installation Phase	S Synergy <i>Continuous feedback between site execution and design documents allows real-time adjustment of systems, especially in irregular structures or legacy buildings.</i>		S Synergy <i>Correct execution of details such as thermal bridges, vapour barriers, or smart device installation ensures monitoring accuracy and long-term durability.</i>
Commissioning, Monitoring and Maintenance	C Complementary <i>Complementary: Post-intervention data (thermal imaging, user feedback, sensor logs) can refine future planning methods and system choices.</i>	S Synergy <i>Performance testing, calibration of automated systems, and user training rely on accurate and compliant construction work.</i>	

- **POLICY FRAMEWORK**

Relevant Policies
<p>International level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (SDGs) – Especially SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), and SDG 13 (Climate Action). ● Paris Agreement & COP Targets – Supports reduction of GHG emissions through energy efficiency. ● UN-Habitat New Urban Agenda – Encourages inclusive and energy-efficient urban retrofitting.
<p>European level</p> <p>DIRECTLY APPLICABLE REGULATIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● New European Bauhaus – Promotes interventions that combine sustainability, aesthetics and inclusion. ● Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EU/2024/1275) ● EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities – Includes building renovation as a key investment priority. <p>OTHERS INTERESTING POLICIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy – Supports local action on building performance. ● European Green Deal – Promotes decarbonisation of the building stock as a key climate strategy. ● Renovation Wave (2020) – Core initiative targeting energy-efficient renovation of buildings across Europe. ● Fit for 55 Package – Sets binding targets for emissions reduction and energy efficiency improvements in the built environment.
<p>National level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National Building Codes (e.g., Spain: CTE DB-HE / DB-HS; France: RT2020; Italy: CAM Edilizia) ● National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) 2021–2030 ● Long-Term Renovation Strategies (LTRS) <p>OTHERS INTERESTING POLICIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NextGenerationEU – Recovery and Resilience Plans (RRPs) ● National Strategies for Climate Resilience
<p>Local level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SECAP – Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans ● Local Housing and Renovation Strategies ● Integrated Urban Strategies & Local Agenda 21 ● Smart City Action Plans ● Urban Regeneration Programs ● Green Infrastructure & Climate Resilience Plans ● Climate City Contracts (CCC)

● **STAKEHOLDER ROLES AND ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK**

Stakeholder	Role	
MUNICIPALITY	Regulatory Financial	Define policy frameworks, issue permits, promote actions in vulnerable areas, and co-finance through subsidies or EU/local funds.
BUILDING OWNERS	Operational Financial	Approve and co-finance interventions, provide building access, coordinate consensus (in multi-family blocks), and oversee execution decisions.
TECHNICAL ADVISORS	Technical Advisory	Perform audits, identify pathologies, design envelope solutions, simulate performance (e.g., PHPP, CE3X), and manage funding applications.
CONSTRUCTION COMPANIES	Operational Contractual	Execute physical interventions (ETICS, windows, shading), ensure quality control, manage logistics and site safety.
ARCHITECTS AND ENGINEERS	Technical Design	Develop detailed design (U-values, thermal bridges, vapour control), supervise works, ensure integration with structure and urban context.
TECHNOLOGY PROVIDERS	Technical Commercial	Develop, supply, and maintain smart envelope systems (e.g., sensors, blinds, adaptive glazing); provide integration support and technical documentation.
LANDSCAPE DESIGNERS	Technical Environmental	Plan and integrate green façades and vegetated systems, select appropriate species, define irrigation and pruning needs.
FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS	Financial	Provide complementary instruments such as green mortgages, renovation loans, or ESCO-based models for deep retrofit financing.
TRAINING CENTRES	Capacity Building Educational	Certify and train professionals in ETICS installation, façade sealing, sensor integration, or bio-based insulation.
COMMUNITY GROUPS	Social Advocacy	Raise awareness, support inclusive renovation campaigns, and mediate between technical teams and residents in vulnerable contexts.
HOUSING ASSOCIATIONS	Operational Financial	Facilitate planning and financial aggregation for collective interventions, manage administrative tasks, and liaise with installers

● **MAIN REFERENCES**

GOOD PRACTICES / SOME EXAMPLES	
Project	
<p>R2CITIES</p> <p>Demonstration of energy-efficient retrofitting strategies in residential districts, including envelope insulation and monitoring systems.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/314473</p>	
<p>REMOURBAN</p> <p>Smart city project focused on deep energy retrofitting, including high-performance envelope solutions in Valladolid.</p> <p>https://www.remourban.eu/</p>	

CITYFIED (Torre Lago)

Large-scale retrofitting of residential buildings, applying ETICS and smart façade components.

<https://www.cityfied.eu/>

MAKING-CITY

Focused on Positive Energy Districts (PEDs), incorporating envelope renovation measures in building retrofits across European cities.

<https://makingcity.eu/>

SMARTENCITY (Vitoria-Gasteiz, Sønderborg, Tartu)

Demonstration of deep renovation of urban districts including high-efficiency envelope upgrades.

<https://smartencity.eu/>

REZBUILD

Integrated renovation strategies for residential buildings, including prefabricated façade solutions and circular economy approaches.

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/768623>

BRESAER

Development and demonstration of a breakthrough energy envelope system with dynamic elements for building retrofitting.

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/637186>

EFFESUS

Focused on energy efficiency in historic districts, including compatible façade solutions for heritage buildings.

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/314678>

INFINITE

Industrialized envelope retrofitting using modular systems for faster on-site integration. Cartif participated in technology development and demonstration.

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/958397>

P2ENDURE

Demonstration of plug-and-play prefab envelope renovation kits in deep retrofit projects across Europe.

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/723391>

NEW PROJECT

• **ZEB Pilot House (Larvik, Noruega)**

Pilot house that demonstrates high-performance envelope solutions, including advanced insulation and passive design, developed by Snøhetta and the Zero Emission Building Centre (ZEB).

<https://www.architecturelab.net/zeb-pilot-house-snohetta/>

Web-site

- **BUILD UP – The European Portal for Energy Efficiency in Buildings**

Official platform of the European Commission providing up-to-date information on energy efficiency in buildings. It includes case studies, technical guidelines, policy updates, and training resources focused on envelope renovation, insulation, efficient windows and passive strategies.

<https://build-up.ec.europa.eu/en/home>

- **IEA – Buildings Sector (International Energy Agency)**

Provides technical and strategic insights into improving building energy efficiency, including the role of envelope performance, insulation solutions and deep renovation in the energy transition.

<https://www.iea.org/energy-system/buildings>

- **Renovation Hub – RenoWiki (BPIE)**

Collaborative EU-wide platform mapping renovation policies, financing tools and successful projects. Includes specific solutions related to envelope insulation, façade upgrades and regulatory frameworks.

<https://renovation-hub.eu>

- **Eurima – European Insulation Manufacturers Association**

Technical site providing publications, data sheets, and guidance documents on insulation materials, their thermal performance, and role in building envelope retrofitting.

<https://www.eurima.org>

- **EPBD – Energy Performance of Buildings Directive**

Official portal of the European Commission providing access to the legislative framework, updates, implementation guidance, and national long-term renovation strategies under the EPBD.

<https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings>

Paper

☐ Hailu, G. (2021). *Energy systems in buildings*. In *Energy services fundamentals and financing* (pp. 181–209). Academic Press.

☐ Amani, N. (2025). Energy efficiency of residential buildings using thermal insulation of external walls and roof based on simulation analysis. *Energy Storage and Saving*, 4(1), 48-55.

☐ Pagoni, P., Møller, E. B., Peuhkuri, R. H., & Jensen, N. F. (2025). Evaluation of the performance of different internal insulation systems in real-life conditions-A case study. *Building and Environment*, 267, 112319.

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- **KEY CONSIDERATIONS**

Additional Notes

7. Design context: Use ≥ 10 cm of insulation (e.g. EPS, $\lambda \leq 0.038$ W/m·K) in temperate climates; up to 14 cm in cold zones. South façades benefit from solar control over extra insulation.
3. Moisture control is essential: Up to 30% of ETICS pathologies are due to poor vapour management. Use breathable renders and apply continuous sealing around windows.
9. Ventilation must be integrated: Airtight façades without mechanical ventilation (e.g. with heat recovery) can increase CO₂ and humidity. EN 16798 recommends 30 m³/h per person of fresh air.
0. Added benefits: Acoustic insulation improves by 8–12 dB with full envelope upgrades. Surface temperatures rise >3 °C in winter, enhancing comfort and reducing mould risk.

Factsheet 2.- Technical: Integration of renewable (CAR)

ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS	INTEGRATION OF RENEWABLES
DESCRIPTION	
Technical description	
<p>Buildings consume a large share of energy; around 38% globally; and contribute to more than one-third of greenhouse gas emissions. Reducing this impact is possible by constructing or renovating buildings to use less energy and by supplying that energy from renewable sources such as sunlight, wind, and geothermal heat. A building that produces as much energy as it consumes is known as a Zero-Energy Building (ZEB).</p>	
<p>ZERO-ENERGY BUILDING: The core idea behind Zero Energy Buildings is to meet energy needs using renewable sources. These include solar, wind, geothermal, hydropower, hydrogen, and biomass. These systems reduce pollution and lower dependence on fossil fuels like oil, gas, and coal. The clean energy produced can be used for electricity, heating and cooling, hot water, and even transport.</p>	
<p><i>Ilustración 1: illustrates a two-way grid, capable of delivering energy to a building and receiving energy back from it. The red arrow in the diagram indicates exported energy, whether from on-site or off-site generation.</i></p>	
<p>HEATING, COOLING AND HOT WATER:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Solar thermal panels use solar radiation to heat water. Production varies by region. These systems are typically installed on rooftops or building façades. Simulations have shown solar coverage of up to 97% in summer and 62% in winter for domestic hot water (DHW). DHW systems can save up to 1459 kWh per year with payback periods between 6 and 10 years. They are often more efficient than PV systems (up to 70%) and work well when combined with thermal storage. 	

● **Heat pumps transfer heat from air, ground, or water to buildings. They operate with low electricity use, delivering 3 to 5 times more heat than the electricity they consume (COP = 3–5).** Types include air-source, ground-source, and water-source heat pumps. **These systems also provide cooling.** They integrate well with thermal or electrical storage, and they are suitable for ZEBs, district energy systems, Positive Energy Districts (PEDs), and energy communities.

- **Geothermal systems harness stable underground temperatures. It is the most efficient solutions when paired with heat pumps. Two main installation methods:**

Closed loop: vertical (better for space-saving and hot water) or horizontal

Open loop: uses naturally stored water

These systems **deliver 3–4 times more heat than the electricity consumed and are more sustainable** when powered by renewable electricity.

Ilustración 2: Schematic of a ground-source heat pump system with vertical boreholes (BH1-BH3), underground thermal storage, heat pump, buffer tank, and air-conditioning system.

- **Air-source heat pumps (ASHPs) can be air-to-water (for central heating) or air-to-air (for space heating).** Their efficiency depends on outdoor temperature and compatibility with low-temperature emitters; otherwise, electricity consumption rises sharply.

ELECTRICITY PRODUCTION:

- **Photovoltaic (PV) panels convert sunlight into electricity.** Their output depends on solar radiation levels. **PV systems have reached efficiencies of up to 23%, up from just 1% in earlier versions.** In places like Hong Kong, rooftop PV systems have Energy Yield Ratios (EYR) of 10 to 15.8, meaning they produce 10–15 times the energy invested in their lifecycle.
- **BIPV (Building-Integrated PV) systems are embedded into the building envelope;** windows, façades, or balconies; **generating electricity without requiring extra space.** Although façades

receive less sunlight, integration with passive or active cooling techniques (e.g., phase change materials) can double the annual solar potential.

- **PVT (Photovoltaic-Thermal) systems produce electricity and heat simultaneously. These systems are more efficient than regular PV, achieving up to 43% higher electrical efficiency. Optimised systems can cover up to 51% of annual energy demand and 36% of DHW needs.**

HYBRID SYSTEMS:

Hybrid renewable energy systems combine at least two sources of renewable energy. They also integrate generation and storage. Some examples:

- **PVT systems: Cover up to 71% of DHW needs and 78% of electricity demand for appliances.**
- **BIPV systems: Double the surface area available for solar capture and enhance building performance**

OTHER RENEWABLE OPTIONS

- **Wind Power:** Wind, caused by atmospheric pressure differences, can generate electricity using wind turbines.

- **Small wind turbines** (e.g., 1.5 kW) installed on rooftops can supply over half a home's electricity annually. Vertical-axis turbines are quieter, work at lower wind speeds, and need less maintenance. They are ideal for urban environments.

Ilustración 3: Urban wind energy integration options: schematic overview of possible placements of vertical and horizontal axis wind turbines on rooftops and façades, with real-life examples. Applications include residential buildings, public infrastructure, and land

Studies show that **small wind turbines (1.5 kW) can produce 2541 kWh/year**, covering 55% of annual electricity use, with a **26.8-year payback and CO₂ savings of 1093 kg/year**. Vertical turbines are more efficient (>70%) than horizontal ones (50–60%). **Urban wind solutions** should therefore be evaluated individually, as they usually serve as complementary measures rather than core technologies within building decarbonisation strategies.

Good practice: Bahrain World Trade Centre uses horizontal turbines to cover 11–15% of energy demand

• **Energy from solid waste:** Provides both waste management and renewable energy. It can supply **20–23% of electricity** and **4–5% of heating demand**.

- **Biomass Uses organic material** (wood, agricultural waste) for heat and power. Biomass accounts for **around 9% of global primary energy**. It emits up to **10 times less CO₂/MWh than fossil fuels**, although it can increase fine particles in urban areas. **Biomass-based systems** can achieve lower net CO₂ emissions than fossil fuels when sustainably sourced and efficiently operated. However, their environmental performance strongly depends on fuel origin, transport distances, combustion technology, and local air quality impacts, particularly regarding particulate matter.

Illustration 4: Biomass conversion routes into various biofuels through fermentation, oil extraction, and pyrolysis.

- **Biogas** Produced from food or animal waste. A **9.5 m³ household system can deliver 5 hours of daily cooking**. Combined systems for heating, cooling, and **electricity can reduce CO₂ emissions by 94% and primary energy use by 32%**, with average efficiency reaching 151%.

Challenges:

- Reduced efficiency in high ambient temperatures
- Limited technical knowledge and risk of system overload
- Requires good design, robust materials, and regular maintenance

Ilustración 5: Cross-section of a biogas plant showing waste input, anaerobic digestion, gas storage, and slurry output.

• **Hydropower** Hydropower from small rivers can also be used in buildings, especially in places where water flows naturally. In 2021, 4400 TWh were generated from hydropower in large dams, 1.6 times more than nuclear power.

Ilustración 6: Small-scale hydro installation with submerged turbines in a canal flow system.

Building scale: Pumped hydro storage (PHS) elevates water to rooftops during low demand, then releases it to generate electricity. Requires structures to support 2 kN/m² and uses rainwater or mains supply. Simulations across 15 buildings show an average of 6 kWh/day generation, covering 70–80% of daily needs. Small-scale pumped hydro storage at building level remains largely experimental and is currently limited to pilot or research applications. Structural requirements, safety considerations, and space constraints significantly restrict its applicability in conventional urban buildings.

ENERGY STORAGE:

Energy storage systems help manage surplus renewable production, improve self-consumption, and balance supply. Types:

- Thermal storage conserves heat or cold for later use. This type of storage can store heat or cold for later use under varying conditions such as temperature, location, time or power.
- Batteries store electricity for use when the sun or wind are not available and allow stabilisation of the intermittency of renewable sources.

- *Chemical storage, Hydrogen is also used in some places as a stationary storage method for both buildings and vehicles.*

ENERGY COMMUNITIES:

Energy communities are legal entities where citizens, local authorities, or organisations collaborate to generate, manage, store, and share energy. Their goal is to create social, environmental, and economic benefits beyond profit.

These communities often use smart systems to track and optimise energy use. Storage (batteries, thermal systems, electric vehicles) helps deal with intermittency and guarantee supply.

Common activities:

- *Generate renewable energy*
- *Provide energy efficiency services*
- *Share surplus energy*
- *Reduce energy bills*

NEW IDEAS: DATA CENTRE HEAT: *Some new systems take the heat from data centres (places where computers are working all day) and use it to warm homes or buildings nearby. This is a smart way to use energy that would normally be wasted, Producing, supplying, consuming, storing, and distributing potentially clean energy and Providing electric mobility or other energy services.*

Ilustración 7: Waste heat from a data centre is recovered and upgraded to supply district heating networks.

SCORING

Technical Scoring

*The technical complexity of **integrating renewable energy** technologies into buildings is medium to high, depending on the type and combination of systems selected.*

- **Low to moderate** complexity systems include **solar photovoltaic (PV) panels, solar thermal collectors, and air-to-water heat pumps**. These are well-standardised in the market, with mature technologies, extensive installer networks, and proven performance in urban contexts. Their implementation typically involves limited structural modifications and can be executed under standard building permits.
- **High-complexity** systems such as **photovoltaic-thermal (PVT) panels, building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPV), vertical geothermal loops, micro wind turbines, and hydrogen-based**

chemical **storage** demand advanced engineering design, structural assessment, custom integration, and interaction with digital control platforms like Energy Management Systems (EMS).

- **Hybrid systems and energy communities** introduce additional layers of technical sophistication. These **include the need for interoperable components**, demand-side flexibility strategies, Internet of Things (IoT) connectivity, and real-time energy monitoring and balancing.

Finance Scoring

11. **High initial capital expenditure**, particularly for comprehensive retrofits, hybrid systems, or deep renovations involving multiple renewable technologies.
12. **Low operational and maintenance costs**, once systems are in place. Solar thermal, heat pumps, and PV have minimal running expenses, especially when maintenance contracts and warranties are established upfront.
13. **Payback periods vary widely**: solar thermal can achieve returns in 6–10 years, while small wind turbines and hydrogen systems may exceed 20–25 years, depending on local conditions and energy prices.
14. Public and private funding mechanisms, can significantly improve financial viability, especially for public buildings and social housing. Co-benefits include:
 - 14.1. **Local economic stimulation** through green jobs in construction, installation, and maintenance.
 - 14.2. **Energy security** via increased self-generation, peak demand reduction, and enhanced resilience of buildings and districts.

Environment Scoring

- **Net-zero energy buildings (NZEBS)** cut CO₂ emissions, reduce primary energy demand, and favour the production of clean, decentralised energy. EU targets EPBD and Fit for 55 package.
- **Improved air quality**, particularly in urban areas, results from reduced use of fossil fuels and, cutting CO₂ and local pollutants (NO_x, PM_{2.5}).
- **Bioenergy and waste-to-energy systems** enhance resource efficiency and circularity by converting organic or municipal waste into useful energy forms (reducing landfill use and methane emissions).
- **Efficient energy storage and smart management** also limit of renewable electricity, ensuring optimal use of clean energy.

Social Scoring

- **High acceptance is driven by visible and tangible benefits**: improved indoor comfort, reduced energy bills and healthier environments.
- **NZEBS and renewable buildings** can significantly reduce energy poverty, particularly when applied in social housing or vulnerable neighbourhoods.
- **Job creation and upskilling** in the local economy enhance social value.

- *Energy communities and participatory retrofits strengthen social cohesion, empower citizens, and increase collective climate action awareness. However, success depends on transparent communication, inclusive governance, and co-design with residents.*

CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

Recurrent risks

- *Poor building insulation or outdated energy systems*
- *Limited rooftop space or low solar/wind potential*
- *High initial investment costs or limited access to financing system*
- *Low user awareness and poor maintenance*
- *Structural constraints for installing renewable systems*
- *Complex or unclear permitting processes*
- *Obsolete technologies with high energy consumption*
- *Low citizen participation in planning or implementation*
- *Weak coordination across municipal departments or Misalignment between national and local regulations*

● **TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE**

Phases of implementation	
P1	Assessment and Planning
Preliminary phase to evaluate the site, contextual conditions, and technical feasibility of integrating renewables and efficiency measures	
P1.1	Site Assessment <i>Evaluate local renewable energy potential, such as solar irradiance, wind speeds...</i>
P1.2	Needs Identification <i>Quantify energy consumption by end use. Identify loads and peak demand profiles. Align demand with the most suitable renewable technologies.</i>
P1.3	Feasibility Analysis <i>Assess technical and economic viability (Include preliminary system, envelope performance, and regulatory compliance.</i>
P2	System Design and Selection
Translate assessment into system specifications. Implementation time depending on building complexity and technologies involved	
P2.1	Technology Selection and Sizing <i>Choose technologies based on site conditions and demand. Dimension systems and ensure compatibility with HVAC and envelope interventions.</i>
P2.2	Integration and Layout Design

	<i>Design system layout, such as panel orientation, wind turbine mounting, heat pump loop depth among others.</i>
P2.3	Grid and Control Strategy <i>Define grid connection, battery backup, and smart controls.</i>
P3	Implementation
Procurement, installation, and commissioning	
P3.1	Energy efficiency works <i>Upgrade envelope, HVAC, lighting (LED), and airtightness</i>
P3.2	Renewable systems installation <i>Install selected RES</i>
P3.3	Storage and smart systems <i>Add storage, electrical batteries, and EMS. Integrate with smart meters and occupant interfaces.</i>
P4	Monitoring and Maintenance
Long-term phase for optimisation and reliability. Continuous process starting at commissioning.	
P4.1	System testing and commissioning Check that all systems are installed correctly and working safely (inverters, batteries, heat pumps). Ensure connection with energy management systems (EMS) and provide user manuals and basic training.
P4.2	Ongoing monitoring and servicing: Monitor system performance using digital tools. Schedule regular maintenance and adjust settings to improve efficiency.

● GANTT

	M 1	M 2	M 3	M 4	M 5	M 6	M 7	M 8	M 9	M 10	M 11	M 12	M 13	M 14	M 15	M 16	M 17	M 18
P1	Assessment and Planning																	
P.1.1	█																	
P.1.2		█	█	█														
P.1.3			█	█	█													
P2	System Design and Selection																	
P.2.1			█	█	█													
P.2.2			█	█	█	█												
P.2.3				█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
P3	Implementation																	
P.3.1				█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
P.3.2				█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
P.3.3														█	█	█	█	█
P4	Monitoring																	
P.4.1																	█	█
P.4.2																	█	█

● STRATEGIC

RECOMMENDATIONS	
DOs	▶ Start with a detailed energy audit
DON'Ts	▶ Don't skip the design phase

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply for EU or national grants Combine renewables with insulation and storage Use smart systems to improve performance Involve users early and offer training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Avoid overcomplicated systems with high maintenance Don't ignore visual impact in sensitive areas Don't forget to plan for regular maintenance for users Don't think it's just about the technology; people need to understand and accept the changes
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● CROSS-LINK MATRIX BETWEEN TECHNICAL ACTIONS

Main Topic ↓ Related →	PV PANELS	THERMAL PANELS	GEOTHERMAL	BIOMASS	ENERGY COMMUNITIES
PV PANELS		C Complementary <i>Can support domestic hot water needs when solar thermal is insufficient.</i>	S Synergy <i>PV supplies electricity for heat pump operation in geothermal systems.</i>	S Synergy <i>PV provides electricity while biomass covers thermal loads, balancing energy profiles.</i>	S Synergy <i>PV enables self-consumption schemes in energy communities.</i>
THERMAL PANELS	C Complementary <i>Can complement PV for full building energy coverage (electric + thermal).</i>		S Synergy <i>Efficient when used for DHW in summer, while geothermal covers winter demand.</i>	S Synergy <i>Thermal panels can operate in summer, biomass in winter for balanced DHW and heating.</i>	R Related <i>Can be integrated in energy communities to supply hot water via shared networks.</i>
GEOTHERMAL	S Synergy <i>PV powers heat pumps used in geothermal systems.</i>	S Synergy <i>Thermal panels cover part of DHW demand, geothermal supplies heating/cooling.</i>		C Complementary <i>Can coexist by covering different demand profiles (e.g. peak vs base load).</i>	R Related <i>Useful in collective heating/cooling systems within energy communities.</i>
BIOMASS	C Complementary <i>Complements PV by supplying thermal energy in low-sunlight periods.</i>	S Synergy <i>Combines well with thermal panels seasonally (biomass in winter, thermal in summer).</i>	C Complementary <i>May be used in parallel where heating demand is high.</i>		R Related <i>Applicable in rural or forested communities for local heat generation.</i>
ENERGY COMMUNITIES	S Synergy <i>PV is often the core of self-consumption and shared electricity models.</i>	C Complementary <i>Thermal panels can feed shared DHW systems in multi-building networks.</i>	R Related <i>Geothermal can power district-level heating and cooling in energy communities.</i>	R Related <i>Biomass provides renewable heat within energy communities, especially in rural areas.</i>	

- **POLICY FRAMEWORK**

Relevant Policies
International level
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Goal 7: Affordable and Clean Energy ○ Goal 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities ○ Goal 13: Climate Action <p><i>*NZEBS contribute to these goals by improving energy efficiency, reducing emissions, and enhancing building resilience.</i></p> ● Paris Agreement and COP Climate Targets: NZEBs support countries' Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) by cutting emissions from the building sector. ● UN-Habitat's New Urban Agenda: This agenda encourages sustainable, inclusive, and energy-efficient urban development. ● Resilient Cities Network: It promotes urban strategies that include energy resilience, with NZEBs as a key component of climate adaptation.
European level
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● European Green Deal: This deal sets the EU's roadmap for climate neutrality by 2050. NZEBs are central to reducing building-sector emissions and boosting sustainable renovation ● New European Bauhaus: It promotes sustainable, inclusive, and aesthetically high-quality built environments ● Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD): This directive requires all new buildings to be NZEBs and promotes deep renovation of existing stock. ● Renovation Wave: This initiative aims to double renovation rates and reduce energy poverty by upgrading the building stock across Europe. ● Fit for 55 Package: It establishes targets for at least 55% GHG reduction by 2030. ● REPowerEU: This plan accelerates clean energy deployment at all scales, including building-level renewables. ● EU Climate Adaptation Strategy, Circular Economy Action Plan, and Digital Europe Programme: These initiatives support sustainable building solutions, efficient resource use, and digital innovation (Monitoring and control). ● Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy: This supports local governments in aligning their actions with EU climate and energy targets.

- **Smart Cities Marketplace / Clean Energy for EU Islands / Energy Poverty Advisory Hub:** These platforms provide technical, financial, and governance tools to facilitate the implementation of energy-efficient, renewable-powered buildings.

National level

- **National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs):** These plans spell out how each country aims to hit the EU's energy and climate targets. Often, Nearly Zero-Energy Buildings (NZEBs) are a big part of cutting down emissions from homes and public buildings.
- **Recovery and Resilience Plans:** These plans get money from the EU to help countries recover green after COVID. Many national plans set aside a lot of cash for fixing up old buildings to make them NZEBs and for putting renewables into them.
- **National Building Codes:** These rules for building are often updated to make sure new buildings are much more energy-efficient and use renewable energy, following the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD).
- **Climate Adaptation Plans, Urban Agendas, Smart City strategies, Sustainable Mobility Plans, Circular Economy roadmaps, national Green Deals, specific climate laws, and funding programs like the NextGenerationEU recovery funds.**

Local level

- **Local Climate and Energy Plans (SECAPs or PACES):** Local governments often make climate plans that include renovating municipal buildings to NZEB level, especially schools, libraries, or housing for low-income families.
- **Local Urban Agendas (e.g. Agenda 21):** These focus on sustainable neighbourhoods and support better energy use in homes and public buildings.
- **Housing Renewal Plans:** Aim to upgrade old buildings. They combine energy efficiency with better living conditions, especially for vulnerable groups
- **Smart City Strategies:** Help cities use technology to reduce energy consumption, improve lighting and heating, and monitor energy use in real time.
- **Sustainable Mobility and Green Infrastructure Plans:** Even though they are focused on transport and nature, they are often connected to clean energy and better buildings.
- **City-specific strategies:** Some cities create their own local energy or renovation strategies. These may include solar roofs, heat networks, building retrofits, or rules for new buildings to follow NZEB standards.

● **STAKEHOLDER ROLES AND ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK**

Stakeholder	Role	Type of Collaboration
MUNICIPALITY	Permits, planning and grants	Regulatory / Financial
BUILDING OWNERS	Investment and decision making	Financial / Operational
USERS	Daily operation and behaviours	Social / Practical
DESIGNERS	Energy audit and system design	Advisory / Technical
INSTALLERS	Renewable setup and upgrades	Technical
ENERGY AGENCIES	Provide expertise, tools, and data to help define energy-efficient solutions	Technical / Advisory
LOCAL BUSINESSES	Supply materials, technologies, or services; may benefit from local jobs.	Economic / Technical
COMMUNITY GROUPS	Awareness and support	Social / Engagement

● **MAIN REFERENCES**

GOOD PRACTICES / SOME EXAMPLES
Project
<p>Project name: RENERMap Location: Europe Description: Decision-support tool that maps and assesses renewable energy potential in the built environment to support NZEB planning. Link: RENERMap Project – CARTIF</p> <p>Project name: LOCALRES Location: Europe Description: Empowers citizens and local authorities to form renewable energy communities, integrating local RES generation and smart management. Link: LOCALRES Project – CARTIF</p> <p>Project name: ENFLATE Location: Europe Description: Uses digital tools to make energy consumption more flexible and integrates prosumers into the energy market, contributing to NZEB models. Link: ENFLATE Project – CARTIF</p> <p>Project name: METABUILD Location: Europe Description: Demonstrates how to optimise building performance and life-cycle sustainability using digital twin and multi-energy models. Link: METABUILD Project – CARTIF</p> <p>Project name: CITYfied Location: Several EU countries</p>

Description: Aims to develop replicable, systemic strategies for retrofitting urban districts into smart, low-carbon, NZEB areas.

Link: CITYfied Project – CARTIF

Web-site

Website: BUILD UP – The European Portal for Energy Efficiency in Buildings

Link: <https://build-up.ec.europa.eu/>

Description: This portal offers extensive resources, case studies, news, and technical guidance on energy efficiency in buildings, including NZEBs and renovation strategies across Europe.

Website: NetZeroCities Knowledge Repository

Link: <https://netzerocities.app/knowledge>

Description: A resource hub providing tools, case studies, and guidance to support cities in achieving climate neutrality.

Website: BUILD UP_ The European Portal for Energy Efficiency in Buildings

Link: <https://build-up.ec.europa.eu>

Description: Offers high-quality resources, technical reports, news, and case studies on building renovation, NZEBs, and EU energy policies.

Paper

Paper title: Assessment of the renewable energy generation towards net-zero energy buildings: A review

Authors: Asam Ahmed, Tianshu Ge, Jinqing Peng, Wei-Cheng Yan, Boon Tuan Tee, Siming You

Journal: Energy and Buildings

DOI or link: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2021.111755>

Paper title: Renewable energy potential towards attainment of net-zero energy buildings status – A critical review

Authors: S. Christopher, M.P. Vikram, Chirodeep Bakli, Amrit Kumar Thakur, Y. Ma, Zhenjun Ma, Huijin Xu, Pinar Mert Cuce, Erdem Cuce, Punit Singh

Journal: Journal of Cleaner Production

DOI or link: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136942>

Paper title: An Overview on Functional Integration of Hybrid Renewable Energy Systems in Multi-Energy Buildings

Authors: L. Canale, A.R. Di Fazio, M. Russo, A. Frattolillo

Journal: Energies

DOI or link: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14175520>

Paper title: Energy communities—lessons learnt, challenges, and policy recommendations

Authors: L. Neij, J. Palm, H. Busch, T. Bauwens, S. Becker, A. Bergek, A. Buzogány, C. Candelise, F. Coenen, P. Devine-Wright, et al.

Journal: Oxford Open Energy, Volume 4, 2025

DOI or link: <https://doi.org/10.1093/ooenergy/oiaf002>

Paper title: Renewable energy communities for sustainable cities: Economic insights into subsidies, market dynamics and benefits distribution

Authors: Paolo Basilico, Alberto Biancardi, Idiano D'Adamo, Massimo Gastaldi, Tan Yigitcanlar

Journal: *Applied Energy*

DOI or link: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2025.125752>

Paper title: *Energy communities in social sciences: A bibliometric analysis and systematic literature review*

Authors: Maksym Koltunov, Lorenzo De Vidovich

Journal: *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*

DOI or link: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.115871>

Paper title: *Solar Thermal Heating and Cooling: Technology Development Report*

Authors: Carlsson J.

Journal: European Commission – Joint Research Centre

DOI or link: <https://doi.org/10.2760/706387> (online)

- **KEY CONSIDERATIONS**

Additional Notes

- **Energy Demand Reduction:** Prioritize building design and renovation strategies that minimize energy consumption (insulation, passive design, and energy-efficient appliances).
- **Renewable Energy Integration:** Select and integrate appropriate renewable sources; solar (PV, BIPV, PVT), wind, geothermal, biomass, and hydropower; based on local resource availability and building characteristics.
- **Lifecycle Assessment:** Assess the environmental and economic impacts of renewable systems over their lifecycle, including payback periods, CO₂ savings, and maintenance requirements.
- **Energy Communities and Smart Management:** Explore participation in energy communities for shared generation, storage, and consumption, leveraging smart systems for optimization.

Factsheet 3.- Environmental: New Design Paradigm (DEMIR)

ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS	NEW DESIGN PARADIGM
DESCRIPTION	
Technical description	
<p>At the heart of this new design thinking is the New European Bauhaus, a creative and interdisciplinary initiative launched by the European Commission. It serves as a bridge between the ambitions of the European Green Deal and the everyday realities of citizens. The NEB promotes design that is <i>sustainable</i>, <i>aesthetic</i>, and <i>inclusive</i>, bringing together architecture, urban planning, culture, technology, and civic engagement into a holistic model. It encourages participatory and co-creative processes in urban and building design, with a strong emphasis on community ownership and place-sensitive development. The architectural dimension of NEB focuses on using sustainable and circular materials, energy-efficient construction methods, and designs that reflect local identity.</p> <p>Complementing this is the use of Nature-Based Solutions. NBS improve climate resilience, enhance biodiversity, regulate temperature and water cycles, and provide social and recreational value. They include interventions such as green roofs and walls, urban forests, permeable surfaces, rain gardens, and constructed wetlands. These solutions not only mitigate environmental risks like flooding or heatwaves but also contribute to improved physical and mental health. Technically, their performance can be measured through indicators such as stormwater retention capacity, urban heat island reduction, biodiversity indices, and air pollutant filtration.</p> <p>A closely related idea is Biophilic Architecture, which focuses on bringing people closer to nature in the places where they live and work. Biophilic design can include things like indoor gardens, green walls, views of trees from windows, or the use of wood and stone inside buildings. It can also mean making spaces feel open, using natural shapes and patterns, or designing for better natural light and airflow. In renovation projects, especially in social and affordable housing, applying biophilic design means creating homes that feel more comfortable and connected to nature, while also being energy-efficient and sustainable.</p> <p>7 ways to incorporate biophilic design into a building</p> <p>There are a wide range of ways the built environment can incorporate natural and environmental features into buildings and infrastructure, including¹:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Indoor plants From potted plants to pergolas lined with intricate vines and even trees, the simplest way to boost connection and exposure to nature is to bring plants into your home, building or office. This is best exemplified by One Central Park in Australia and Garden and House in Japan. 2. Use natural materials A more subtle technique in biophilic design is the use of natural materials in construction and decoration, such as wood, bamboo, rattan or cork. 1 Hotels suites such as their Hanalei Bay 	

¹ University of the Build Environment <https://www.ube.ac.uk/whats-happening/articles/biophilia-examples-built-environment/#Heading%204> , 10 Jan 2025

location are constructed with salvaged materials, as well as reclaimed components like marble and stone.

3. Incorporate water elements

Indoor water elements are another effective way to foster human connections to nature in urban environments. Water features have been found to decrease stress and increase relaxation, according to research. In busy, bustling city environments, they help address noise pollution and create a sense of peace and calm.

4. Mimic natural environments in your design

Biomimicry is the replication of natural elements to solve human challenges. While it's not the same as biophilia, in the context of design and architecture these two philosophies can be combined to great effect. Mimicking images of nature in design can improve human health and wellbeing, as well as helping optimise both sustainability and environmental performance.

5. Utilise natural lighting

Exposure to natural light is an essential part of a healthy lifestyle. It's also something we're severely lacking, with research published by the Lawrence Berkley National Library finding that we spend 90% of our time in indoor environments.

Unsurprisingly, natural light is a significant element of biophilic design, as evidenced by One Central Park in Australia and The Jewel in Singapore among many others. It can be easily incorporated through skylights, outdoor spaces, large windows and the use of mirrors.

6. Add green spaces and easy access to nature

Adding green public spaces to urban environments is another effective way of bringing natural elements into our everyday lives. They offer a wealth of benefits, from improving air quality and reducing noise pollution to offsetting carbon emissions and creating habitat for wildlife.

7. Incorporate natural ventilation

Another way to implement the health benefits of biophilia in an indoor environment is through utilising natural ventilation. This can be achieved through operable windows and vents. Implementing operable windows can improve the air quality of a building – achieving a similar outcome to a mechanical ventilation system with far less noise (and cost).

Jewel Changi Airport in Singapore is one of the most impressive examples of biophilic architecture in the world. It shows what's possible when designers and architects prioritize the human experience of the built environment and incorporate natural elements into the design. *Photo: Matteo Morando*

Benefits of Biophilic Design

- **Improved well-being:** Biophilic design has been shown to improve mood, reduce stress levels, and increase productivity.

- **Environmental sustainability:** By incorporating natural elements into the built environment, biophilic design can reduce energy consumption, water usage, and waste production.
- **Increased property value:** Biophilic design can increase the value of a property by making it more attractive to buyers and renters.

Difference Between Biophilic and Green Architecture

While biophilic architecture and green architecture share some similarities, there are also some key differences.

Green architecture focuses primarily on **reducing the environmental impact of buildings** through the use of **sustainable materials, energy-efficient systems, and renewable energy sources**.

On the other hand, biophilic architecture focuses more on the **human experience of the built environment**, seeking to improve well-being and productivity by **connecting people with nature**. While both approaches are important for creating sustainable and healthy buildings, **biophilic architecture places more emphasis on the psychological and emotional benefits of connecting with nature**.

Architecture has a profound influence on our mental and emotional well-being. Thoughtful design can nurture joy, creativity, and connection, while poorly conceived spaces can foster stress, isolation, and anxiety. From biophilic design to cohousing concepts, and improvements in low-income areas, architectural strategies demonstrate that environments can be transformed to uplift lives. As we continue to evolve our understanding of mental health, it is essential to prioritize spaces that support human flourishing. The challenge for architects, planners, and policymakers is clear: to create environments that heal, inspire, and connect us to one another—and to ourselves.

SCORING

Technical Scoring

The New Design Paradigm requires advanced expertise across architecture, ecology, and engineering. It involves integrating Nature-Based Solutions and biophilic features into existing systems (e.g., drainage, ventilation), which can be complex—especially in dense or older urban areas. High coordination across disciplines and site-specific adaptation further increase the technical challenge, justifying a high difficulty score.

Finance Scoring

The New Design Paradigm typically requires a moderate initial investment, especially when incorporating custom design features, sustainable materials, and Nature-Based Solutions like green roofs or rain gardens. While biophilic elements (e.g., natural light, ventilation, greenery) can often be integrated passively at low cost, some components—like structural adaptations or integrated water systems—can increase expenses. Operational and maintenance costs vary depending on design complexity and community involvement. NBS features may require specialized care, though native or low-maintenance solutions can reduce long-term costs. In many cases, external funding may be needed to support implementation in social or public housing contexts.

Environment Scoring

The New Design Paradigm delivers strong environmental benefits through its integration of Nature-Based Solutions, biophilic elements, and NEB principles. It significantly contributes to emission reduction by encouraging passive design strategies (e.g., natural ventilation, daylighting) that lower energy demand. NBS features like green roofs, permeable surfaces, and urban greenery enhance biodiversity, stormwater management, and urban cooling, reducing pressure on grey infrastructure.

Social Scoring

It is generally well-aligned with public values such as health, comfort, inclusion, and quality of life. Biophilic elements and green public spaces are widely appreciated for improving mental well-being, social interaction, and aesthetic value. These features tend to be highly visible and positively perceived by communities. While acceptance is strong overall, resistance may arise in contexts where maintenance capacity or awareness is limited.

CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

Recurrent risks

Technical Complexity: Integrating NBS and biophilic features with existing infrastructure can cause delays or design conflicts, especially in dense or older urban areas.

Budget Constraints: Higher upfront costs for sustainable materials, custom designs, and specialized labor may exceed initial budgets, particularly in public or social housing contexts.

Maintenance Gaps: Long-term care of green elements (e.g., green roofs, rain gardens) requires clear responsibilities and funding; lack of planning can lead to deterioration.

Climate and Site Constraints: Local climate, soil conditions, or water availability may limit the feasibility of certain NBS or biophilic features.

- **TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE**

Phases of implementation	
P1	Pre-Design: Visioning & Context Assessment
Establish the project's goals and framework through collaborative analysis of the physical, social and ecological context.	
P1.1	Define Integrated Goals Align the design approach with NEB values (sustainability, inclusion, aesthetics), environmental objectives (e.g., climate resilience), and human well-being.
P1.2	Environmental & Spatial Assessment Analyze site-specific features including solar access, wind, vegetation, soil, water flow, noise and existing infrastructure.
P1.3	Social & Cultural Mapping Explore community demographics, mobility patterns, nature-culture relationships, and accessibility challenges.
P2	Design Development & Planning
Translate shared goals into coordinated design and prepare for implementation.	
P2.1	Integrated Spatial Planning

	Develop spatial layouts, landscape plans and architectural schemes based on site findings and engagement outcomes.
P2.2	Nature-Based and Climate-Responsive Integration Plan for multi-benefit systems such as green roofs, permeable surfaces, tree canopies, or rain gardens where context allows.
P2.3	Regulatory & Technical Alignment Ensure the design complies with local regulations (housing, safety, environmental), and conduct technical assessments where needed.
P3	Construction & Implementation
Deliver the physical transformation of the site while protecting natural assets and ensuring inclusive access.	
P3.1	Site Preparation & Protection Secure and prepare the site while preserving existing trees, soil quality, and local ecosystems.
P3.2.	Execution of Built and Ecological Elements Implement housing upgrades, shared spaces, and planned features such as semi-open areas, planting schemes, water elements, and NBS interventions.
P3.3.	Quality Assurance & Safety Compliance Monitor construction to ensure material standards, environmental protection, and accessibility criteria are met.
P4	Post-Occupancy Operation & Monitoring
Enable residents to use and shape the space, while tracking how the environment performs.	
P4.1.	Orientation & Community Introduction Provide guidance to residents on using shared spaces, green elements and resource-saving infrastructure.
P4.2.	Environmental & Social Performance Monitoring Track key indicators such as thermal comfort, air quality, biodiversity, noise levels, and social use of outdoor areas.
P4.3	System Calibration & Maintenance Setup Finalize maintenance routines for shared elements (e.g., green roofs, water systems, public furniture), assigning roles or service contracts.
P5	Community Engagement & Long-Term Stewardship
Support sustained, resident-led ownership and activation of the transformed spaces.	
P5.1	Local Stewardship Structures Establish resident committees, co-ops, or partnerships with local actors to care for shared assets and promote inclusivity.
P5.2	Periodic Review & Adaptation Encourage long-term reflection and flexibility, allowing the design and use of the space to evolve with community needs.

- GANTT

		M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
P1	Pre-Design: Visioning & Context Assessment												
	P.1.1 Define Integrated Goals												
	P.1.2 Environmental & Spatial Assessment												
	P.1.3 Social & Cultural Mapping												
P2	Design Development & Planning												
	P.2.1 Integrated Spatial Planning												
	P.2.2 Nature-Based and Climate-Responsive Integration												
	P.2.3 Regulatory & Technical Alignment												
P3	Construction & Implementation												
	P.3.1 Site Preparation & Protection												
	P.3.2 Execution of Built and Ecological Elements												
	P.3.3 Quality Assurance & Safety Compliance												
P4	Post-Occupancy Operation & Monitoring												
	P.4.1 Orientation & Community Introduction												
	P.4.2 Environmental & Social Performance Monitoring												
	P.4.3 System Calibration & Maintenance Setup												
P5	Community Engagement & Long-Term Stewardship												
	P.5.1 Local Stewardship Structures												
	P.5.2 Periodic Review & Adaptation												

● **STRATEGIC**

RECOMMENDATIONS			
DOs	Do assess the local environment and social needs.	DON'Ts	Don't install green features without local ecological fit.
	Do apply multifunctional Nature-Based Solutions.		Don't ignore residents' preferences and cultural context.
	Do design green spaces that support biodiversity and climate adaptation.		Don't rely solely on artificial or high-tech nature simulations.
	Do use natural materials and maximize daylight and ventilation.		Don't create inaccessible or unsafe natural areas.
	Do connect people with nature through plants, water, and natural patterns.		Don't neglect coordination with urban planning and infrastructure.

● CROSS-LINK MATRIX BETWEEN TECHNICAL ACTIONS

Main Topic ↓ Related →	Pre-Design: Visioning & Context Assessment	Design Development & Planning	Construction & Implementation	Post-Occupancy Operation & Monitoring	Community Engagement & Long-Term Stewardship
Pre-Design: Visioning & Context Assessment		S Clear vision and assessment guide detailed design.	R Early vision informs construction approaches.		C Early engagement supports future stewardship.
Design Development & Planning			S Design development directly leads into construction execution.		
Construction & Implementation					
Post-Occupancy Operation & Monitoring				C Smooth handover and operation need close coordination.	
Community Engagement & Long-Term Stewardship				S Operation phase and community stewardship strongly reinforce each other.	

● POLICY FRAMEWORK

Relevant Policies
International level
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UN 2030 Agenda & Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): Especially SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being). ● Paris Agreement: Helps meet climate targets through emission reductions in the built environment and ecosystem-based adaptation strategies (e.g., urban cooling, carbon capture through vegetation).
European level
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● New European Bauhaus (NEB): It calls for transforming public spaces and housing into environments that inspire, heal and belong to everyone. The design paradigm operationalizes NEB values through architecture and urban planning.

- EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030: Encourages cities to integrate green spaces, green roofs and pollinator corridors — all key Nature-Based Solutions.

National level

- *National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs): Encourage energy-efficient renovation and construction aligned with NEB’s vision for sustainable, beautiful, and inclusive buildings.*
- *Sustainable Mobility Plans: Integrate green corridors and pedestrian zones lined with native vegetation, linking biophilic urban design with low-carbon mobility, enhancing accessibility, and contributing to healthier cities.*

Local level

- Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans: These plans incorporate Nature-Based Solutions and biophilic design as measurable targets for urban heat reduction, air quality improvement, and enhanced climate resilience, aligned with NEB’s emphasis on sustainable and health-promoting environments.
- Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP): SUMPs integrate green corridors and pedestrian pathways lined with native vegetation, embedding biophilic elements that improve user experience and support low-carbon transport modes consistent with NEB’s vision for inclusive, liveable cities.

• **STAKEHOLDER ROLES AND ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK**

Stakeholder	Role	Type of Collaboration
National Authorities	Define sustainability laws, NEB-aligned policies, green building regulations, and allocate national funding	Regulatory
Municipal Authorities	Approve permits, integrate NBS in urban planning, ensure accessibility, support community outreach	Regulatory/ Participatory
Architects & Urban Designers	Lead spatial and biophilic design, interpret NEB values into built form, integrate passive and nature-based elements	Technical
Construction Companies	Implement NEB/NBS designs using appropriate materials, ensure quality of green infrastructure and biophilic features	Technical
Academic / Research Institutions	Monitor outcomes, provide LCA/S-LCA tools, evaluate impacts of NBS and biophilic strategies	Technical/ Advisory
NGOs / Civil Society Groups	Advocate for inclusion, coordinate community activities, support education and communication	Facilitator/ Participatory
Residents / Community Members	Co-create project goals, use and care for spaces, offer feedback post-occupancy	Participatory

● MAIN REFERENCES

GOOD PRACTICES / SOME EXAMPLES	
Project	
15.	Urban GreenUp
Web-site	
16.	European Commission – New European Bauhaus https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu
17.	European Commission. (2021). <i>Communication on the New European Bauhaus</i> https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_21_4627
18.	European Commission. <i>Nature-Based Solutions and Re-Naturing Cities</i> https://www.greenpolicyplatform.org/sites/default/files/downloads/resource/Guarnacci_Nature-Based%20Solutions.pdf
19.	European Environment Agency (EEA). (2021). <i>Urban sustainability and biophilia in city planning</i>
Paper	
20.	Kellert, S. R., Heerwagen, J. H., & Mador, M. L. (2008). <i>Biophilic Design: The Theory, Science and Practice of Bringing Buildings to Life</i>
21.	Terrapin Bright Green. (2014). <i>14 Patterns of Biophilic Design</i> https://www.terrabinbrightgreen.com/reports/14-patterns/

Factsheet 4.- Environmental: Urban Decarbonisation (CIRCE)

LOW CARBON DISTRICT	URBAN DECARBONISATION
DESCRIPTION	
Technical description	
<p><i>Integrated urban decarbonisation combines deep renovation, system electrification and sector coupling. Under the revised EPBD (Directive (EU) 2024/1275), Member States must establish MEPS and renovation trajectories; the EED (2023/1791) sets a binding 11.7% consumption reduction target by 2030. The EU will introduce ETS2 for fuels in buildings and road transport to incentivise emissions cuts and fund social measures via the Social Climate Fund.</i></p> <p><i>EU cases: In Tartu (EE), SmartEnCity retrofitted 17 condominiums towards nZEB; preliminary data show ~43% average energy-demand reduction and 27–58% cuts by carrier. Sønderborg (DK) reports a 55% citywide CO₂ reduction (2007–2021) from efficiency, renewables, and district heating.</i></p> <p><i>Key metrics to track: primary energy (kWh/m²·y), operational GHG (kgCO₂e/m²·y), embodied GHG for retrofits (kgCO₂e/m²), RES share (%), electrification ratio (% heat via HP/DH), flexibility (kW curtailed or shifted), and mobility emissions (gCO₂e/pkm).</i></p>	
SCORING	
Technical Scoring	
<p><i>Implementation requires advanced expertise in energy modelling, HVAC retrofits, BEMS, district energy, and system integration with mobility and the grid. Technical coordination is complex due to the need for interoperability (ISO/IEC standards, smart meters, etc.) and large-scale project management. Difficulty is medium-high because most technologies are mature but require integration at scale.</i></p>	
Finance Scoring	
<p><i>High upfront CAPEX (retrofits, renewables, storage, mobility charging). OPEX can be reduced through efficiency gains. External funding often needed (EU cohesion funds, NextGenerationEU, green bonds). Long payback but strong climate and energy-security benefits.</i></p>	
Environment Scoring	
<p><i>Strong environmental benefits: 40–60% operational CO₂ reductions possible at district scale, with added flexibility and RES share. Risks include embodied emissions of retrofits if not mitigated with circular strategies.</i></p>	
Social Scoring	

Generally well accepted if co-designed. Risks of disruption during works and affordability issues (if ETS2 costs passed to households). Strong acceptance when combined with subsidies and citizen engagement.

CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

Recurrent risks

Urban decarbonisation projects often face several recurring risks. Technical difficulties arise from integrating multiple systems (district heating, renewables, building retrofits, smart grids) that require interoperability and advanced expertise. Budget limitations can delay deep renovation or large-scale renewable deployment, particularly when upfront CAPEX is high and external funding is uncertain. Social resistance may occur among end-users who are skeptical about disruptions, rising costs (e.g., from ETS2), or changes in daily routines. Legal and regulatory restrictions—such as slow permitting processes, zoning constraints, or inconsistent transposition of EU directives—can further complicate implementation.

City Issues

Many cities still struggle with structural problems that amplify decarbonisation challenges. High traffic congestion increases energy demand and local air pollution, while a lack of green areas limits opportunities for carbon sinks and resilience to heatwaves. Poor housing stock, especially buildings constructed before thermal regulations, exhibits high energy consumption and weak comfort levels, making retrofits both urgent and costly.

Environmental Problems

Cities remain hotspots of environmental stress: air pollution (NO₂, PM_{2.5}), noise, and urban heat islands exacerbate climate vulnerability. Rising climate risks—heatwaves, flooding, and drought—require decarbonisation measures that also increase resilience. Decarbonisation projects must therefore address not only emission reductions but also adaptation and environmental quality improvements.

Management Gaps

Weak planning capacity, fragmented governance between municipal departments, and insufficient citizen involvement often undermine the success of urban decarbonisation programmes. A lack of integrated strategies across buildings, mobility, and energy systems may lead to sub-optimal results. Limited technical staff in municipalities also hampers long-term monitoring and evaluation.

Obsolete Technologies

Many urban infrastructures rely on outdated technologies with high energy consumption and poor environmental performance—such as inefficient boilers, poorly insulated housing, conventional street lighting, or legacy public transport fleets. These assets are often incompatible with current standards (e.g., EPBD MEPS, Euro 7, or smart-ready requirements), making replacement or deep renovation unavoidable.

- TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE

Phases of implementation	
P1	Diagnostics & Planning
Establish a robust baseline and prepare a detailed roadmap for decarbonisation, using internationally accepted methodologies. This phase ensures realistic targets, resource allocation, and stakeholder engagement.	
P1.1	Baseline & Inventory Develop a city-wide energy and GHG inventory using the Global Protocol for Community-Scale GHG Emission Inventories (GPC) and EN ISO 52000-1. Collect data from smart meters (IEC 62056) to establish hourly/daily load profiles. Technical values: baseline in kWh/m ² ·year for buildings; CO ₂ intensity in kgCO ₂ e/m ² ; mobility emissions in gCO ₂ /pkm.
P1.2	Targets & Roadmap Define measurable objectives aligned with EPBD Directive (EU) 2024/1275 and EED Directive (EU) 2023/1791 , such as 50% reduction in operational emissions by 2030 and 11.7% EU energy-consumption reduction target . Roadmap includes prioritised actions: retrofits, renewables, and transport electrification.
P1.3	Feasibility & Governance Conduct techno-economic assessments for renovation packages (U-value targets ≤ 0.30 W/m ² K for façades; COP > 4 for heat pumps; PV yield > 1,200 kWh/kWp·year). Establish governance (One-Stop-Shop models) and financing strategies (NextGenerationEU funds, Social Climate Fund).
P2	Implementation
Deliver energy efficiency, renewable deployment, and integrated mobility actions, ensuring system compatibility and optimised sequencing.	
P2.1	Building Retrofits Upgrade building envelopes, HVAC, and controls. Ensure air-tightness ≤ 3.0 m ³ /h·m ² at 50 Pa for existing retrofitted buildings. Integrate BEMS (ISO 50001/50002)
P2.2	Distributed Energy & Flexibility install rooftop/community PV systems (target: >30% RES share in electricity mix), heat pumps (SCOP ≥ 4), and thermal storage. Enable demand response using IEC 61850/62351.
P3	Commissioning, MRV & Optimisation
Ensure operational performance, continuous monitoring, and long-term scaling.	
P3.1	Commissioning & Tuning: Conduct functional testing of retrofitted systems and digital twins to calibrate against baseline. Metrics: heating/cooling demand reductions ≥ 40%; peak load reductions ≥ 20%.

MRV (Measurement, Reporting, Verification): Apply ISO 50001 MRV cycles and annual audits. Dashboards to report kWh/m²·year, kgCO₂e/m²·year, flexibility capacity (kW/°C), and renewable share (%).

Scaling & Replication: Develop replication pathways for other districts, incorporating lessons learned. Align with Mission 100 Climate-Neutral Cities and update to latest EPBD MEPS.

● GANTT

		M 1	M 2	M 3	M 3	M 4	M 5	M 6	M 7	M 8	M 9	M 10	M 11	M 12
P1	Diagnostics & Planning													
P2	Implementation													
P3	Commisioning & MRV													

● STRATEGIC

RECOMMENDATIONS	
DOs	<p>Integrate with local context: Start with priority districts where housing stock is old (pre-1980s) and energy performance is poorest; this maximises cost-effectiveness and social benefit.</p> <p>Leverage EU and national frameworks: Align local decarbonisation with the EPBD recast 2024, EED 2023/1791, and national PNIEC goals. This ensures eligibility for funding (NextGenerationEU, Cohesion Policy, Social Climate Fund).</p> <p>Engage citizens and stakeholders early: Establish “One-Stop-Shops” for building renovation advice, and include citizen assemblies or HOA workshops to improve acceptance.</p>
DON'Ts	<p>Do not ignore affordability: Implementing ETS2-driven measures without support schemes risks fuel poverty and social backlash.</p> <p>Avoid siloed actions: Retrofitting buildings without considering mobility and grid interactions can cause rebound effects (e.g., electrification raising peak demand).</p> <p>Don't underestimate legal barriers: Starting large retrofits without checking zoning, heritage restrictions, or public procurement rules leads to delays.</p> <p>Do not over-rely on technology alone: Technical fixes without citizen engagement can face resistance and underperformance.</p>

<p>Combine measures with co-benefits: Link decarbonisation with improvements in air quality, comfort, and public health (reducing respiratory illnesses).</p> <p>Adopt digital tools: Use digital twins and open data platforms to integrate monitoring and accelerate replication.</p> <p>Pilot, then scale: Begin with compact urban districts to validate approaches, then expand citywide.</p>	<p>Avoid “one-size-fits-all” strategies: Each neighbourhood has unique socio-economic and building stock conditions; applying uniform solutions undermines effectiveness.</p> <p>Do not neglect resilience: Focusing only on CO₂ reductions without addressing climate risks (heatwaves, flooding) can create vulnerabilities.</p>
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- **POLICY FRAMEWORK**

Relevant Policies
<p>International level</p> <p><i>European Green Deal – overarching EU commitment to climate neutrality by 2050.</i></p> <p><i>2030 Agenda & SDGs – particularly SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), and SDG 13 (Climate Action).</i></p> <p><i>Paris Agreement & COP targets – legally binding framework to limit global warming to 1.5–2 °C.</i></p> <p><i>New European Bauhaus – design and cultural initiative linking sustainability, aesthetics, and inclusion.</i></p> <p><i>UN-Habitat New Urban Agenda – global framework for sustainable urban development.</i></p> <p><i>Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy – city-level commitments to reduce emissions and adapt to climate change.</i></p> <p><i>Resilient Cities Network & Just Transition Framework – ensuring that climate neutrality pathways consider social justice and resilience.</i></p>
<p>European level</p> <p><i>Fit for 55 Package (2021) – emission reduction package including ETS2 for buildings and road transport, binding energy efficiency and renewable targets.</i></p> <p><i>Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD, 2024/1275) – mandates Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPS), smart-ready provisions, and rooftop PV requirements.</i></p>

Energy Efficiency Directive (EED, 2023/1791) – binding 11.7% final energy reduction target by 2030.

Renovation Wave Initiative – goal to double renovation rates by 2030, addressing energy poverty and stimulating construction jobs.

REPowerEU Plan (2022) – accelerates electrification, heat pumps, rooftop PV, and energy security measures.

EU Climate Adaptation Strategy – integrates adaptation measures into city decarbonisation.

Smart Cities Marketplace – EU platform for scaling integrated energy solutions.

EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 – promotes green infrastructure and nature-based solutions for resilience and decarbonisation.

Digital Europe Programme – supports data and digital infrastructure relevant to smart grids and building systems.

National level (Spain)

Plan Nacional Integrado de Energía y Clima (PNIEC) 2023–2030 – sets targets for 42% renewable energy share, 39.5% efficiency improvements, and 23% GHG reduction vs 1990 by 2030.

Ley de Cambio Climático y Transición Energética (2021) – Spanish climate law committing to climate neutrality by 2050.

Estrategia de Movilidad Segura, Sostenible y Conectada 2030 (MITMA) – integrates decarbonisation with mobility and transport.

National Renovation Strategy (ERESEE) – long-term plan for building energy retrofits, aligned with EPBD.

Circular Economy Roadmap 2030 – enhances resource efficiency and material reuse, supporting low-carbon construction.

NextGenerationEU Recovery Funds – significant financing instrument for building retrofits, RES deployment, and district energy.

Local level

SECAPs (Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans) – municipal plans under the Covenant of Mayors framework.

Local Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP) – align transport decarbonisation with building and energy measures.

Local Housing and Regeneration Strategies – policies promoting energy renovation in social housing and low-income neighbourhoods.

Agenda Urbana Española (Spanish Urban Agenda) – guides municipalities in sustainable, integrated planning.

Green Infrastructure & Renaturalisation Strategies – link building retrofits with urban heat island mitigation.

Open Data & Smart City Action Plans – enable monitoring, citizen engagement, and digital tools for energy management.

● **STAKEHOLDER ROLES AND ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK**

Stakeholder	Role	Type of Collaboration
Municipality / City Council	Regulation, local planning authority, co-financing of retrofits, zoning and permitting. Lead implementation through Climate Action Plans and SECAPs.	Regulatory / Financial
Regional / National Government	<i>Define policy frameworks (EPBD transposition, PNIEC targets), distribute EU/national funds (NextGenerationEU, Cohesion Funds), ensure compliance.</i>	Regulatory / Financial
DSOs & Utilities	<i>Grid reinforcement, integration of renewables and EV charging, operation of district heating/cooling networks, demand response platforms.</i>	<i>Technical / Infrastructure / Market</i>
Private Developers & ESCOs	<i>Carry out building retrofits, provide EPC/ESCO contracts, integrate BEMS and renewable systems. Assume technical and financial risks.</i>	<i>Technical / Financial</i>
<i>Citizens / Homeowners Associations (HOAs)</i>	<i>Decision-making on building retrofits, participation in co-design, energy behaviour changes, demand response programmes</i>	<i>Participatory / Social</i>

● **MAIN REFERENCES**

GOOD PRACTICES / SOME EXAMPLES
Project
<i>Project name: SmartEnCity (H2020)</i>
<i>Location: Tartu (Estonia), Sonderborg (Denmark), Vitoria-Gasteiz (Spain)</i>

Description: SmartEnCity demonstrated large-scale retrofitting of multi-family buildings into near-zero energy districts, integration of renewable energy, smart city platforms, and citizen engagement strategies. Tartu achieved an average 43% reduction in energy demand across 17 condominiums, while Sonderborg reduced 55% of citywide CO₂ emissions between 2007–2021.

Link: <https://smartencity.eu/>

Web-site

Website: European Commission – Energy Performance of Buildings

Link: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-performance-buildings/energy-performance-buildings-directive_en

Description: The EC's official page on the EPBD provides updated information on legislative requirements, minimum energy performance standards (MEPS), and links to supporting initiatives such as the Renovation Wave and Smart Readiness Indicator.

Paper

Paper title: Deep decarbonisation pathways for cities

Authors: Creutzig, F., et al.

Journal: Nature Climate Change, 6, 873–875 (2016).

DOI/Link: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate3136>

Description: This paper provides an integrated analysis of strategies available to cities for achieving deep decarbonisation, highlighting the role of building retrofits, renewable energy, sustainable mobility, and behaviour change.

Factsheet 5.- Environmental/ Social: Sustainable mobility (CIRCE)

LOW CARBON DISTRICT	SUSTAINABLE MOBILITY
DESCRIPTION	
Technical description	
<p><i>Sustainable Mobility focuses on reshaping urban transport systems to reduce emissions, improve accessibility, and enhance quality of life. The action involves a shift from private car dependency toward active travel (walking and cycling), electrified public transport, and shared mobility solutions. The objective is to design an integrated, people-centred mobility system that prioritises safety, inclusivity, and efficiency, while aligning with EU climate and urban policy targets.</i></p> <p><i>Mobility contributes to more than 30% of urban CO₂ emissions in Europe. Cars still dominate modal shares in many medium and large cities, causing congestion, air pollution, and noise. Shifting to sustainable modes can drastically reduce per-capita emissions, improve public health, and reclaim urban space for social use. The action described here builds on the EU Urban Mobility Framework and SUMP (Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans) methodology, ensuring both planning consistency and adaptability to local contexts.</i></p> <p>The technical objectives of this action are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Reduce transport-related emissions by encouraging modal shift and zero-emission vehicle use.</i> ● <i>Improve accessibility by providing safe, continuous, and affordable mobility options for all, including vulnerable groups.</i> ● <i>Enhance public health by reducing air pollution and increasing active mobility.</i> ● <i>Increase system efficiency by integrating modes (walking, cycling, buses, trams, shared services) through physical and digital connectivity.</i> ● <i>Support EU policy goals such as the Fit for 55 package, New Urban Mobility Framework, and Climate-Neutral Cities Mission.</i> ● <i>Technical Aspects of Implementation</i> <p>1. Active Mobility Networks</p> <p>Infrastructure: <i>Continuous walking and cycling routes, protected cycle tracks (min. 2.0–2.5 m width per direction), safe intersections with protected signal phases, traffic calming in residential zones.</i></p> <p>Accessibility: <i>Sidewalks compliant with universal design, minimum 2.0 m clear width, ramps for wheelchairs and strollers.</i></p>	

Safety Standards: Alignment with Vision Zero principles; speed limits ≤ 30 km/h on urban residential streets.

2. Public Transport Modernisation

Electrification: Transition bus fleets to battery-electric or hydrogen fuel cell. Charging based on IEC 61851 standards (depot and/or opportunity charging).

Integration: Priority bus lanes, signal priority at intersections, and intermodal hubs linking buses, trams, and cycling networks.

Digitalisation: Real-time passenger information systems (GTFS, SIRI standards) and ticketing platforms that enable fare capping and MaaS (Mobility-as-a-Service).

3. Shared and Micro-Mobility Services

Shared Mobility Platforms: E-bikes, e-scooters, and car-sharing services regulated through permits and integrated with public transport.

Technical Standards: Compliance with EN 15194 (EPAC bicycles) and EN 17128 (e-scooters).

Management Tools: Geofencing for speed/parking control, docking infrastructure, and open data sharing via GBFS/MDS feeds.

4. Traffic and Space Management

Low-Emission Zones (LEZ): Restrict polluting vehicles in central areas to encourage sustainable modes.

Parking Reforms: Dynamic pricing, reduction of on-street car parking, and reallocation to bike lanes, bus stops, or green space.

Freight Logistics: Last-mile delivery hubs, cargo bikes, and time-window restrictions for heavy-duty vehicles.

5. Digital and Monitoring Infrastructure

ITS (Intelligent Transport Systems): Adaptive traffic lights, integrated multimodal dashboards, and open data portals.

KPIs: Modal share (% walking, cycling, public transport), accessibility (jobs within 45 min by sustainable modes), safety (fatalities/serious injuries per 100k), air quality (NO_2 , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$), and CO_2e per passenger-km.

Evaluation: Regular monitoring cycles (annual) and citizen feedback workshops to fine-tune measures.

Expected Outcomes

- **Environmental:** Reduction of up to 40–50% of CO₂ transport emissions in districts adopting strong LEZ + electrification policies.
- **Social:** Safer streets, higher physical activity rates, improved access to jobs and education for low-income groups.
- **Economic:** Reduced congestion costs, new green jobs in mobility services, and lower household expenditure on transport.
- **Governance:** Stronger integration between city planning, utilities, and private operators, supported by SUMPs as a binding planning tool.

SCORING

Technical Scoring

The technical difficulty of sustainable mobility measures is considered moderate. Most actions—such as building cycling lanes, reallocating road space, and electrifying bus fleets—are well-established technologies with clear design guidelines (EN 15194 for EPACs, EN 17128 for e-scooters, IEC 61851 for bus charging). The main challenge lies in integrating multiple systems (infrastructure, vehicles, ITS platforms, MaaS applications) and coordinating across departments and operators. Cities need engineering expertise in transport planning and ITS, but no breakthrough technologies are required. Implementation complexity increases in dense cities with limited road space, where design trade-offs are needed.

Finance Scoring

The financial cost is medium. Infrastructure for walking and cycling is relatively low-cost compared to road or rail projects. For instance, a kilometre of protected cycle track is typically an order of magnitude cheaper than road widening or tram construction. Public transport electrification requires significant upfront investments (vehicles, depots, charging infrastructure), but operational and maintenance costs decrease over time due to fuel and maintenance savings. Shared mobility platforms are usually co-financed by private operators, reducing public costs. Funding opportunities are available from NextGenerationEU, Cohesion Funds, and the European Investment Bank (EIB). Financial risk increases when large-scale fleet electrification is pursued without subsidies or bulk procurement strategies.

Environment Scoring

The environmental impact is highly positive. Sustainable mobility reduces GHG emissions, air pollution (NO₂, PM_{2.5}), and noise, while also contributing to reduced land consumption through compact, multimodal planning. Mode shift from private cars to walking, cycling, and public transport can reduce transport emissions by 30–50% in well-implemented districts. Electrified fleets eliminate local tailpipe emissions and, when combined with renewable electricity, achieve near-zero operational emissions. Additional environmental benefits include improved public

health, biodiversity gains (through less road expansion), and reduced material use compared to car-centric infrastructure.

Social Scoring

The social acceptance of sustainable mobility measures is generally very high, especially once users experience the benefits: safer streets, cleaner air, and more affordable transport options. Evidence from Barcelona’s Superblocks and Seville’s cycling network shows initial resistance from car users but rapid acceptance after implementation, with rising support over time. Accessibility improves for vulnerable groups (children, elderly, low-income residents) when safe walking and cycling routes and affordable public transport are provided. The main risks are political pushback or short-term opposition during the transition phase, especially when car restrictions are introduced without viable alternatives. However, long-term societal alignment with climate goals, public health, and inclusivity strongly favours acceptance.

CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

Recurrent risks

Recurrent

Frequent risks during implementation include **technical difficulties** (e.g., integrating new charging infrastructure into constrained electrical grids or ensuring interoperability of MaaS platforms), **budget limitations** for large fleet upgrades or high-quality infrastructure, **resistance from end-users** (drivers who oppose road-space reallocation or parking reforms), and **legal restrictions** such as national traffic laws that may limit micromobility or regulate LEZs differently across regions. These factors require proactive adaptation of the solution to each city’s legal and financial context.

Risks

City

Urban environments often face **high traffic congestion**, a lack of continuous walking and cycling infrastructure, and **insufficient green areas**. In many cities, **poor housing and social segregation** exacerbate mobility inequities, as residents of low-income districts are often furthest from high-quality public transport and safe active mobility routes. Addressing these issues requires mobility measures that are not only technical but also socially inclusive.

Issues

Environmental

Cities also confront **air pollution (NO₂, PM_{2.5})**, noise, and **climate-related risks** such as heatwaves that are worsened by car-centric design. Expanding sustainable mobility reduces emissions but must also integrate with **climate adaptation strategies**, for example by incorporating green corridors that combine active travel with shade, cooling, and stormwater management.

Problems

Management

Weak planning capacity, fragmented governance between transport agencies and municipal

Gaps

departments, and **low citizen involvement** are common gaps that undermine sustainable mobility projects. Without integrated planning (e.g., through SUMP) and active public engagement, measures risk underuse or public backlash.

Obsolete

Many cities still rely on **outdated bus fleets with high diesel consumption**, traffic-light systems that do not prioritise sustainable modes, and paper-based ticketing systems that fail to meet today’s standards of efficiency and integration. Replacing these with **zero-emission buses, ITS-controlled traffic flows, and integrated digital platforms** is critical to achieving EU climate and mobility objectives.

Technologies

- **TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE**

Phases of implementation	
P1	Assessment & Planning
P1.1	Baseline Analysis: Collect data on travel patterns, road safety, congestion, air quality, and existing walking/cycling infrastructure.
P1.2	Stakeholder Engagement Involve citizens, transport operators, NGOs, and businesses to identify needs and priorities.
P1.3	Mobility Plan Design: Draft a Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (SUMP) defining clear goals, priority corridors, and modes to promote (walking, cycling, public transport, shared mobility).
P2	Implementation
P2.1	Active Mobility Networks Build or upgrade safe, continuous cycling and walking routes, ensuring accessibility for all.
P2.2	Public Transport Improvements Modernise bus or tram fleets (preferably zero-emission), improve service frequency, and create dedicated priority lanes.
P2.3	Shared & New Mobility Introduce or regulate shared mobility services (e-bikes, e-scooters, car-sharing) and integrate them into existing systems.
P2.4	Traffic & Space Management Reallocate road space for sustainable modes, create low-emission zones, and manage parking or delivery areas.
P3	Monitoring & Optimisation
P3.1	Data Collection & KPIs Monitor indicators such as mode share, road safety, emissions, and user satisfaction.
P3.2	Public Feedback Conduct surveys and workshops to gather citizen feedback on implemented measures.
P3.3	Continuous Improvement Adjust and expand projects based on lessons learned and performance results.

- **GANTT**

		M 1	M 2	M 3	M 4	M 5	M 6	M 7	M 8	M 9	M 10	M 11	M 12
P1	Diagnostics & Planning												
P2	Implementation												
P3	Commisioning & MRV												

- **STRATEGIC**

RECOMMENDATIONS	
DOs	<p>Start with a solid baseline assessment: Collect mobility data (traffic volumes, congestion hotspots, accident records, public transport ridership, air quality indicators). This allows interventions to target the most critical issues.</p> <p>Prioritise compact and dense urban areas: These contexts are ideal for walking, cycling, and electrified public transport, as short trip distances make sustainable modes competitive.</p> <p>Leverage existing policy frameworks: Build upon the city’s SUMP (Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan), Climate Action Plans (SECAP), or national mobility strategies to ensure alignment and access to EU/national funds.</p> <p>Engage citizens and stakeholders early: Organise workshops with residents, schools, local businesses, and mobility operators to identify priorities and co-design safe routes. Public involvement increases acceptance and adoption.</p>
DON'Ts	<p>Do not neglect viable alternatives before restricting cars: Introducing Low-Emission Zones (LEZs) or parking restrictions without ensuring reliable public transport and safe active mobility infrastructure can generate public opposition and reduce acceptance.</p> <p>Avoid fragmented interventions: Implementing isolated bike lanes, partial bus corridors, or pilot projects without network continuity creates low usability and discourages adoption.</p> <p>Don’t underestimate financial risks: Electrifying fleets without a clear long-term funding plan (for depots, charging, and vehicle renewal) can create budgetary stress and dependence on subsidies.</p> <p>Do not overlook inclusivity: If measures are not designed with universal accessibility in mind, vulnerable groups (elderly, children, people with disabilities, low-income residents) may face reduced mobility options.</p>

<p>Integrate with housing and regeneration projects: Combine mobility improvements with social housing upgrades and public space renewal, ensuring vulnerable communities benefit.</p> <p>Use quick-build, low-cost pilots: Test cycling lanes, bus priority corridors, or shared mobility hubs with temporary infrastructure (paint, bollards, parklets) to demonstrate impact quickly.</p> <p>Apply digital tools for integration: Ensure open data (GTFS, GBFS, MDS) and MaaS platforms are in place for multimodal journey planning, fare capping, and real-time passenger information.</p> <p>Seek EU/national funding: Mobilise resources from programmes such as NextGenerationEU, Cohesion Funds, or Horizon Europe pilot projects to support fleet electrification and large-scale infrastructure.</p>	<p>Avoid technology without governance: Deploying shared mobility services or MaaS platforms without clear regulations (parking rules, safety standards, open data) often leads to chaos, unfair competition, or public backlash.</p> <p>Don't ignore behavioural change: Infrastructure alone does not guarantee usage—neglecting awareness campaigns, school mobility programmes, and incentives limits the effectiveness of investments.</p> <p>Do not focus only on emissions: Mobility measures must also address safety, resilience, and liveability; car electrification alone does not solve congestion, road danger, or space consumption.</p> <p>Avoid short-termism: Quick wins are valuable, but failing to embed them in a long-term strategy (SUMP, Climate Action Plan) risks policy reversal with political change.</p>
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● **POLICY FRAMEWORK**

Relevant Policies
<p>International level</p> <p><i>European Green Deal – roadmap for climate-neutrality by 2050, requiring deep transport decarbonisation.</i></p> <p><i>2030 Agenda & SDGs – particularly SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) and SDG 13 (Climate Action).</i></p> <p><i>Paris Agreement & COP climate goals – binding international framework to reduce emissions and improve resilience.</i></p>

New European Bauhaus – urban design and mobility integration for sustainable, inclusive, and aesthetic spaces.

UN-Habitat’s New Urban Agenda – sustainable mobility as a pillar of inclusive urban growth.

Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy – supports city-level commitments to sustainable mobility.

Resilient Cities Network & Just Transition Framework – ensure decarbonisation and accessibility measures do not leave vulnerable groups behind.

European level

EU Urban Mobility Framework (COM/2021/811) – guidance for SUMPs, multimodal planning, and zero-emission mobility.

Sustainable & Smart Mobility Strategy (COM/2020/789) – roadmap to achieve a 90% reduction in transport emissions by 2050.

Fit for 55 Package – binding EU target of -55% GHG emissions by 2030, including extension of ETS to transport.

Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR, 2023/1804) – mandates charging infrastructure across Europe.

EU Climate Adaptation Strategy – integrates mobility resilience into adaptation planning.

REPowerEU (2022) – accelerates electrification of transport and deployment of charging infrastructure.

Digital Europe Programme – supports ITS, MaaS platforms, and digital twins for transport systems.

EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 – encourages integration of green corridors with mobility planning.

National level (Spain)

Plan Nacional Integrado de Energía y Clima (PNIEC) 2023–2030 – includes transport sector decarbonisation measures (42% renewable energy, modal shift, fleet electrification).

Estrategia de Movilidad Segura, Sostenible y Conectada 2030 (MITMA) – national mobility strategy prioritising safety, sustainability, and digitalisation.

Ley de Cambio Climático y Transición Energética (2021) – mandates low-emission zones in municipalities >50,000 inhabitants.

National Strategy for Cycling (2021) – supports safe cycling networks across Spain.

NextGenerationEU Recovery Funds – financial support for fleet electrification, cycling infrastructure, and SUMP implementation.

Local level

Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans (SECAPs / PACES) – city-level climate and energy roadmaps including mobility measures.

Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP) – binding tool for integrated mobility planning.

Local Climate Action Plans – combine mobility with adaptation and resilience goals.

Agenda Urbana Española (Spanish Urban Agenda) – integrated approach linking mobility, housing, and regeneration.

Green Infrastructure & Renaturalisation Strategies – integrate cycling/walking corridors with urban greening.

Smart City Action Plans & Open Data Strategies – ensure ITS platforms and MaaS integration for citizens.

● **STAKEHOLDER ROLES AND ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK**

Stakeholder	Role	Type of Collaboration
Municipality / City Council	Lead authority for planning and implementation. Defines SUMP, establishes regulations (e.g., LEZs), reallocates road space, and co-finances infrastructure.	Regulatory / Governance / Financial
Regional & National Governments	Regional & National Governments	Regional & National Governments
Public Transport Authorities & Operators	Manage public transport services, electrify fleets, ensure integration with active and shared mobility.	Operational / Technical
DSOs & Utilities	Provide electrical grid reinforcement, enable charging infrastructure, and integrate with renewable energy sources.	Technical / Infrastructure
Private Mobility Operators	Deploy and operate shared mobility systems (bike sharing, e-scooters, car sharing). Share data with municipalities under agreed standards (GBFS/MDS).	Deploy and operate shared mobility systems (bike sharing, e-scooters, car sharing). Share data with municipalities under

agreed standards
(GBFS/MDS).

- MAIN REFERENCES

GOOD PRACTICES / SOME EXAMPLES

Project

Project name: CIVITAS Initiative (EU)

Location: Over 80 European cities (e.g., Ljubljana, Ghent, Stockholm)

Description: CIVITAS supports cities in testing and implementing integrated sustainable mobility solutions such as clean public transport, low-emission zones, cycling networks, and MaaS platforms. Ljubljana (Slovenia) achieved a 20% modal share increase for cycling and walking since adopting its SUMP.

Link: <https://civitas.eu/>

Project name: Barcelona Superblocks (Superilles)

Location: Barcelona, Spain

Description: The Superblocks programme reorganises city streets to prioritise pedestrians, cycling, and public space. Vehicle traffic is restricted inside designated blocks, reducing NO₂ pollution by 25% and increasing green space. The initiative is recognised as a best practice for combining mobility and liveability improvements.

Link: <https://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/superilles/en>

Web-site

Website: ELTIS – The Urban Mobility Observatory

Link: <https://www.eltis.org/>

Description: ELTIS is the European Commission’s knowledge hub for sustainable urban mobility. It provides case studies, guidelines, data, and policy resources, including the official SUMP Guidelines used across Europe.

Website: European Commission – Urban Mobility Framework

Link: https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/clean-transport-urban-transport/urban-mobility_en

Description: Official EC page explaining EU strategies, funding programmes, and legislative frameworks for sustainable mobility and SUMPs.

Paper

- **The climate change mitigation effects of daily active travel in cities**
 - **Authors:** Christian Brand, Evi Dons, Esther Anaya-Boig, Ione Avila-Palencia, Anna Clark
 - **Journal:** Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment (April 2021)
 - **DOI:** 10.1016/j.trd.2021.102305
 - **Summary:** A longitudinal panel study across seven European cities found that replacing one car trip per day with active travel (walking or cycling) for 200 days annually cuts

individual mobility-related lifecycle CO₂ emissions by ~0.5 tonnes/year—an exceptionally high impact potential.

- **‘Effect of pop-up bike lanes on cycling in European cities’**
 - **Authors:** Sebastian Kraus & Nicolas Koch
 - **Platform:** arXiv (August 2020 preprint)
 - **Summary:** Analysis across 106 European cities showed that each kilometre of provisional pop-up bike lane increased cycling by 0.6%. If such infrastructure becomes long-lasting, the estimated **health benefits** could reach roughly **\$2.3 billion per year** across Europe. ([arXiv](#), [WIRED](#))
- **‘Modelling cities’ pathways to zero-emission urban mobility...’**
 - **Authors:** Stefano Borgato, Francesca Fermi & Francesco Chirico
 - **Publication:** Transport Transitions conference paper, Lecture Notes in Mobility (May 2025)
 - **Summary:** Explores simulated scenarios across five European metro regions (Brussels, Madrid, Manchester, Milan, Warsaw), showing how strategic combinations of active mobility, public transport, and electrification could lead toward **zero-emission urban mobility by 2030**. ([SpringerLink](#))
- **Promoting Sustainable Transport: A Systematic Review of Walking and Cycling**
 - **Authors:** Multiple (MDPI journal)
 - **Journal:** Future Transportation, 2025, 5(3), 79
 - **DOI:** 10.3390/futuretransp5030079
 - **Summary:** Analyses 56 studies globally through the COM-B behavioural framework, highlighting that sustainable active mobility requires a blend of **infrastructure, policy, behavioral interventions, and digital tools** to succeed. ([mdpi.com](#))

Factsheet 6.- Technical: District heating and Cooling Networks (CAR)

LOW CARBON DISTRICTS	District Heating and Cooling Networks
DESCRIPTION	
Technical description	
<p><i>District heating is a centralised heating system that distributes hot water or steam from a generation plant to several buildings—residential, commercial, or institutional—through thermally insulated pipes.</i></p> <p>Main advantages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Energy efficiency: Better than individual systems.</i> ● <i>Space saving: No need for individual boilers.</i> ● <i>Sustainability: Allows the use of renewable sources and waste heat.</i> ● <i>Emissions reduction: Helps fight climate change.</i> <p><i>The system works through a central plant where heat is produced from different sources such as gas, biofuels, solar thermal panels, geothermal energy, or waste. This heat is transported as hot water or steam to the buildings, where it is transferred to the internal system through plate heat exchangers. The water cools down and returns to the plant to be reheated, repeating the cycle.</i></p> <p><i>Example: In Tibet, a solar system with seasonal thermal storage (a large pit) was analysed, able to cover 75% of the annual heating demand. Even though the initial investment is high (70% just for the pit), the operating costs are low, and the system is ideal for cold and sunny climates.</i></p>	

Figure 2: Schematic representation of how a fifth-generation district heating system (5GDHC) works, where the network is balanced thermally over the year through warm and cold return flows. Extra heat or cooling is covered with renewable sources.
Source: Wikipedia / Laura Toffetti.

A well-designed District Heating adapts to user demand. The more precise the control of supply (supply and return temperatures, flow rates), the higher the efficiency and the lower the cost. Its efficiency is calculated based on factors like system performance, energy cost, or individual control options, although many articles say the only factor should be urban density. **A KEY INDICATOR: PA-LCOH** (Predicted Allowable Levelized Cost of Heat) helps evaluate whether a DH network is more profitable than individual heating.

CLASSIFICATION: GENERATIONS OF DISTRICT HEATING.

The technological evolution of these systems is divided into generations:

1st Generation (1880–1930)

High-temperature steam, coal use.
Low efficiency and reliability.

2nd Generation (1930–1970)

Steam replaced by pressurised hot water (>100 °C).
Fossil fuels (coal, oil), heavy systems.

3rd Generation (from 1970)

Underground pre-insulated pipes.
Lower temperatures (<100 °C).
Use of renewables (biomass, geothermal, solar)

4th Generation (currently in development)

Low temperatures (≤70 °C).
Integration with renewable energy, thermal storage, smart control

5th Generation (5GDHC or cold DH)

Temperatures close to ground level (10–25 °C).

Each building uses heat pumps for heating or cooling.

Allows heat exchange between buildings

Example: The Mijnwater system (Netherlands) uses water from abandoned mines as a heat source.

Figure 3: A circular representation of a 5GDHC system. The network is balanced over the year, with warm return flows from cooling supply and cold return flows from heating supply covering as much of the demand as possible. Any residual heat or cold demand is supplied

THE ROLE OF DISTRICT HEATING IN THE ENERGY TRANSITION

According to studies on 100% renewable energy systems:

- **Sector integration:** DH must coordinate with electricity, hydrogen, and other sectors.
- **Operational flexibility:** Ability to absorb renewable surpluses using heat pumps or electric boilers.
- **Progressive decarbonisation:**
 - o Replacement of oil/gas with clean sources.
 - o Inclusion of industrial heat, solar thermal, and geothermal.
- **National optimisation:** Viable even in areas with lower urban density if total savings are considered (emissions, costs, biomass).
- **Reducing heat demand:** Through passive design, energy renovation, and efficient appliances.
- **Territorial planning:** Use of GIS models to prioritise areas near heat sources.
- **Modularity and decentralisation:**

- *Reversible and scalable networks.*
- *Buildings as thermal prosumers.*
- *Thermo-neutral network allowing efficient exchanges through local heat pumps.*

A key example of efficient district heating electrification is found in Norway, where ambitious measures have been applied such as improving building energy efficiency, installing DH in urban areas, and using heat pumps in rural areas. These actions have led to a 26% reduction in total electricity use for heating and a 35–40% drop in peak electricity demand, avoiding overloads in the grid. In addition, DH usage has increased significantly without raising costs or emissions. A key part of this strategy has been the inclusion of seasonal thermal storage (TES) and electric boilers, used during hours with lower energy prices to increase system flexibility.

WASTE HEAT RECOVERY:

Using waste heat is a key strategy in district heating systems. It allows recovery of heat energy that would otherwise be lost. This heat can come from industrial processes, incineration plants, data centres, or even sewage, by using technology that extracts heat from wastewater.

This kind of recovery brings many benefits: improves overall energy efficiency, reduces the need for primary energy sources, and benefits local communities by using available heat sources nearby.

DISTRICT HEATING BENEFITS:

District heating is seen as a practical and efficient way to provide heating to buildings. Instead of separate heating units being installed in every building, heat is supplied from a single central system. In this way, energy can be saved and pollution can be reduced, especially when modern air-cleaning systems are used. Fuel costs are usually lowered because energy is bought in large quantities.

Clean energy sources; such as solar power, geothermal heat, or waste heat from factories; can also be added more easily, which helps ensure a stable and less polluting system. If extra heat is produced, it does not have to be wasted. This surplus can be turned into cooling during warmer periods, so energy is used more efficiently throughout the year.

SCORING

Technical Scoring

High complexity: Needs careful design, GIS mapping, hydraulic calculations, and coordination with buildings' internal systems. Use of smart meters and balancing valves adds sophistication. 5GDHC adds more layers with bidirectional flows and decentralised heat pumps.

Finance Scoring

Investment can be very high, especially for infrastructure and storage. For example, in Tibet example, the storage pit cost 70% of the total. However, once built, operating costs are low. Funding may come from recovery plans or public-private models.

Environment Scoring

District heating cuts emissions significantly by replacing fossil boilers and using clean heat. It avoids local air pollution and allows renewable integration. Seasonal storage and smart control help avoid energy waste.

Social Scoring

Well-accepted if users understand the savings and comfort. Construction can cause disruption. Benefits include comfort, stable costs, and green image.

CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

Recurrent risks

22. *Technical challenges:*

22.1. *Legacy heating systems, insufficient insulation, or poorly balanced networks can reduce efficiency.*

22.2. *Careful assessment of building stock is essential.*

23. *Economic barriers:*

23.1. *High installation costs and return-on-investment uncertainty are common, especially in the absence of public support or guaranteed user demand.*

24. *Social and regulatory hurdles:*

24.1. *People may be resistant to change due to aesthetic or control concerns.*

24.2. *Planning delays can arise from local regulations or community objections.*

25. *Urban fit:*

25.1. *District heating is most effective in dense urban environments or zones with grouped demand. It's particularly useful in cities facing pollution, energy insecurity or limited space for individual systems.*

● **TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE**

Phases of implementation	
P1	Planning and Feasibility
Identify zones with high heat demand and local renewable sources. Use tools like GIS	
P1.1	Demand mapping: Identify areas with high thermal needs using GIS and urban density
P1.2	Sources identification Check local renewable or residual heat sources
P1.3	Cost-benefit analysis Use a methodology to assess if district heating is more viable than individual systems
P2	Design and Authorisation
Define the system's layout and temperature levels. Prepare legal documents and secure permits for the installation	

P2.1	Technical district heating design Define supply temperature, flow rates, insulation levels, and pumping requirements
P2.2	Legal and permit process Secure approvals for construction and energy regulations
P3	Installation and Start-up Build the network and energy centre. Test all components before starting regular operation
P3.1	Construction of network Lay insulated underground pipes and build the energy centre
P3.2	Commissioning and testing Check pressure, flow, and connection points before supply begins
P4	Monitoring and Maintenance Use digital tools to monitor system performance. Carry out regular checks and preventative maintenance
P4.1	Smart controls Install monitoring systems to optimise flow and temperature
P4.2	Regular upkeep Inspect pumps, heat exchangers, and insulation.

● GANTT

● STRATEGIC

RECOMMENDATIONS	
DOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use GIS to identify viable urban zones Combine with energy renovation plans Apply investment plan to implement Prioritise neighbourhoods near renewable or residual heat sources
DON'Ts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Avoid low-density areas unless thermal demand is very high Don't overdesign pipe networks, optimise sizing Don't rely only on one source, flexibility increases resilience Avoid ignoring user concerns or delays in connections

Offer user incentives and transparent tariffs

● **CROSS-LINK MATRIX BETWEEN TECHNICAL ACTIONS**

Main Topic ↓ Related →	ENERGY GENERATION	DISTRIBUTION NETWORKS	HEAT EXCHANGE
ENERGY GENERATION		C Complementary <i>Heat source must match temperature and flow specs of network design</i>	C Complementary <i>The temperature and pressure from the energy source determine the type and size of heat exchangers needed</i>
DISTRIBUTION NETWORKS	C Complementary <i>Design must adapt to the type and capacity of the source</i>		S Synergy <i>Pipe flow and return temperatures affect exchanger performance directly</i>
HEAT EXCHANGE	C Complementary <i>Irregular heat or flow reduces system efficiency at building level</i>	S Synergy <i>Good insulation and pressure management in the network improve exchanger results</i>	

● **POLICY FRAMEWORK**

Relevant Policies
International level
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Paris Agreement ● UN SDGs (Goal 7, 11, 13) ● Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy
European level
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EU Green Deal ● Fit for 55 Package ● Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) ● Renovation Wave ● REPowerEU ● Energy Efficiency Directive (EED, revised, Directive (UE) 2023/1791) ● Renewable Energy Directive (RED, revised, Directive (UE) 2023/2413) ● Heating & Cooling Directive ● EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) ● Clean Industrial Deal (en desarrollo) ● LIFE Programme (financiación, cooperación)
National level

- *NECPs (National Energy and Climate Plans)*
- *Recovery and Resilience Funds*
- *National heat strategies*
- *National regulations on district heating*
- *Long-term Strategies (LTS) for 2050*

Local level

- *SECAPs (Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans)*
- *Local Urban Regeneration Plans*
- *Smart City strategies*
- *Local heating and cooling plans*
- *Climate City Contracts*
- *Urban Agenda for the EU (en cooperación)*

● **STAKEHOLDER ROLES AND ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK**

Stakeholder	Role	Type of Collaboration
MUNICIPALITY	Regulation, co-financing, project lead	Regulatory / Financial
ENERGY OPERATORS	Design the system, build infrastructure, and manage day-to-day operation	Technical / Financial
BUILDING OWNERS	Decide whether to connect, co-finance installation, and ensure access to buildings	Operational / Financial
CITIZENS / RESIDENTS	Use the system, give feedback, and influence social acceptance	Social / Behavioural
TECHNICAL ADVISORS	Support with energy studies, feasibility analysis and system optimisation	Advisory / Expert
CONTRACTORS	Carry out construction works: pipes, trenches and energy centre	Technical / On-site Execution

● **MAIN REFERENCES**

GOOD PRACTICES / SOME EXAMPLES

Project

Project name: MIJNWATER

Location: Heerlen, Netherlands

Description: The Mijnwater system in Heerlen reuses geothermal energy from flooded coal mines to supply a low-temperature district heating and cooling network. It operates with a fifth-generation energy concept that allows energy exchange between buildings and integrates renewable sources.

Link: <https://mijnwater.eu/>

Project name: MAKING-CITY

Location: Groningen (Netherlands) and Oulu (Finland) – Lighthouse Cities

Description: MAKING-CITY is a Horizon 2020 project focused on the large-scale deployment of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs) as a pathway toward urban decarbonisation. it explores innovative

energy system solutions, including the integration of renewable-based district heating and cooling networks, smart energy management, and local energy communities.

Link: <https://www.makingcity.eu/>

Project name: THUNDER

Location: EU collaborative project

Description: THUNDER aims to overcome key barriers to waste heat recovery in data centres by developing innovative and cost-effective seasonal thermal energy storage (STES) using thermochemical materials. These systems are designed to integrate into district heating networks, enabling higher energy efficiency, better use of residual heat, and significant carbon emission reductions across urban areas.

Link: <https://www.thunderproject.eu/>

Project name: SCO2OP-TES

Location: Europe

Description: This project develops innovative electricity storage systems based on thermal energy conversion (Thermal Energy Storage - TES). While focused on electricity, the technology has potential applications in flexible energy systems that could support or complement district heating strategies.

Link: <https://www.sco2op-tes.org/>

Web-site

Website: Veolia – District Heating Services

Link: <https://www.veolia.co.uk/services/district-heating>

Description: Information on Veolia's district heating services, including design, operation, and environmental benefits.

Website: Alfa Laval – District Heating: ¿qué es y cómo funciona?

Link: <https://www.alfalaval.es/industrias/hvac/district-heating/district-heating-que-es-y-como-funciona/>

Description: Basic explanation of how district heating works and the role of heat exchangers.

Paper

Paper title: *Investigating the sensitivity of input parameters on the predicted allowable heat generation costs for district heating supply*

Authors: Wang, G., Zhao, Y., Sun, M., et al.

Journal: Energy Reports

DOI or link: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2025.01.079>

Paper title: *District heating in clean energy systems*

Authors: Lund, H., Werner, S., Thorsen, J.E., et al.

Journal: Nature Cities

DOI or link: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s44359-025-00076-8>

Paper title: *Techno-economic performance and optimization of a large solar district heating system with pit storage under Tibetan Plateau climate conditions*

Authors: Zhang, Y., Wang, K., Li, J., et al.

Journal: Energy

DOI or link: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2025.134449>

Paper title: Reducing electricity demand and enhancing heat supply flexibility through energy efficiency and district heating

Authors: Tomasgard, A., Korpås, M., Hellemo, L., et al.

Journal: Energy

DOI or link: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2025.135310>

Paper title: A data-based comparison of methods for reducing the peak flow rate in a district heating system

Authors: Persson, J., Bøhm, B., Olsen, P.K., et al.

Journal: Smart Energy

DOI or link: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segy.2024.100168>

Paper title: Conversion to Fourth-Generation District Heating (4GDH): Heat Accumulation Within Building Envelopes

Authors: Zvingilaite, E., Sorknæs, P., Münster, M., et al.

Journal: Energies

DOI or link: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en18092307>

Paper title: Towards sustainable urban energy solutions: A multi-dimensional assessment framework for fifth-generation district heating and cooling systems

Authors: Buffa, S., Lollini, R., Fracastoro, G., et al.

Journal: Energy and Buildings

DOI or link: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.115071>

● KEY CONSIDERATIONS

Additional Notes

- Focus District Heating in dense, mixed-use zones for efficiency and use low-temperature networks when possible to cut losses
- Integrate local renewables or waste heat to improve sustainability, prioritised seasonal thermal storage in cold climates
- Use passive design and energy-efficient appliances to reduce demand
- Inform users clearly to reduce resistance and ensure connections

Factsheet 7.- Environmental: Urban Green Infrastructure (DEMIR)

SUSTAINABLE LIFESTYLES	URBAN GREEN INFRASTRUCTURE
DESCRIPTION	
Technical description	
<p>Urban Green Infrastructure (UGI) refers to a strategically planned network of natural and semi-natural spaces—such as parks, green roofs, community gardens, and reforested areas—designed to deliver multiple ecosystem services in urban settings. UGI aims to improve environmental quality, promote biodiversity, and enhance residents’ well-being.²</p> <p>Unlike isolated green spaces, UGI is designed to work as a coherent, connected system, embedding nature into the urban fabric and offering multifunctional benefits to cities and their residents. UGI interventions are most effective when they are inclusive, context-specific, and integrated into local planning. Key to their success is collaboration among public authorities, technical experts, private developers, and communities.</p> <p>It integrates green and blue elements (e.g. vegetation and water bodies) in the built environment to regulate climate, manage stormwater and provide social and health benefits. The implementation of UGI is particularly relevant in the context of climate adaptation, energy efficiency and sustainable urban planning.</p> <p>Key actions in UGI typically include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Urban Green Areas: Urban green areas are the most visible components of UGI and can take many forms; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <u>Green Roofs:</u> Vegetated layers installed on rooftops that reduce urban heat, absorb rainfall, and improve insulation. ○ <u>Community Gardens:</u> Shared plots cultivated by residents for food, education, and leisure, improving food security and social cohesion. ○ <u>Urban Reforestation:</u> Planting trees in degraded or underutilized urban land to enhance biodiversity, air quality, and carbon sequestration. ● Urban Ecosystem: UGI is not just about planting green elements — it's about creating functional urban ecosystems that deliver multiple benefits. Successful UGI requires integrating green infrastructure with urban water systems, biodiversity goals, and social inclusion strategies. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <u>Water:</u> Many UGI elements help manage stormwater by increasing permeability and reducing runoff. Examples include bioswales, rain gardens, and green roofs. ○ <u>Biodiversity:</u> UGI can restore habitat corridors in cities, supporting pollinators, birds, and small mammals. Urban forests and native planting schemes enhance local biodiversity. ○ <u>People:</u> UGI improves health by reducing air pollution, providing recreation, and mitigating heat islands. It also promotes social equity when designed inclusively. 	

² World Green Infrastructure Network. (2021, April 12). *Key Definition: Green Infrastructure*. World Green Infrastructure Network. <https://worldgreeninfrastructurenetwork.org/key-definition-green-infrastructure/>

UGI is increasingly recognized as a nature-based solution (NbS) for enhancing urban resilience. Through elements such as permeable surfaces—including rain gardens, bioswales, and green paving—UGI significantly contributes to flood risk reduction by allowing natural infiltration of rainwater, decreasing surface runoff, and easing pressure on urban drainage systems. Simultaneously, vegetated infrastructure (like green roofs, urban forests, and tree-lined streets) helps to reduce the urban heat island (UHI) effect by providing shade and facilitating evapotranspiration, which cools surrounding air and improves thermal comfort in dense urban areas. Moreover, UGI solutions actively contribute to climate mitigation through CO₂ capture and storage, with trees and vegetation sequestering carbon and improving air quality, thus supporting local and global climate goals.

Implementation Considerations:

Green Roofs: Successful implementation begins with careful **site selection**, focusing on flat or gently sloped rooftops (typically less than 30°) that possess sufficient load-bearing capacity. The design must include multiple components such as a waterproofing membrane, root barrier, drainage layer, growing medium, and appropriate vegetation—often sedum, grasses, or low-maintenance shrubs. There are two main types: *extensive* green roofs, which are lighter and suitable for retrofitting existing buildings, and *intensive* systems, which are heavier and support more complex vegetation but require stronger structural support, often found in new constructions. Implementation must comply with local building regulations and typically requires structural analysis, drainage planning, and permit approvals. Maintenance involves periodic inspections, irrigation (particularly during the establishment phase), and plant replacement as necessary.

Community Gardens: Their success depends on selecting well-lit, accessible locations with clean soil; where contamination risks exist, raised beds with imported soil should be used. Key infrastructure includes fencing, composting areas, irrigation systems, accessible pathways, and seating. Early and continuous community engagement is essential to promote a sense of ownership and ensure long-term stewardship. Institutional arrangements—such as land-use agreements and liability definitions—should be clarified with municipalities or housing authorities. These gardens provide substantial social benefits, including enhanced community cohesion, improved mental health, and access to fresh produce, especially in disadvantaged neighborhoods.

Urban Reforestation: Implementation must start with species selection, prioritizing native or climate-resilient trees that require minimal care while supporting urban wildlife. Design considerations include planting density, root space, safety (e.g., visibility for pedestrians), and integration with urban infrastructure. Technical needs often involve soil remediation, especially on formerly industrial or compacted land, and planning for long-term irrigation, protection from vandalism, and growth monitoring. Reforestation efforts should aim to connect with existing ecological networks such as green corridors, pollinator pathways, and nearby wetlands to maximize their ecological value and resilience.

Cook, L. M., Good, K. D., Moretti, M., Kremer, P., Wadzuk, B., Traver, R., & Smith, V. (2024). Towards the intentional multifunctionality of urban green infrastructure: a paradox of choice? *NPJ Urban Sustainability*, 4(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42949-024-00145-0>

SCORING

Technical Scoring

The technical difficulty of implementing UGI varies depending on the type of intervention (e.g., green roofs, community gardens, urban reforestation), site conditions, and integration requirements with existing infrastructure. While community gardens are relatively simple to establish, actions like green roofs and urban reforestation require specialized expertise, such as structural assessments, landscape design, and integration with drainage or utility systems. Successful implementation demands coordination among multiple professionals—engineers, architects, ecologists—as well as alignment with local regulations and existing urban infrastructure. Although not as technically demanding as energy systems, UGI still requires thoughtful planning to ensure long-term functionality, especially in dense or older urban environments.

Finance Scoring

Initial investment costs can be significant, especially for green roofs, which require structural modifications, waterproofing, and specialized materials. Community gardens and urban reforestation generally have lower initial costs but may still require funding for site preparation, irrigation systems, and planting. Operational and maintenance costs, including watering, pruning, and inspections, contribute to long-term budget needs and can be substantial if not planned carefully. Many UGI projects rely on a combination of municipal budgets, grants, and external funding sources to cover these expenses. While affordable compared to large infrastructure projects, securing sustained funding and integrating UGI maintenance into existing urban management plans remain key challenges.

Environment Scoring

Urban Green Infrastructure (UGI) scores high for environmental impact due to its substantial benefits in reducing urban heat islands, improving air quality and enhancing biodiversity. UGI interventions like green roofs, community gardens, and urban reforestation contribute to carbon sequestration and reduce stormwater runoff, thus lowering emissions related to urban flooding and water treatment. By promoting ecosystem services and supporting urban sustainability goals—such as climate adaptation, biodiversity conservation, and improved livability—UGI stands out as a highly positive environmental solution.

Social Scoring

Community gardens and accessible green areas are generally well embraced by residents, promoting social cohesion and environmental awareness. However, adoption ease can vary depending on local awareness, cultural values, and the visibility of benefits, with some technical interventions like green roofs requiring more outreach to gain public support. When residents are involved in planning and taking care of these spaces, the projects work better and are accepted more easily.

CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

Recurrent risks

Recurrent risks and challenges during the implementation of Urban Green Infrastructure (UGI) include technical difficulties such as ensuring structural stability for green roofs or proper soil conditions for planting.

Budget limitations can delay or reduce the scale of projects, while ongoing maintenance costs may be underestimated. Resistance from residents or end-users may arise due to lack of awareness or concerns about changes to their environment.

Legal restrictions, including zoning laws, building codes, or land ownership issues, can also pose barriers.

- **TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE**

Phases of implementation	
P1	Planning & Feasibility
Identifying local needs, assessing site conditions, and engaging stakeholders to determine the potential for UGI interventions.	
P1.1	Assessment Identify local environmental, social, and spatial needs that UGI interventions can address.
P1.2	Site Selection Evaluate and select appropriate sites based on land availability, ownership, and suitability.
P1.3	Preliminary Technical Assessment Assess structural, environmental, and legal conditions to determine feasibility.
P2	Design and Preparation
Developing detailed plans and securing approvals to prepare the site and resources for implementation.	
P2.1	Concept Development Define the design vision, objectives and suitable UGI components.
P2.2	Technical Detailing and Costing Prepare technical drawings, material specifications, and cost estimates.
P2.3	Permitting and Procurement Obtain required permits and initiate procurement of contractors and materials.

P3	Construction and Installation
Carrying out the physical implementation of the UGI measures on-site.	
P3.1	Installation of UGI Components Execute the construction of green roofs, gardens, planting areas, or reforestation.
P3.2	Quality Control Monitor construction and materials to ensure compliance with design standards.
P4	Long-Term Maintenance and Evaluation
Maintaining performance over time and fostering community engagement for sustainability.	
P4.1	Routine Maintenance Conduct regular maintenance including cleaning, repairs and weeding.
P4.2	Performance Evaluation Measure environmental and social impacts over time.

● GANTT

		M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
P1	Planning & Feasibility												
	P.1.1 Assessment												
	P.1.2 Site Selection												
	P.1.3 Preliminary Technical Assessment												
P2	Design and Preparation												
	P.2.1 Concept Development												
	P.2.2 Technical Deatiling and Costing												
	P.2.3 Permitting and Procurement												
P3	Construction and Installation												
	P.3.1 Installation of UGI Components												
	P.3.2 Quality Control												
P4	Long-Term Maintenance and Evaluation												
	P.4.1 Routine Maintenance												
	P.4.2 Performance Evaluation												

● STRATEGIC

RECOMMENDATIONS	
DOs	<p>Integrate Urban Green Infrastructure into urban planning early.</p> <p>Select native and climate-resilient plant species.</p> <p>Engage communities from the planning phase.</p> <p>Conduct thorough site and stakeholder assessments.</p> <p>Plan for maintenance from the beginning.</p>
DON'Ts	<p>Don't treat Urban Green Infrastructure as a decorative afterthought.</p> <p>Don't rely solely on short-term funding.</p> <p>Don't neglect structural assessments for green roofs.</p> <p>Don't use non-permeable materials around UGI.</p> <p>Don't underestimate the need for trained maintenance.</p>

Monitor performance and adapt over time.	Don't neglect accessibility and equity.
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● **CROSS-LINK MATRIX BETWEEN TECHNICAL ACTIONS**

Main Topic ↓ Related →	Planning & Feasibility	Design & Preparation	Construction & Installation	Maintenance & Evaluation
Planning & Feasibility		S Good planning informs design quality	C Coordination needed to ensure constructability is considered early.	R Maintenance depends on early planning choices
Design & Preparation			S Technical designs directly guide construction activities	
Construction & Installation				S Construction quality directly affects durability and maintenance outcomes.
Maintenance & Evaluation		C Design influences ease and cost of long-term maintenance.		

● **POLICY FRAMEWORK**

Relevant Policies
<p>International level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (United Nations): Especially supports SDG 11- Sustainable Cities and Communities, SDG 13- Climate Action, SDG 15- Life on Land. ● Paris Agreement: Encourages nature-based solutions and green infrastructure to reduce emissions and build climate resilience. ● Resilient Cities Network: Encourages urban resilience through strategies like UGI to address climate, environmental, and social shocks.
<p>European level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● European Green Deal: Aims to make the EU climate-neutral by 2050 with strong support for urban sustainability and biodiversity. ● EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030: Promotes green infrastructure and ecosystem restoration in urban and rural areas. ● New European Bauhaus: Encourages projects that are sustainable, inclusive, and aesthetically integrated—UGI fits well within this vision.
<p>National level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs): Often include nature-based solutions and green infrastructure as part of strategies to reduce emissions and adapt to climate impacts.

- Smart City Strategies: Incorporate UGI to improve urban livability, digital monitoring of green areas, and the combination of green and smart solutions.
- Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP): Connect green corridors with walkability, cycling, and low-emission zones, integrating mobility with greenery.

Local level

- Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP): Integrate climate adaptation and mitigation measures using nature-based solutions such as green roofs, parks, and reforestation.
- Renaturalisation or Green Infrastructure Strategies: Focus on restoring ecosystems, daylighting urban rivers, and increasing green coverage to reduce urban heat and flood risk.

● **STAKEHOLDER ROLES AND ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK**

Stakeholder	Role	Type of Collaboration
Municipal Authorities	Lead planning and policy alignment; facilitate permits; allocate public land for UGI.	Regulatory
Urban Planning Departments	Integrate UGI into master plans	Technical
Public Housing Authorities	Enable UGI integration into renovation and housing development projects	Facilitator
Academic and Research Institutions	Support research, monitoring, and public education on ecosystem benefits.	Knowledge Provider
Local communities & Residents	Participate in co-design and long-term care of community green spaces.	Participatory role

● **MAIN REFERENCES**

GOOD PRACTICES / SOME EXAMPLES	
Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Urban GreenUP: Project implemented nature-based solutions in cities to improve climate resilience and urban sustainability. It directly contributes to Urban Green Infrastructure (UGI) by integrating green spaces like green walls, urban forests, and sustainable drainage systems into city planning. 	
Web-site	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● European Commission (2013). Building a Green Infrastructure for Europe. https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/ecosystems/docs/green_infrastructure_broc.pdf ● European Environment Agency (2021). Urban Green Infrastructure in Europe: Typologies, Environmental Effectiveness, and Policy Context. EEA Report No 31/2021. 	

<https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/urban-green-infrastructure-in-europe>

- **FAO (2020).** Guidelines on Urban and Peri-Urban Forestry.
<https://www.fao.org/documents/card/en/c/ca8603en>
- UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)
<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

Paper

- European Environment Agency (2021). “Urban green infrastructure and the role of nature-based solutions in cities.” *EEA Report No 18/2021*.
- Newton, J., Construction Industry Research And Information Association, Ecology Consultancy Ltd, Livingroofs.org, Great Britain. Department Of The Environment, Transport And The Regions. Environmental Protection Group, & Al, E. (2007). *Building greener : guidance on the use of green roofs, green walls and complementary features on buildings*. Ciria.
- Kabisch, N., et al. (2016). “Nature-based solutions to climate change mitigation and adaptation in urban areas: perspectives on indicators, knowledge gaps, barriers, and opportunities for action.” *Ecology and Society*, 21(2).

Factsheet 8.- Technical: Energy Use: Improving Behaviours (CAR)

SUSTAINABLE LIFESTYLES	ENERGY USE: IMPROVING BEHAVIOURS
DESCRIPTION	
Technical description	
<p>Energy demand in cities is shaped as much by everyday behaviour as by technology. The same building can deliver very different consumption profiles depending on how occupants heat, cool, ventilate, light spaces, and operate appliances. Behavioural measures are attractive because they deliver fast, low-cost savings and can be put in place while deeper retrofits or infrastructure investments are planned. Framing behaviour through a degrowth lens strengthens this potential: the aim is not only to use energy more efficiently but also to reduce absolute demand to a level that is compatible with ecological limits and social equity. Degrowth emphasises sufficiency, care, and shared use over maximising throughput. In practice this means normalising moderate comfort ranges, reducing unnecessary services, sharing equipment where possible, and designing routines that make low-energy choices the default.</p> <p>Objectives</p> <p>The action has four practical goals. First, to achieve measurable reductions in electricity, heating, and cooling through visible feedback, better defaults, and simple operational changes. Second, to embed sufficiency in daily routines so that savings last beyond the first campaign cycle and do not depend on constant incentives. Third, to support grid stability by shifting flexible loads away from peak periods and toward times when renewable generation is abundant. Fourth, to improve fairness by helping households and public facilities cut bills without expensive investments, while protecting comfort and health.</p> <p>Behavioural interventions combine information technologies with social design. Smart meters, sub-metering, in-home displays, web dashboards, and mobile apps provide near real-time feedback on consumption. When feedback is specific, timely, and paired with concrete actions—like adjusting thermostat setpoints, scheduling appliances, or eliminating standby loads—it reliably changes behaviour. Social comparison and goal-setting add a second layer: when people see how their household or facility performs against similar peers and receive tailored suggestions, adoption improves. Campaigns in schools, social housing, and municipal buildings serve as living labs that generate evidence, stories, and local champions. From a management standpoint, it is important to integrate these efforts into an energy-management system so that monitoring, review, and improvement become routine rather than one-off. ISO 50001 and EN 16247 provide a simple skeleton for doing this: define scope and baselines, set objectives and indicators, teach people how to meet them, verify results, and correct course.</p>	

Degrowth turns efficiency into sufficiency. Instead of treating the built environment as a machine to be optimised for ever greater output, it asks what level of service is enough for health and wellbeing and designs for that. In buildings this translates into comfort guidelines that are reasonable rather than extravagant, such as winter heating setpoints around the low twenties and summer cooling setpoints in the mid-twenties, combined with ventilation and shading practices that protect indoor air quality and thermal comfort without over-reliance on mechanical systems. It encourages shared use of rarely used appliances, repair over replacement, and slower replacement cycles that favour durability. In mobility, it prioritises active modes and public transport over discretionary car travel. The result is a structural reduction in demand that does not depend on constant technological upgrades.

Jevons paradox describes a situation where improving the efficiency of using a resource lowers its effective cost and, paradoxically, increases total consumption as people find new or expanded uses for it. Rebound effects are the practical expressions of this dynamic. After installing efficient lighting, occupants may leave lights on for longer because the penalty feels small. After upgrading to a more efficient boiler, households may increase the number of heated rooms or extend the heating season. Even when direct consumption falls, savings can be spent on other energy-intensive activities, a form of indirect rebound. Recognising this risk is essential. The answer is not to avoid efficiency, but to pair it with sufficiency and clear rules so that the gains are locked in. Behaviour programmes should set and communicate sensible comfort norms, use automation to enforce efficient defaults, and report not only intensity metrics but absolute totals. Where appropriate, budgets or caps can be used to prevent rebound from eroding gains.

A practical rollout starts with a baseline: metered data, bills, simple walk-throughs, and brief surveys to understand routines and pain points. Early pilots in municipal buildings, schools, and social housing demonstrate what works locally and help adjust messages and tools. Technical elements include installing or activating smart metering and sub-metering where missing, enabling user-facing dashboards, and configuring alerts for abnormal consumption. Behavioural elements include concise guidance on everyday actions, prompts at points of decision (for example, signage at thermostats and switches), and small group challenges with public recognition rather than cash rewards. Comfort and health are non-negotiable: any reduction strategy must track indoor temperatures, humidity, and ventilation to ensure safe, acceptable conditions. Where tariffs or grid signals are available, flexible loads such as water heating or EV charging can be shifted automatically to off-peak periods. Data governance matters as much as technology. Consumption data should be minimised, anonymised where possible, and shared only with consent for clearly stated purposes. Simple privacy practices—clear notices, opt-out options, and local aggregation—build trust and participation.

Success depends on measuring the right things. Track absolute energy use and intensity against a clear baseline. Separate savings from weather effects by normalising heating and cooling degree

days. Monitor peak demand, since shifting load can reduce costs and emissions even when totals change modestly. Report participation rates and persistence, because small actions performed by many people over long periods are more valuable than large but short-lived responses. Complement energy indicators with comfort and satisfaction data to keep the programme grounded in lived experience.

Behaviour is a system property, not a one-time campaign. Assign clear roles: a coordinating team that manages data, tools, and communications; facility managers or community leaders who act as local points of contact; and a simple escalation path for issues and ideas from occupants. Align the programme with renovation and mobility actions so that messages are consistent. When a building is retrofitted, use the handover as an opportunity to refresh training and reset baselines. When tariffs change, update automation rules and user prompts. Public procurement can reinforce sufficiency by specifying devices and systems that make efficient defaults easy to keep—thermostats with lockable ranges, lighting with task-based controls, appliances with low-standby designs, and user interfaces that show the energy consequence of choices.

The main technical risks are poor data quality, weak integration between meters and dashboards, and fragile automations that fail silently. These are managed by starting small, testing integrations before scaling, and keeping manual fallbacks. The main social risks are fatigue, privacy concerns, and perceived loss of comfort. These are managed by transparent communication, opt-out choices, visible benefits, and explicit protection of acceptable comfort bands. The rebound risk is managed by combining efficiency with sufficiency: set clear consumption goals, keep defaults conservative, and make progress visible at household, facility, and city levels so that saving becomes a shared accomplishment rather than a private sacrifice.

When designed and governed well, behaviour and degrowth measures deliver steady savings at minimal cost and create a culture that supports the rest of the transition. Typical programmes record mid-single- to low-double-digit reductions in energy use within the first year, with stronger gains where comfort norms and automation reinforce human intent. More importantly, they reduce the size of the technical solution required elsewhere: smaller heating and cooling plants are needed, peak loads fall, and the same renewable capacity serves more people. By centering sufficiency, they also help prevent efficiency gains from dissolving into rebound. The outcome is a city that does more with less, protects comfort and health, and stays within environmental limits by design rather than by accident.

Figura 2 “Diagram of natural resource flows (captioned ‘The Earth’s Biosphere’).” Original JPG by User:Gaeanautes (2015); English SVG vectorization and labels by Д.Ильин (2020). License: CC0 1.0 Public Domain Dedication (free to use, no attribution required—attr

Figura 3 The Environmental Kuznets Curve. Reproduced from Trincado, E.; Sánchez-Bayón, A.; Vindel, J.M., *The European Union Green Deal: Clean Energy Wellbeing Opportunities and the Risk of the Jevons Paradox*, *Energies* 14(14):4148 (2021). Licensed under CC BY 4.0 <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/14/14/4148>

Figure 4 The effect of the elasticity of demand on the rebound effect. Reproduced from Trincado, E.; Sánchez-Bayón, A.; Vindel, J.M., *The European Union Green Deal: Clean Energy Wellbeing Opportunities and the Risk of the Jevons Paradox*, *Energies* 14(14):4148 (2021). Licensed under CC BY 4.0. <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/14/14/4148>

SCORING

Technical Scoring

The technical difficulty of implementing energy behaviour programmes is assessed as medium. Unlike infrastructure-heavy measures such as deep retrofits or renewable integration, behavioural actions do not require large-scale construction or high-tech equipment. The main tools—smart meters, feedback dashboards, mobile apps, and awareness campaigns—are already widely available and technically mature.

However, the complexity arises from integration and management. Energy data platforms must be connected with existing metering infrastructure and building management systems, requiring ICT and data governance expertise. Ensuring interoperability and compliance with standards such as ISO 50001 (Energy Management Systems) and EN 16247 (Energy Audits) is essential for consistent monitoring. In addition, securing data privacy and cybersecurity adds another layer of technical challenge.

From a human-resources perspective, the action requires interdisciplinary expertise: energy engineers to interpret consumption data, behavioural scientists to design effective nudges, communication specialists to deliver campaigns, and municipal staff to coordinate

implementation. Without this cross-sector collaboration, interventions risk being ineffective or short-lived.

Therefore, while the basic technological solutions are straightforward, the success of implementation depends on institutional capacity, technical expertise, and sustained monitoring. For this reason, the technical score is positioned at a medium level of complexity: achievable by most municipalities but requiring structured support and a multi-skilled team to deliver long-term results.

Finance Scoring

The financial difficulty is assessed as low-to-medium (€–€€). Behavioural programmes require modest investment compared to large retrofits or renewable infrastructures. Main costs include installing or activating smart meters, developing user dashboards, conducting training sessions, and maintaining communication campaigns. Operational costs are relatively low and scale with the size of the population engaged.

However, the degrowth perspective highlights that true success depends not on maximising consumption of new gadgets or digital services but on prioritising sufficiency and long-term durability. This can reduce costs further by avoiding unnecessary technology rollouts and focusing resources on education, participatory workshops, and monitoring. Funding is often available through EU programmes (e.g., Horizon Europe, LIFE, or cohesion funds) and national energy-efficiency incentives. Because payback is quick—bill savings appear in the first year—external financing needs are minimal compared to infrastructure-heavy measures.

Environment Scoring

The environmental benefit is assessed as **high (♠♠♠)**. By directly reducing demand, behavioural measures cut emissions, resource use, and waste generation immediately, without requiring large material inputs. Typical reductions range between **5–15% of electricity and heating consumption** within a year, scaling to higher impacts when sufficiency and degrowth strategies are fully applied.

Degrowth reframes the objective: rather than chasing endless efficiency improvements that risk rebound effects, behaviour change is aimed at **absolute demand reduction**. This ensures that the savings are not offset by increased consumption elsewhere. The environmental impact therefore extends beyond emissions: it reduces strain on ecosystems, lowers extraction of fuels and raw materials, and contributes to long-term resilience of the energy system.

Social Scoring

The social acceptance of this measure is generally **high (😊😊😊)**. Citizens usually welcome initiatives that reduce bills, improve comfort, and involve them directly in climate solutions. Participation is enhanced when programmes are transparent, inclusive, and tailored to local

contexts. However, there may be **resistance if measures are perceived as limiting comfort or freedom**—for example, stricter thermostat settings or restrictions on certain uses.

The **degrowth framing** helps mitigate this risk by shifting the narrative: rather than sacrificing wellbeing, the goal is to **redefine prosperity** around sufficiency, shared value, and care for future generations. Social co-benefits include empowerment (citizens as active participants, not passive consumers), energy justice (support for vulnerable groups), and cultural shifts toward sustainability. When combined with community-led initiatives, behaviour-based measures become an important entry point for collective climate action.

CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

Recurrent risks

Behavioural programmes face several **implementation risks**. Technical difficulties may include problems integrating smart meters or dashboards with existing building management systems, as well as unreliable or incomplete data. Budget limitations are common when municipalities prioritise visible infrastructure over “soft measures” like awareness campaigns. Resistance from end-users can occur if measures are perceived as restrictions on comfort or lifestyle, especially when the framing is not participatory. Legal or regulatory restrictions (for example, data privacy rules under GDPR) may also limit how consumption data can be collected and used, requiring robust safeguards and transparent communication.

City Issues

Urban challenges such as **traffic congestion, lack of green areas, or poor housing quality** shape energy behaviour. In low-quality housing, for example, residents may rely on inefficient appliances or heating practices that are hard to change without structural renovation. Similarly, in cities with limited access to green spaces and active mobility options, residents may over-rely on climate control systems. Addressing behaviours therefore requires acknowledging these **urban context limitations**.

Environmental Problems

Air pollution, urban heat islands, and climate risks (such as heatwaves) directly affect how energy is used. Citizens exposed to high outdoor temperatures may increase air-conditioning use, while poor air quality discourages natural ventilation. These **environmental stressors** can undermine behavioural programmes unless combined with broader adaptation strategies, such as green infrastructure and improved building envelopes.

Management Gaps

Behavioural initiatives often suffer from **weak planning, fragmented responsibility, and low citizen involvement**. Without clear leadership, actions remain pilot projects with little continuity. Cities may lack a dedicated energy manager or institutional capacity to monitor and sustain interventions over time. Equally, if residents are not actively engaged in co-

designing measures, they are less likely to maintain new habits once incentives or campaigns end.

Obsolete Technologies

Many urban areas still depend on **outdated, energy-intensive technologies**—inefficient boilers, poor insulation, incandescent lighting, and appliances that fail to meet current EU standards. Even if behaviour improves, these obsolete technologies can **lock in high energy demand** and limit the achievable savings. For this reason, behavioural measures should be paired with gradual technology renewal and minimum efficiency standards.

● TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE

Phases of implementation	
P1	Descriptive name: Baseline Assessment & Planning
P1.1	Energy Consumption Audit: Collect baseline data through smart meters, utility bills, and surveys to identify where behaviour changes can have the largest impact (e.g., heating, lighting, standby appliances).
P1.2	Behavioural Mapping: Analyse habits and routines of different user groups (residents, public employees, schools) to identify “energy-intensive behaviours.”
P1.3	Stakeholder Engagement: Involve citizens, schools, building managers, and community groups early to ensure buy-in and define local priorities.
P2	Intervention Design and Capacity Building
P2.1	Educational Campaigns: Prepare materials and workshops to raise awareness of energy-saving practices, aligned with EU Green Deal and ISO 50001 recommendations.
P2.2	ICT Tools & Feedback Systems: Deploy smart meters, apps, or dashboards that provide real-time consumption feedback and personalised tips.
P2.3	Training Programmes: Train municipal staff, teachers, and facility managers to act as “energy ambassadors” who model and spread good practices.
P3	Implementation and Monitoring
P3.1	Pilot Implementation: Launch small-scale pilots (e.g., in schools or public buildings) to test communication strategies, feedback systems, and incentive mechanisms.
P3.2	Citywide Rollout: Expand successful approaches across households, commercial spaces, and municipal facilities
P3.3	Monitoring and KPIs: Track progress using indicators such as kWh saved per household, reduction in peak demand, and participation rates in awareness campaigns

● GANTT

		M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
P1	Descriptive name: Baseline Assessment and Planning													
P2	Intervention Design and Capacity Building													
P3	Implementing and Monitoring													

● STRATEGIC

RECOMMENDATIONS	
<p>DOs</p> <p>Integrate with city context: Link behavioural actions to broader city challenges such as housing quality, energy poverty, and climate risks. For example, pair campaigns with municipal renovation programmes or social housing upgrades to maximise fairness.</p> <p>Focus on sufficiency, not just efficiency: Promote realistic comfort ranges (e.g., moderate heating and cooling setpoints) and encourage shared use of appliances to align with degrowth principles.</p> <p>Use transparent and participatory processes: Co-design interventions with communities, schools, and local organisations to strengthen ownership and persistence of new habits.</p> <p>Combine technology with human engagement: Smart meters and dashboards are effective when paired with workshops, social comparison, and nudges that make the data actionable.</p>	<p>DON'Ts</p> <p>Don't frame behaviour change as restriction: Avoid messages that suggest loss of comfort or punitive measures; instead, emphasise wellbeing, fairness, and resilience.</p> <p>Don't rely only on short campaigns: One-off actions without long-term integration into city energy strategies tend to lose impact quickly.</p> <p>Don't ignore structural barriers: Behavioural advice alone will not succeed in poorly insulated homes or with obsolete appliances. Pair behaviour change with gradual technology upgrades.</p> <p>Don't underestimate rebound effects: Efficiency gains can be offset by higher consumption elsewhere. Anchor programmes in sufficiency to ensure that total demand decreases.</p>

<p>Ensure data protection: Respect GDPR and privacy rules by anonymising or aggregating data. This builds trust and prevents resistance from end-users.</p> <p>Monitor and report results: Use clear KPIs (absolute energy savings, CO₂ reductions, participation rates) and communicate outcomes to reinforce motivation and accountability.</p>	<p>Don't neglect vulnerable groups: Generic campaigns may miss low-income households or communities with language or digital barriers. Tailor communication and provide direct support.</p> <p>Don't overcomplicate tools: Complex apps and dashboards can alienate users. Interfaces should be intuitive, multilingual, and accessible.</p>
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● POLICY FRAMEWORK

Relevant Policies
<p>International level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> At the international level, it may align with the European Green Deal, the 2030 Agenda and its Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the New European Bauhaus, the Paris Agreement and COP climate goals, UN-Habitat's New Urban Agenda, the Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy, the Resilient Cities Network, or the Just Transition Framework.
<p>European level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> At the European sectoral level, relevant references may include the EU Urban Mobility Framework, the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, the Smart Cities Marketplace, the EU Biodiversity Strategy, the Fit for 55 Package, the EU Climate Adaptation Strategy, REPowerEU, the Renovation Wave initiative, and the Digital Europe Programme.
<p>National level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> At the national or regional level, the topic may relate to National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs), Climate Adaptation Plans, Urban Agendas, Smart City strategies, Sustainable Mobility Plans, Circular Economy roadmaps, national Green Deals or climate legislation, or investment frameworks such as the NextGenerationEU recovery funds.
<p>Local level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> At the local level, supporting references may include Local Climate Action Plans (SECAP or PACES), Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP), strategies for renaturalisation or green

infrastructure, Smart City action plans, Local Urban Agendas (such as Agenda 21), as well as local housing, energy renovation, regeneration, digitalisation or open data strategies.

● **STAKEHOLDER ROLES AND ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK**

Stakeholder	Role	Type of Collaboration
Municipal Authorities	Lead energy-awareness campaigns, regulate energy demand policies, integrate degrowth principles in local climate/energy plans	Regulatory / Financial
Educational Institutions & NGOs	<i>Develop and deliver awareness programmes, citizen training, and behaviour-change initiatives</i>	<i>Educational / Social</i>
Energy Utilities & Grid Operators	<i>Provide real-time consumption data, enable demand-response, and integrate behavioural programmes into smart metering</i>	<i>Technical / Data Provider</i>
Citizens & Communities	<i>Adopt sufficiency practices, co-create behavioural change actions, and engage in participatory processes</i>	<i>Social / Behavioural</i>
Local Businesses & SMEs	<i>Implement efficiency and sufficiency strategies in daily operations, contribute to awareness campaigns</i>	<i>Operational / Innovation</i>

● **MAIN REFERENCES**

GOOD PRACTICES / SOME EXAMPLES
Project
<p>Project name: LIFE Lugo + Biodinámico Location: Lugo, Galicia, Spain Description: Urban adaptation and bioclimatic pilot focusing on low-energy construction (timber, materials, monitoring of energy use and comfort). Link: https://concellodelugo.gal/es/actuaciones/proyecto-lugobiodinamico</p>
<p>Project name: Gotland Energy Transition – Sufficiency Scenario Location: Gotland, Sweden Description: Community-based sufficiency modeling with EnergyPLAN to compare growth vs degrowth pathways. Link: https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/09654313.2025.2543959</p>
<p>Project name: DELaw – Degrowth through Energy Law</p>

Location: European Union

Description: Research into embedding degrowth principles in energy law—aiming to reorient policy toward demand reduction.

Link: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101163065>

Web-site

Website: Energy Sufficiency Research Platform

Link: <https://energysufficiency.de/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/1-s2.0-S0301421521003530-main.pdf>

Description: Study on sufficiency's role in EU energy and climate planning.

Website: Degrowth.info – Urban Energy Sufficiency

Link: <https://degrowth.info/en/library/reducing-energy-dependence-at-urban-scale-as-an-aspect-of-degrowth>

Description: Collection of case studies and articles on sufficiency and urban energy degrowth.

Paper

Paper title: Degrowth can work — here's how science can help

Authors: Jason Hickel, Giorgos Kallis, Tim Jackson, Daniel O'Neill, Juliet Schor, Julia Steinberger, Peter Victor, Diana Ürge-Vorsatz

Description: Advocacy for prosperity with lower energy/material use, emphasizing sufficiency policies.

Journal: *Nature*, 612 (2022)

DOI or link: [10.1038/d41586-022-04412-x](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-04412-x)

Paper title: Degrowth: a theory of radical abundance

Authors: Jason Hickel

Description: Conceptual exploration of degrowth and the Low Energy Demand (LED) scenario for deep decarbonization

Journal: *Real-World Economics*

DOI or link: <https://www.paecon.net/PAEReview/issue87/Hickel87.pdf>

Paper title: The Potential of Sufficiency Measures

Authors: Zozmann, E. et al.

Description: Modeling of sufficiency measures in fully renewable systems showing demand reductions up to 20.5%.

Journal: *Cornell University*

DOI or link: [arXiv:2109.00453](https://arxiv.org/abs/2109.00453)

Paper title: Energy communities for degrowth

Authors: Petrovics, D., Savini, F

Description: Framework for democratic, sufficiency-oriented energy communities embracing degrowth principles.

Journal: *Energy Research and Social Science*

DOI or link: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2025.103946>

- **KEY CONSIDERATIONS**

Additional Notes

Risks and Barriers

- Technical reliability: Behavioural interventions depend on the availability of accurate, real-time energy data. Poor integration between smart meters, dashboards, and building management systems can undermine trust and participation.
- Rebound effect: Efficiency gains can trigger increased consumption elsewhere, as described by the Jevons paradox. Without sufficiency measures, the environmental impact may be neutralised.
- Budget prioritisation: Behavioural programmes are often seen as “soft” measures compared to infrastructure, leading to underfunding and short-lived campaigns.
- Social resistance: If measures are perceived as limiting comfort, intrusive, or patronising, citizens may disengage. Clear communication and co-design are essential.
- Equity challenges: Vulnerable groups in poor housing conditions may struggle to adopt behavioural recommendations, requiring tailored support.

Enabling Factors

- Policy alignment: EU directives (e.g., Energy Efficiency Directive, Renovation Wave) support behaviour-based energy savings, creating political momentum.
- Digital readiness: Cities with advanced metering infrastructure and open data platforms are better positioned to deliver effective behavioural interventions.
- Community engagement: Co-creation with schools, housing associations, and NGOs increases legitimacy and persistence of behaviour change.
- Degrowth framing: By promoting sufficiency and wellbeing instead of growth, behavioural actions avoid rebound effects and strengthen public acceptance.

Factsheet 9.- Environmental/Social: Life-cycle Thinking and circularity (CIRCE)

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE AND GOVERNANCE	LIFE-CYCLE THINKING AND CIRCULARITY
DESCRIPTION	
Technical description	
<p>Introduction</p> <p><i>Life-cycle thinking looks at the entire life of a building or urban asset—from raw material extraction to manufacturing, transport, construction, use, maintenance, and end-of-life. Instead of focusing only on energy in operation, it measures embodied impacts (materials, manufacturing, transport, construction processes) and end-of-life outcomes (demolition, landfill, recycling, or reuse). Circularity then acts on those insights: it changes how we design, procure, build, operate, and deconstruct so that materials remain in use at their highest value for as long as possible.</i></p> <p><i>This action equips cities and project teams to quantify impacts with Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA) and to intervene with circular strategies such as design for disassembly (DfD), high-value reuse, urban mining, and materials passports. The result is lower embodied greenhouse-gas emissions, fewer extraction impacts, less waste, and better resilience to supply-chain shocks.</i></p> <p>Objectives</p> <p><i>Quantify environmental impacts across the full life cycle (carbon, resource use, water, waste), using recognised standards (e.g., ISO 14040/14044, EN 15978, EN 15804 for Environmental Product Declarations—EPDs).</i></p> <p><i>Reduce embodied carbon and resource demand by selecting low-impact materials, reusing components, and specifying products with robust, verified EPDs.</i></p> <p><i>Enable future reuse through DfD, standardized fixings, modular systems, and clear documentation (e.g., materials passports).</i></p> <p><i>Close material loops with selective demolition/deconstruction, on-site sorting, certified reuse, and urban mining partnerships.</i></p> <p><i>Integrate LCA and circularity into procurement, permits, and contracts so that outcomes are measurable and enforceable.</i></p> <p>Technical Scope and Standards</p> <p><i>LCA follows a clear methodology so results are comparable and defensible.</i></p> <p><i>Functional Unit (FU): for buildings, typical FU is 1 m² of Gross Floor Area over a reference study period (e.g., 50–60 years).</i></p>	

System Boundaries: per EN 15978, cover modules A1–A3 (product stage, including raw materials and manufacturing), A4–A5 (transport to site, construction/installation), B1–B7 (use stage, including maintenance, repair, replacements, energy and water in use), C1–C4 (end-of-life), and D (benefits and loads beyond system boundary—e.g., credited benefits from reuse/recycling).

Data Sources: use EN 15804-compliant EPDs for products when available; complement with quality-assured generic datasets where needed. Track data quality (representativeness, age, completeness, uncertainty).

Impact Indicators: at minimum Global Warming Potential (GWP); where relevant add Resource Use, Acidification, Eutrophication, Photochemical Ozone Formation, Water Use, and Waste.

Frameworks & Tools: align with EU Level(s) indicators for design and public reporting. Typical software: One Click LCA, SimaPro, GaBi, OpenLCA.

Workflow and Responsibilities

1) Early Design — “Quantify first, decide early”

- *Screening LCA: run a quick model during concept design to identify hotspots (e.g., structural frame, façade, insulation, MEP).*
- *Optioneering: compare alternatives such as low-carbon concrete mixes, timber or hybrid structures, high-recycled-content steel, or lightweight assemblies that reduce material mass.*
- *DfD Principles: select reversible connections (bolts, screws), accessible fixings, standardised modules, and layer separation (structure, services, finishes) to enable disassembly and replacement.*
- *Specification: require EPDs and declare repairability, reusability, and recycled content in tenders.*

2) Detailed Design & Procurement — “Make it contractual”

- *Performance Targets: include embodied-carbon limits (e.g., kgCO₂e/m² by element or whole building) and minimum recycled content requirements in procurement documents.*
- *Materials Passport: prepare a bill of materials with IDs, quantities, and documentation to support future reuse.*
- *Supplier Engagement: pre-qualify vendors providing EN 15804 EPDs, take-back schemes, and component leasing where appropriate (carpets, luminaires, façades).*

3) Construction — “Build for disassembly, track materials”

- *Selective Construction & QA: verify declared product EPDs, batch numbers, and installation methods that preserve disassembly potential.*
- *On-site Waste Management: sort by high-value fractions (metals, timber, clean concrete, plasterboard); protect reusable offcuts/components.*
- *Digital Tracking: update the materials passport with as-built quantities and locations (QR/BIM link).*

4) Use & Maintenance — “Keep value high”

- *Planned Maintenance: choose replacement cycles that extend component life (e.g., re-laminating, re-finishing).*
- *Minor Works Protocols: require that small refurbishments preserve DfD and update the materials passport.*
- *Monitoring: periodic LCA updates when major refurbishments occur; track waste diversion and reused content over time.*

5) End-of-Life / Next Use — “Mine the city”

- *Pre-demolition Audits: map reusable elements (doors, radiators, beams, façade cassettes) and recyclable streams.*
- *Deconstruction Plans: prefer sequenced disassembly over demolition; schedule reverse logistics to reuse hubs or digital marketplaces.*
- *Module D Accounting: document credits from reuse/recycling to show net life-cycle benefits.*
- *Circular Design & Intervention Catalogue (what to do in practice)*
- *Structure: cement-reduced concretes, high-recycled steel, timber/hybrid systems; standard spans and bolt-on secondary structures.*
- *Envelope: demountable façades (cassette systems), removable rainscreens, mechanical fixings, replaceable insulation layers.*
- *Interiors: modular partitions, flooring and ceiling systems designed for lift-and-reuse; leased carpet tiles with take-back.*
- *MEP: accessible service corridors, plug-and-play components, product-as-a-service models (e.g., luminaires, batteries).*
- *Public realm: prefabricated elements, reused pavers/street furniture, reversible foundations for temporary uses.*

KPIs and Verification

Embodied GWP (A1–A3, A4–A5, B, C, D): kgCO₂e/m² for key elements and whole asset.

Reused/Recovered Content: % of components reused or % recycled content by mass and by value.

Waste Diversion: % construction and demolition waste diverted from landfill; hazardous waste handled per regulation.

Design for Disassembly Score: qualitative checklist (reversible fixings, access to connections, modularity, documentation).

Data Quality: share of product quantities covered by 3rd-party EPDs vs generic datasets.

Technical Risks and How We Manage Them

Data gaps or inconsistent EPDs: mitigate with supplier engagement, documented assumptions, and sensitivity analysis.

Design lock-in: start LCA very early to avoid “too late to change” decisions.

Cost concerns: apply total cost of ownership thinking (resale value of components, avoided landfill, reduced new material purchases).

Quality/Compliance: require third-party critical review for public claims and align with Level(s) reporting for comparability.

Integration with City Policy & Procurement

Planning & Permits: require screening LCA at concept stage and detailed LCA at building permit.

Public Procurement: include embodied-carbon thresholds, EPD coverage requirements, and DfD criteria in tender scoring.

Deconstruction Bylaws: mandate pre-demolition audits and deconstruction for suitable assets; set reuse quotas for municipal works.

City Platforms: support reuse hubs and digital marketplaces to connect deconstruction sites with designers and contractors.

Expected Benefits

Adopting life-cycle thinking and circular practices cuts embodied carbon and reduces virgin-material demand. Projects typically see meaningful double-digit percentage reductions in embodied GWP when circular options are chosen early, alongside significant waste diversion during construction and end-of-life. Documentation (materials passports, Level(s) reporting) makes these gains visible, auditable, and replicable across the municipal portfolio.

Visual Information

Figure 5 Building LCA stages according to EN-15978

– Life-Cycle Stages (EN 15978) and Impact Modules

A simple banded diagram showing stages A1–A3 (products), A4–A5 (construction), B (use), C (end-of-life), D (beyond system boundary), with arrows indicating data inputs (EPDs) and outputs (impacts).

SCORING

Technical Scoring

The technical complexity of implementing LCA and circularity is moderate to high. Performing a full LCA requires expertise in ISO 14040/44 methodologies, data modelling, and access to reliable life-cycle inventory (LCI) databases such as Ecoinvent or ELCD. Integration with existing procurement and construction processes can also be challenging, particularly when multiple stakeholders (designers, suppliers, contractors, municipalities) must adopt common reporting tools. While simplified LCAs and sectoral tools reduce complexity, the accuracy of results is lower. This makes technical implementation feasible but knowledge-intensive, requiring skilled consultants or in-house experts

Finance Scoring

The financial effort is medium. Initial costs stem from purchasing or licensing LCA software, training staff, and hiring consultants for complex projects. Ongoing costs relate to data collection, monitoring, and periodic updates. However, these investments can be offset by long-term financial benefits: optimised material use, lower operational impacts, and compliance with EU green procurement criteria. Access to funding through EU programmes (Horizon Europe, LIFE, NextGenerationEU) can significantly reduce upfront costs, especially for municipalities or pilot projects.

Environment Scoring

The environmental benefits are very high. LCA provides a systemic framework to identify and mitigate emissions, resource depletion, and waste generation across the entire life cycle of materials and buildings. By guiding circular strategies such as reuse, recycling, and eco-design, it helps avoid lock-ins to carbon-intensive technologies and maximises alignment with EU climate neutrality goals. For example, studies show that incorporating recycled materials and modular designs can reduce embodied carbon in construction by up to 30–50% compared with business-as-usual practices.

Social Scoring

*The social acceptance of LCA and circularity is **generally positive**, though challenges exist. Stakeholders increasingly recognise the value of transparent environmental information and circular practices. Citizens appreciate visible actions such as reuse centres, material passports, and recycled-content buildings. However, resistance may arise if LCA requirements are seen as bureaucratic or if they increase costs for small businesses. Effective communication—translating complex indicators into accessible metrics (e.g., “CO₂ per m² of housing”)—is key to ensuring that LCA outcomes are trusted and embraced.*

CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

Recurrent risks

Frequent risks during implementation may include technical difficulties, budget limitations, resistance from end-users, or legal restrictions. These should be considered to adapt the solution realistically to its context.

City issues like traffic, lack of green areas, or poor housing

*Environmental problems like pollution or climate risks
 Management gaps like weak planning or low citizen involvement
 Obsolete technologies with high energy consumption or that fail to meet current standards.*

● **TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE**

Phases of implementation	
P1	Assessment & Goal Definition
P1.1	Assessment & Goal Definition Determine the objectives (e.g., reducing embodied energy, prioritising recyclability).
P1.2	Data Inventory (LCI): Collect input/output data on energy use, emissions, raw material extraction, and waste.
P1.3	Hotspot Identification: Identify processes or life-cycle stages with the highest environmental burdens.
P2	Planning & Strategy Design
P2.1	Planning & Strategy Design Test strategies such as reuse, remanufacturing, or material substitution.
P2.2	Circular Design Integration: Apply eco-design principles, considering disassembly, modularity, and recyclability.
P3	Implementation & Monitoring
P3.1	Pilot Actions: Implement demonstration projects (e.g., recycled concrete use, urban wood recovery).
P3.2	Stakeholder Engagement: Train municipalities, contractors, and citizens on recycling/reuse practices.
P3.3	Monitoring & Reporting: Use LCA-based indicators to track environmental performance (CO ₂ , resource use).

● **GANTT.**

	M 1	M 2	M 3	M 4	M 5	M 6	M 7	M 8	M 9	M 10	M 11	M 12	M 13
P1	Assessment and Goal definition												
P2	Planning and Strategy Design												
P3	Implementation and Monitoring												

● STRATEGIC

RECOMMENDATIONS	
DOs	<p>Integrate LCA early in planning: Apply life-cycle thinking during the design phase of buildings, infrastructures, or procurement processes to prevent lock-in to unsustainable solutions.</p> <p>Adopt circular procurement: Use public procurement as a driver for circularity by including requirements for recycled content, modularity, or material passports in tenders.</p> <p>Ensure transparency and standardisation: Rely on internationally recognised methodologies (ISO 14040/44, EN 15804, EU Product Environmental Footprint) to ensure comparability and credibility of LCA results.</p> <p>Promote local material loops: Encourage the reuse and recycling of construction and demolition waste locally, reducing transport impacts and creating local green jobs.</p> <p>Invest in capacity building: Provide training for municipal staff, architects, engineers, and SMEs to develop LCA competencies and circular design practices.</p>
DON'Ts	<p>Don't use LCA as a tick-box exercise: Avoid conducting LCAs only for compliance without integrating results into decision-making.</p> <p>Don't neglect data quality: Using generic or outdated databases undermines the accuracy of results and can lead to poor policy or design decisions.</p> <p>Don't overlook social aspects: Circularity is not only about materials and energy but also about creating fair, inclusive systems. Excluding citizens or SMEs from processes risks public resistance.</p> <p>Don't ignore end-of-life planning: Designing products or buildings without considering reuse and recycling pathways perpetuates linear "take-make-dispose" patterns.</p> <p>Don't assume one-size-fits-all: Copying LCA or circular models from other regions without adaptation may fail due to different local waste streams, regulatory environments, or cultural contexts.</p>

● POLICY FRAMEWORK

Relevant Policies
International level
At the international level , it may align with the European Green Deal, the 2030 Agenda and its Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the New European Bauhaus, the Paris Agreement and COP climate goals, UN-Habitat’s New Urban Agenda, the Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy, the Resilient Cities Network, or the Just Transition Framework.
European level
At the European sectoral level , relevant references may include the EU Urban Mobility Framework, the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, the Smart Cities Marketplace, the EU Biodiversity Strategy, the Fit for 55 Package, the EU Climate Adaptation Strategy, REPowerEU, the Renovation Wave initiative, and the Digital Europe Programme.
National level
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Local level
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● STAKEHOLDER ROLES AND ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

Stakeholder	Role	Type of Collaboration
Municipal Authorities	Regulation, co-financing, project lead	Regulatory / Financial
Construction Companies & Developers	Implementation of circular design, adoption of LCA requirements in projects	Operational / Technical
Waste Management & Recycling Firm	Provide infrastructure for reuse, recycling, and material recovery	Technical / Service Provider
Universities & Research Institutes	Methodological support, database development, training, and innovation	Research / Capacity Building
Citizens & Housing Associations	Adoption of circular behaviours (sorting, reuse), participation in pilot projects	Social / Behavioural

● MAIN REFERENCES

GOOD PRACTICES / SOME EXAMPLES
Project
<p>Project Name: LIFE Level(s) Location: European Union (multi-country) Description: Promotes the adoption of the EU Level(s) framework for sustainable buildings, which integrates LCA-based indicators (carbon footprint, material efficiency, resource use) into design and certification processes. Demonstrates how municipalities and developers can embed life-cycle thinking into public procurement. Link: LIFE Level(s)</p> <p>Project Name: Buildings as Material Banks (BAMB) Location: Belgium, Netherlands, UK, and others (Horizon 2020 project) Description: Developed methodologies and digital tools (material passports, reversible building design protocols) to enable reuse and recycling of construction materials. Provided real-life case studies where LCA metrics were used to measure and optimise circularity. Link: BAMB Project</p>
Web-site
<p>Website: European Commission – Circular Economy Action Plan Link: Circular Economy Action Plan Description: Official EU site with policies, guidance, and updates on circularity strategies, including links to LCA-based frameworks and implementation tools for cities and businesses.</p> <p>Website: Circular Buildings Toolkit (Ellen MacArthur Foundation) Link: Circular Buildings Toolkit Description: Provides practical guidance and tools for integrating circular economy principles into building projects, including how to apply LCA to materials selection, design, and end-of-life strategies.</p>
Paper
<p>Paper Title: Life cycle assessment in the built environment: A critical review Authors: Cabeza, L. F., Rincón, L., Vilariño, V., Pérez, G., & Castell, A. Journal: Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, 29, 394–416 (2014) DOI/Link: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2013.08.037 Description: Comprehensive review of LCA applications in construction, highlighting methodological challenges, databases, and results that inform circular design strategies.</p> <p>Paper Title: Circular economy in the construction sector: A review of strategies, implementation, and impacts Authors: Ghisellini, P., Ripa, M., & Ulgiati, S. Journal: Journal of Cleaner Production, 178, 618–643 (2018)</p>

DOI/Link: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.11.207>

Description: Examines how circular economy approaches, including LCA, can be operationalised in the construction sector, with emphasis on recycling, reuse, and material efficiency.

Factsheet 10.- Environmental/Social: Waste: End of Life Phase (DEMIR)

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS	WASTE: END-OF-LIFE PHASE
DESCRIPTION	
Technical description	
<p>The End-of-Life (EoL) phase in building renovation and demolition refers to the stage at which materials, components and products reach the end of their functional life and must be discarded, reused or recycled. This phase plays a critical role in shaping the environmental footprint of construction activities and determines how well cities can close material loops and reduce landfill dependency.</p> <p>In the EU, construction and demolition waste (CDW) is the largest waste stream by volume, accounting for approximately 25–30% of all waste generated (Eurostat, 2023). Poorly managed, this waste can increase pollution and resource depletion. However, when properly planned, it offers valuable inputs to the circular economy.</p> <p>Waste from EoL phase can include;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Concrete, wood, glass, metal, and plastics, ● Hazardous materials (e.g., asbestos, lead-based paint), ● Packaging from new installations, ● Organic waste from households (during renovations in occupied buildings). <p>Addressing this waste stream is essential for aligning with circular economy goals, reducing renovation-related emissions, increasing resource efficiency and empowering local value chains, including reuse cooperatives and social enterprises.</p> <p>A strategic and technically sound approach to the EoL phase supports the EU Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC), which outlines the waste hierarchy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Prevention (Reduction): Prevent or reduce the generation of waste before it occurs. ● Reuse: Use materials or components again without significant reprocessing. ● Recycling: Process waste materials into new raw materials for products. ● Recovery: Extract energy or resources from waste that cannot be recycled. ● Disposal: Safely eliminate waste that cannot be reused, recycled, or recovered. 	

European Commission. (2023). *Waste Framework Directive*.

https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/waste-and-recycling/waste-framework-directive_en

Throughout the entire life cycle of a building, systematic tracking and reporting of material flows—including the quantities and types of materials used, reused, and discarded—play a crucial role in achieving circularity and resource efficiency. This approach is strongly encouraged by the **Level(s) framework**, the European Union’s voluntary tool for assessing and improving the sustainability of buildings. Level(s) promotes life cycle thinking by guiding stakeholders to document material use and waste generation at every stage, facilitating informed decision-making for waste minimization and maximizing opportunities for recycling and reuse during the end-of-life phase.

Complementing this, the recently adopted **Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) 2024/1275** introduces stronger regulatory requirements that align with circular economy principles. The directive mandates more rigorous sustainability criteria for buildings, including enhanced end-of-life material management strategies and the use of digital building logbooks to improve transparency and traceability of materials throughout the building’s lifespan. By requiring comprehensive reporting and encouraging the integration of circular economy practices, EPBD 2024/1275 aims to reduce environmental impacts, support the decarbonization of the construction sector, and promote sustainable resource use. Together, the Level(s) framework and EPBD 2024/1275 provide a cohesive foundation for embedding effective waste management and material reporting into modern building design, construction, and demolition processes.

SCORING

Technical Scoring

The implementation of waste management during the end-of-life (EoL) phase involves a high level of technical difficulty due to several factors. Unlike traditional demolition, selective dismantling requires skilled personnel who are trained to carefully deconstruct buildings while separating different materials for recycling or reuse. Integrating project-based activities with local or regional recycling and reuse infrastructure requires coordination and mapping. Additionally, the handling of hazardous waste (e.g., asbestos, lead paint, outdated insulation materials) requires certified professionals.

Finance Scoring

The estimated cost of implementing waste management during the end-of-life phase is relatively high, reflecting several key financial factors. Initial investment costs include specialized equipment for selective dismantling, training programs for skilled personnel and investments in safe hazardous waste handling and storage facilities. Operational and maintenance costs encompass ongoing labor expenses, transportation and processing of separated materials and compliance with regulatory requirements related to hazardous waste disposal. Additionally, there may be a need for external funding or subsidies to support the upfront capital expenditure, especially for smaller contractors or municipalities with limited budgets.

Environment Scoring

The environmental impact of implementing selective waste management during the end-of-life phase is generally very positive, contributing significantly to sustainability goals. By promoting selective dismantling and material separation, this approach reduces landfill waste and enables higher rates of recycling and reuse, thereby conserving natural resources and lowering the demand for virgin materials. Additionally, careful handling and proper disposal of hazardous materials prevent harmful emissions and soil or water contamination. While some emissions and energy consumption are associated with transportation and processing of separated waste streams, these emissions and energy use are much lower than those from traditional demolition and sending waste to landfills. Overall, this approach minimizes resource consumption and waste generation.

Social Scoring

Selective dismantling and material recovery in the EoL phase are generally well aligned with societal values such as sustainability, circular economy principles, and responsible resource use. Public acceptance tends to be positive, especially when waste is visibly sorted and reused locally, reducing the environmental impact and promoting transparency in construction practices. The approach contributes to social goals by enabling local job creation in deconstruction, sorting, and reuse sectors. It also fosters community-level engagement in sustainability discussions, especially in urban areas where construction waste and illegal dumping are common concerns.

CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

Recurrent risks

Technical difficulties may arise due to the need for trained personnel, availability of appropriate equipment, and lack of standardized procedures for selective dismantling and material sorting. In cities with outdated demolition practices or limited expertise, this can delay implementation and reduce effectiveness.

Budget limitations are common, particularly in municipalities or projects with tight financial constraints. The high initial costs for labor, equipment, and hazardous waste handling may limit uptake unless supported by external funding or subsidies.

Legal and regulatory barriers can make implementation difficult, especially in places where there are no clear rules for selective demolition, handling hazardous waste, or reusing materials. Complicated permits and different local laws can slow down the process or make it harder to carry out.

- **PHASES OF IMPLEMENTATION**

Phases of implementation	
P1	Baseline Assessment & Planning
Assess current material flows and identify opportunities to reduce, reuse or recover waste before renovation begins.	
P1.1	Pre-renovation waste audit Assess types and quantities of expected waste before work begins.
P1.2	Map material composition and volumes Identify main materials (e.g. concrete, wood, metal) to estimate reuse/recovery potential.
P1.3	Identify existing reuse/recycling infrastructure Locate nearby facilities and services for material recovery or donation.
P1.4	Engage with local actors Build early collaboration with waste companies, recyclers, and social economy partners.
P2	Infrastructure Set-up
Enable on-site separation, reuse and circular logistics.	
P2.1	Set up on-site sorting stations Install containers for different material streams to maximize recycling.
P2.2	Define safe handling of hazardous materials Ensure proper identification and separation of asbestos, lead, etc.
P3	Capacity Building & Engagement
Equip workers and residents to implement waste strategies.	
P3.1	Train construction crews Educate workers on selective dismantling, sorting and safe handling.
P3.2	Educate tenants Inform residents on how to sort and reduce household waste during and after works.
P3.3	Engage community organizations Involve local NGOs or social enterprises to support reuse, repair, or donation activities.
P4	Operation, Monitoring & Evaluation
Track waste flows, evaluate results, and ensure continuous improvement.	
P4.1	Collect and report waste KPIs Monitor volumes of waste, reuse, and recycling each month
P4.2	Audit actual performance Compare real outcomes against planned targets (e.g. 70% CDW recovery).

● GANTT

		M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
P1	Baseline Assessment & Planning												
	P.1.1 Pre-renovation waste audit												
	P.1.2 Map material composition and volumes												
	P.1.3 Identify existing reuse/recycling infrastructure												
	P.1.4 Engage with local actors												
P2	Infrastructure Set-up												
	P.2.1 Set up on-site sorting stations												
	P.2.2 Define safe handling of hazardous materials												
P3	Capacity Building & Engagement												
	P.3.1 Train construction crews												
	P.3.2 Educate tenants												
	P.3.3 Engage community organizations												
P4	Operation, Monitoring & Evaluation												
	P.4.1 Collect and report waste KPIs												
	P.4.2 Audit actual performance												

● STRATEGIC

RECOMMENDATIONS	
<p>DOs</p> <p>Design renovation plans with circularity in mind- prioritize reuse of existing materials.</p> <p>Separate waste on-site into distinct streams: wood, metal, concrete, plastic, glass, gypsum, hazardous waste.</p> <p>Collaborate with social enterprises and reuse centres for materials redistribution.</p> <p>Educate tenants on correct sorting, reuse practices and train workers in selective dismantling and identification of reusable materials.</p>	<p>DON'Ts</p> <p>Don't demolish reusable or repairable elements without assessment.</p> <p>Don't mix hazardous and non-hazardous waste—it compromises recovery.</p> <p>Don't discard materials before checking local reuse initiatives or markets.</p> <p>Don't assume residents or workers already know how to sort or reuse correctly.</p>

● **CROSS-LINK MATRIX BETWEEN TECHNICAL ACTIONS**

Main Topic ↓ Related →	Baseline Assessment & Planning	Infrastructure Set-up	Capacity Building & Engagement	Operation, Monitoring & Evaluation
Baseline Assessment & Planning			C Guides training content and focus	S Provides baseline for evaluation
Infrastructure Set-up	R Needs data from baseline		S Needs trained workforce for operations	
Capacity Building & Engagement				S Ensures participation for evaluation
Operation, Monitoring & Evaluation	S Compares actual vs. planned performance			

● **POLICY FRAMEWORK**

Relevant Policies	
International level	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Paris Agreement: Encourages carbon neutrality efforts where reducing construction-related emissions (e.g., through material reuse and recycling) . ● 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (UN SDGs): SDG 12- Responsible Consumption and Production (especially Target 12.5 on waste reduction through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse) ● Global Covenant of Mayors: Encourages local governments to adopt climate mitigation and adaptation actions including sustainable waste and resource management in buildings. EoL waste actions contribute to reported emissions reductions. 	
European level	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● European Green Deal: Promotes a circular economy and zero pollution ambition; Aims to ensure that waste is prevented, reused and recycled, particularly in construction and demolition sectors. ● Waste Framework Directive (Directive 2008/98/EC, amended by 2018/851/EU): Establishes the waste hierarchy (prevention, reuse, recycling, recovery, disposal). ● Construction & Demolition Waste Management Protocol (EU Construction and Demolition Waste Protocol, 2016): Promotes best practices for CDW sorting, recycling, and reuse across Europe. ● EU Circular Economy Action Plan: Prioritizes circularity in buildings and construction, including measures for material recovery, design for disassembly, and recycled content requirements. 	

- EPBD 2024/1275: Enhances the management of materials at the end-of-life phase by requiring circularity principles and digital reporting to improve reuse, recycling, and resource efficiency in building demolition and renovation.
- The Level(s) framework: Supports effective waste management at the end-of-life phase by promoting life cycle material reporting and encouraging reuse and recycling to reduce environmental impacts.

National level

- National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs): Outline national measures for energy efficiency, circularity and climate neutrality.
- Circular Economy Roadmap: Set country-specific strategies for transitioning to circular systems, often with a strong focus on the built environment.

Local level

- Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans: Local governments committing to reduce CO₂ emissions and adapt to climate change often integrate waste prevention and circular economy actions into their energy renovation and resource efficiency efforts.
- Waste Treatment Plans

● **STAKEHOLDER ROLES AND ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK**

Stakeholder	Role	Type of Collaboration
Municipal Authorities	Define local waste regulations, monitor compliance. Integrate EoL strategies into urban plans (e.g., SECAPs, housing strategies).	Leadership/ Regulatory
Social Housing Providers	Integrate waste strategies into renovation processes, facilitate tenant engagement.	Facilitator
Waste Management Companies	Operate collection, sorting, recycling and recovery systems; manage hazardous and construction and demolition waste (CDW).	Technical/ Service Provider
Tenants and Residents	Sort household waste, engage with training and awareness programs.	Participatory role
Urban Planners	Integrate material flow planning, advise on reuse logistics and zoning for circular infrastructure (e.g., reuse depots).	Technical
Academic and Research Institutions	Conduct LCA/LCC/SLCA studies; assess material recovery effectiveness; support capacity building	Capacity builder

● **MAIN REFERENCES**

GOOD PRACTICES / SOME EXAMPLES	
Project	
<i>Project name:</i>	LEGOFIT
<i>Location:</i>	Guadalajara (Spain), Istanbul (Türkiye), Betzdorf (Luxembourg), Pécs (Hungary) and Nuenen (Netherlands)

Description: LEGOFIT is a Horizon Europe project developing scalable smart solutions to deliver Energy Positive Homes in new builds and renovations.

Link: <https://www.legofit.eu/>

Web-site

- European Commission – Circular Economy Action Plan
https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/circular-economy-action-plan_en
- EU Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC)
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32008L0098>
- Eurostat Waste Statistics
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/waste/data/database>
- UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)
<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

Paper

- **European Commission (2020). "Circular Economy in the Built Environment."**
Summary of barriers and enablers for circularity in construction.
- **EEA Report: "Construction and Demolition Waste: Challenges and Opportunities in a Circular Economy" (2020)**
<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/construction-and-demolition-waste-challenges>

Factsheet 10.- Finance: Economic models, Reducing energy poverty and available grants and funding (UoY)

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT	ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF ENERGY ACTIONS
DESCRIPTION	
Technical description	
SUBTOPIC A — ECONOMIC MODELS	
<p>Bottom-up business model.</p>	
<p><u>Energy Saving Model Development:</u> The first step involves application of the SUPER-i energy-saving model to estimate the expected energy savings from each proposed intervention. This process begins with conducting on-site audits to gather baseline data on current energy usage and building characteristics. Utilising software tools and simulation techniques, the model evaluates the impact of various energy efficiency interventions, considering factors such as building type, existing energy systems, and climatic conditions. The model's accuracy is validated through historical data and pilot studies.</p>	
<p><u>Simulation of Financial and Socio-Economic Variables:</u> In the second step, economic models are used to project future values of critical financial and socio-economic variables. These include the energy market bid price, inflation rate, interest rate on debt, property value growth rate, rent growth rate, and the default rate on rent. Additionally, socio-economic variables such as regional employment rates, national income growth rates, earning rates on personal savings, corporate taxes, private investment, private consumption, and government spending are simulated. Historical data from reliable sources are gathered to develop and calibrate the model. By running multiple simulations, future scenarios for each variable are generated, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of potential risks and uncertainties.</p>	
<p>Calculation of the Social Discount Rate (SDR): The third step involves calculating the social discount rate (SDR) using the weighted average method (WAM). The SDR is a combination of the social rate of time preference (SRTP), which measures private savings/consumption, and the social opportunity cost of capital (SOC), which measures private investment. The formula for SDR is: $SDR = WAM = (a)SOC + (1-a)SRTP$, where 'a' represents the proportion of project cost funded by private investment and (1-a) by public investments. The simulated socio-economic variables are used to derive the SRTP and SOC, ensuring that the SDR reflects the socio-economic context of each region.</p>	
<p>Financial and Socio-Economic Impact Analysis: In the fourth step, the financial and socio-economic impacts of the interventions for each building are analysed using the energy savings model findings, the simulated financial variables, and the social discount rate. Financial viability is</p>	

assessed through metrics such as Return on Investment (ROI), Net Cash Flow (NCF) and risk-adjusted extra return. Socio-economic benefits, including job creation, improved living conditions, and environmental impact, are also evaluated. This comprehensive analysis ensures that the interventions are both financially viable and socially beneficial.

PPP funding mechanics:

- **Shared savings contract:** The ESCO is responsible for covering the investment cost and operating the EE renovations while the housing association provide the physical asset (building); The ESCO receives the minimum guaranteed savings + 65% of the extra energy savings while the housing association receives 35% of the extra energy savings and the increase in property market value; The technical and performance risk are covered by the ESCO.
- **Guaranteed savings contract:** The housing association is responsible for covering the investment cost while the ESCO is responsible for operating and maintaining the EE renovations; The housing association receives the minimum guaranteed savings + 20% of the extra energy savings and the increase in property market value while the ESCO receives 5% of the extra energy savings; The technical and performance risk are covered by the ESCO.

Replication at Building Block Level: The fifth step involves scaling up the analysis from individual buildings to building blocks. Data from individual buildings are aggregated to re-assess financial and socio-economic impacts at this higher level of aggregation. This process identifies potential synergies and economies of scale, enhancing the overall effectiveness and efficiency of the interventions. By combining data from multiple buildings, the model is adjusted to account for interactions between them, providing a holistic view of the impacts at the building block level.

Replication at District Level: In the sixth step, the analysis is extended to the district level. Data from multiple building blocks are aggregated to evaluate the financial and socio-economic impacts across the entire district. This broader analysis identifies community-wide benefits and systemic improvements, offering insights into how large-scale energy efficiency renovations can contribute to regional sustainability goals. The model is further adjusted for district-wide interactions and infrastructure considerations, ensuring that the interventions are effective on a larger scale.

Ranking of Funding Solutions: The final step ranks the proposed funding solutions based on risk-adjusted returns. This ranking considers the overall impact on energy efficiency, financial returns, and socio-economic benefits. By prioritising solutions that offer the best balance of risk and return, the analysis provides actionable recommendations for policy and investment strategies. This ensures that the most effective and sustainable funding solutions are identified and implemented.

SUBTOPIC B — REDUCING ENERGY POVERTY

Targeting and EE bundles.

Prioritise buildings with high energy-expenditure burdens and high arrears; choose EE renovation bundles that reduce heat demand by $\geq 30\%$ (often 45–65%) to access national grants.

Key Performance Indicators.

Track annually:

Energy expenditure as a percentage of income:

The figure below shows the current annual energy cost paid by the residents in each lighthouse as a percentage of their annual income and the potential percentage after the EE renovations. We observe a significant decrease in energy expenditure to annual income for the residents in Boito and Riga, while for Faellesbo we observe a smaller reduction.

Percentage of residents unable to keep their houses cool during summer and warm in winter:

The figure below illustrates the percentage of residents unable to keep their homes cool during summer and warm during winter in each lighthouse. For this figure we observe that all the lighthouses show a substantial improvement.

Potential annual energy consumption per dwelling.

The figure below illustrates the current annual energy consumption per dwelling and the potential annual energy consumption after the implementation of the proposed EE renovations for each lighthouse district.

Potential annual energy savings per dwelling.

The figure below shows the potential annual energy savings per dwelling for each proposed EE renovation and the total potential annual energy savings for all EE renovations bundled together.

Potential annual CO2 emission reduction per dwelling in tonnes

The figure below shows the potential annual CO2 emission reduction in tonnes per dwelling for each EE renovation and for all EE renovation bundled together.

Technical Scoring

Does not apply

Finance Scoring

The figure below, shows the potential Return On Investment (ROI) for post EE renovation in each Lighthouse. Based on the ROI, the shared saving contract was ranked the most appropriate in each lighthouse. Furthermore, the investment in EE renovation in the SUPERSHINE lighthouses has a higher potential ROI than if the same amount was invested in S&P500 index.

Environment Scoring

Does not apply

Social Scoring

Boito (Trieste, IT): The affordability figure shows one of the largest post-retrofit drops in the energy expenditure to income ratio among lighthouses. The thermal-comfort figure also indicates a substantial reduction in residents reporting they cannot keep homes warm in winter and cool in summer. The consumption and savings figures point to substantial per-dwelling energy expenditure cuts once measures are bundled, with the CO₂ figure confirming meaningful per-dwelling emissions reductions.

Faellesbo (Herning, DK): The affordability figure shows a smaller yet positive reduction in energy-cost burden compared with the other sites. However, the thermal-comfort figure still shows a clear improvement. The consumption and savings figures indicate consistent demand reductions from the retrofit bundle, with corresponding per-dwelling CO₂ cuts.

Riga (LV): The affordability figure shows a large decline in energy-expenditure to income post-EE retrofit among the best improvements in the set. Thermal-comfort outcomes improve substantially. The energy consumption and energy savings figures show strong per-dwelling reductions when EE renovations are bundled, and the CO₂ figure signals notable emissions reductions at dwelling level

CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

Recurrent risks

Baseline and modelling error. If the pre-retrofit collected energy consumption data is wrong, the energy savings and economic analyses will be less accurate and misleading.

Electricity market bid price volatility. Energy price volatility can inflate or deflate monetised savings. Run multiple electricity market price scenarios (low, moderate, extreme).

Financing cost shocks. Interest-rate and inflation rises can reduce ROI and increase the payback period.

Regulatory changes. Regulatory changes such as in Italy, delays EE renovation implementations.

- PHASES OF IMPLEMENTATION

Phases of implementation	
P1	Data collection & model development
P1.1	Data collection & energy savings model development. Develop the SUPERSHINE Survey questions, distribute the survey to the SUPERSHINE lighthouses and fellow cities representatives, build the energy saving model to measure the post EE renovation potential energy savings and CO2 emission reduction from walls, roof, windows and PV solar panels.
P1.2	Price savings; build cash-flows. Monetise the potential energy savings from the proposed EE renovations; generate 20–25-year net cash-flows (NCFs) at building and district levels.
P1.3	Apply market and social discount rate. Apply Weighted-Average Method (WAM) SDR paths that combine a social time-preference term with opportunity-cost of capital and country growth projections.
P2	PPP contracts & finance
P2.1	Blend finance. Combine grants (national & local schemes), PPP contract , and crowdfunding taking into account levels of interest rate (low interest rate (2.00% - 3.15%), bank loan interest rate (4.5%-6.5%) and risky investment interest rate (7.00%-9.5%)).
P2.2	Choose the PPP model. Rank Shared Savings (SS) , Guaranteed Savings (GS) , and ESC using risk-adjusted returns for both housing association and ESCO; specify revenue sharing, responsibilities, and risk allocation; set up ESA with the ESCO.
P3	Structure crowdfunding strategy
P3.1	investors safeguards. investors are guaranteed a minimum guaranteed energy savings in terms of positive cash flow for a specific duration pre agreed. If the energy savings realised from the EE renovations are below expected in a period of time, the shortfall will be covered by the ESA account and the ESCO.

P3.2	Social housing and tenant safeguards. The social housing association forgoes the right to the energy savings for a period of time (payback period). Then receives all energy savings. The tenants keep measured bill savings; ESA account covers EE under performance; ESCO covers energy saving shortfalls up to the guaranteed amount.
P3.3	KPI monitoring. Track energy, financial, and energy-poverty KPIs at start, mid and end of the project.

- **STRATEGIC**

RECOMMENDATIONS			
DOs	Use deep EE renovation bundles to unlock grants and cut payback; default to Shared Savings unless housing association finance or tariff structure argues otherwise.	DON'Ts	Don't reduce tenants' benefits from EE renovations by increasing rent.
	Establish ESA to de-risk crowd investors and protect housing associations		Don't launch crowdfunding offers without ESCO, ESA, and agreed payback period

- **POLICY FRAMEWORK**

Relevant Policies	
International level	Not applicable
European level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>EPBD/EED;</i> ● <i>InvestEU</i> ● <i>Cohesion funds.</i>
National level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>ALTUM</i> ● <i>NBF</i> ● <i>National Plan for Social and Affordable Housing Construction (Piano Nazionale di Edilizia Abitativa)</i>

● **STAKEHOLDER ROLES AND ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK**

Stakeholder	Role	Type of Collaboration
Social housing association	Building owner, ESA account setter, protecting the interest of tenants	Data provision; PPP procurement; KPI reporting
ESCO	Design, build and operate the EE renovations	Energy audits; EPC; cover shortfalls up to guarantee
Crowdfunding platform organiser	Raise capital	During Pre-offer, offer and Post offer stages; annual reports of the performance of the EE renovations to the crowdfunding investors
Financial institutions	Provide loans and investments	Co-lending
Municipality	Grants, permitting and oversight	Align eligibility; streamline grant approvals

● **MAIN REFERENCES**

GOOD PRACTICES / SOME EXAMPLES	
Project	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>SUPER-i project</i>: Support the funding of EE (Energy Efficient) refurbishment of social housing stocks across Europe while increasing the share of renewable energy in the final energy consumption 2. <i>SocialWatt</i>: Tackle energy poverty in social housing by equipping energy utilities and obligated parties with data tools and schemes to design, finance, and deliver programmes that alleviate energy poverty in social housing 3. <i>RECO2ST</i>: Residential Retrofit assessment platform and demonstrations for near zero energy and CO2 emissions with optimum coST, health, comfort and environmental quality. 	
Web-site	
https://super-i-supershine.eu/ https://socialwatt.eu/ https://reco2st.eu/	
Paper	
<p>Zerilli, Paola Z and Djeddi, Ahmed (2025) <i>Optimising Public Private Partnership (PPP) contracts- A Minimum-CVaR Framework for Risk-Efficient Contract Design</i></p>	